

Name-bearing type specimens of Trichoptera (Insecta) in the Canadian National Collection of Insects, Arachnids & Nematodes (CNC), with a biography of Fernand Schmid

O. LONSDALE

Owen Lonsdale, Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada, 960 Carling Avenue, Ottawa, Ontario, K1A 0C6, Canada. E-mail: Owen.Lonsdale@agr.gc.ca

Abstract. A catalogue is provided for the name-bearing type specimens of Trichoptera held by the Canadian National Collection of Insects, Arachnids & Nematodes (CNC). All 993 specimens are holotypes, representing 27 families from 29 countries, especially India (746 specimens), Pakistan (79), Iran (33) and Canada (29). Six taxa are unplaced to family; one of these, the amber-preserved *Electralberta cretatica* Botoșăneanu & Wichard from Alberta, is the sole fossil specimen held. Holotypes of four taxa are considered lost: *Setodes ekachringa* Schmid (Leptoceridae); *Ylodes schmidi* Manuel & Nimmo (Leptoceridae); *Tinodes pseudorostocki* Botoșăneanu (Psychomyiidae); *Himalopsyche angnorbui sherpa* Schmid (Rhyacophilidae). Fernand Schmid and his contributions to the CNC are discussed. Schmid was the only CNC staff member ever hired to study Trichoptera, working at the CNC from 1963 to 1985. He designated 900 of the Trichoptera holotypes held at the CNC and he collected 908 of the CNC Trichoptera specimens that were designated as types.

A catalogue is presented for the name-bearing types of Trichoptera (Insecta) deposited at the Canadian National Collection of Insects, Arachnids & Nematodes (CNC). This is the third study in an ongoing series documenting name-bearing type specimens in the CNC for those taxa without associated research staff - that is, excluding Nematoda, Acari, Coleoptera, Diptera, Hemiptera/Thysanoptera, Hymenoptera and Lepidoptera. An outline of these catalogues, including a discussion of type specimens and an estimated total number of name-bearing types in the CNC, was provided by Lonsdale & Locke (2018).

All name-bearing types are holotypes, totalling 993 specimens from 29 countries: Afghanistan (1), Bolivia (1), Bosnia and Herzegovina (5), Canada (29), China (6), Colombia (1), Denmark (1), France (1), Greece (1), Guinea (4), India (746), Iran (33), Japan (15), Macedonia (6), Mexico (8), Nepal (1), Pakistan (79), Peru (3), Romania (1), Russia (1), Slovakia (1), Spain (22), Sri Lanka (1), Switzerland (5), Thailand (6), Turkey (1), U.S.A. (12), Ukraine (1), Yugoslavia (1). Of

these, only 33 are types for species presently considered to be junior synonyms of other taxa, resulting in the CNC holding type specimens for 6.6% of all valid Trichoptera species. Numerous other specimens held by the CNC were formerly syntypes of species described by Banks and Hagen, but these were reduced to the status of paralectotypes following the actions of Ross (1938).

Holotypes at the CNC represent twenty-seven families of Trichoptera (Table 1). Six types belong to species unplaced to family, including the single fossil type *Electralberta cretatica* Botoșăneanu & Wichard, an amber-preserved specimen from Alberta. Most types belong to the families Leptoceridae (259), Rhyacophilidae (184), Psychomyiidae (88), Hydroptilidae (75) and Philopotamidae (69).

Type specimens belonging to the following four taxa could not be located during this study and are presumed lost: *Setodes ekachringa* Schmid (Leptoceridae), *Ylodes schmidi* Manuel & Nimmo (Leptoceridae), *Tinodes pseudorostocki*

Botoșăneanu (Psychomyiidae), and *Himalopsyche angnorbui sherpa* Schmid (Rhyacophilidae).

As of August 2019, there are nearly 2,700 terminal taxa of Trichoptera in the CNC, but the actual number is certainly much higher because large numbers of specimens are still unidentified beyond order, family or genus, especially those collected in south Asia, where much of the fauna likely remains undescribed.

Fernand Schmid

The Trichoptera collection at the CNC is mostly the result of the personal collecting and curatorial efforts of a single highly productive researcher, and discussion of the collection would be incomplete without also mentioning him. Fernand Schmid (Figs. 14–18) was born in Sion, Switzerland on May 12, 1924. His father ran the print shop in Valais and wanted Fernand to continue in the printing business. Despite this, Fernand instead chose to save his money and move to nearby Lausanne to continue his academics.

Fernand published out of the Zoological Museum in Lausanne from 1947, where he received his License in Science (1951) and his DSc (1953) under the mentorship of J. de Beaumont and R. Matthey (Weaver & Nimmo 1999). He gravitated to butterflies (especially the birdwings), the aquatic Diptera and the aquatic orders Plecoptera and Trichoptera, but spent the vast majority of his graduate work and subsequent career on caddisflies. He revised a number of trichopteran taxa, predominantly within the family Limnephilidae, and his doctoral thesis was an aggregate of contributions to that family. Many of his early works were treatments of the Swiss and Spanish fauna (Weaver & Nimmo 1999), resulting in part from material he collected locally and during his 1950 expedition to Spain (Figs. 17, 18), but also of the neotropical fauna.

After receiving his doctoral degree, Fernand embarked on a decade of intensive field work organized through the University of Lausanne that would provide an enormous cache of research material that he would continue to draw upon for the rest of his highly productive life. He jour-

neyed to Pakistan (1953–1954) (Fig. 19), Sri Lanka (1954), Guinea, Yugoslavia, Macedonia, Bosnia & Herzegovina (all 1955), Iran (1955–1956), and of course, India (1958–1962) (Figs 20–34). His expeditions were often lengthy, and he spent at least nine months of the year in the field for four years straight in India, except for 1960, when he was there for seven months.

He embraced the nomadic, simple life that these travels afforded him, and enjoyed eating food collected in the field, including berries and wild honey. Field notes for his trips to India, preserved in the CNC as a series of small black softcover notebooks, have provided invaluable information for the present work. These books detail the specifics of his collection events, including notes on collection method, habitat and other potentially relevant locality information not present on his scant specimen labels (Fig. 35). Among his observations, he noted such things as Trichoptera being most active before sunset because of the heat of the day and collecting was most successful when it rained. In his notes for his 1958 trip to the Kumaon Region, he was accompanied by a zoologist, who had a liaison officer role, and two sherpas; he visited 290 biotopes, and captured about 15,000 Trichoptera that he estimates represents about 70% of the Trichoptera of that region. In his notes for the Sikkim expedition, he talked about travelling to avoid the monsoons, and how he collected around 60,000 specimens from 352 biotopes; about 80% of his material from that trip was Trichoptera representing about 380 species, or what he thought was 80% of the local fauna. He also recalled his Sri Lankan expedition, where he captured around 6,000 specimens representing approximately 270 Trichoptera species. Scans of these books are available from the author upon request, but preparations are presently being made to make these works freely available on the *Biodiversity Heritage Library* (<https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/>) as part of the *BHL Field Notes Project*. If field notes exist for his other expeditions, their location is unknown.

After returning from his final trip to India, he had the option to continue his work at Lausanne, but he instead decided to accept a position in

Ottawa at the Entomological Research Institute (ERI), which was part of the Canadian Department of Agriculture (now Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada). The ERI would later be called the Biosystematic Research Institute (BRI), and is today known as the Canadian National Collection of Insects, Arachnids & Nematodes (CNC). Fernand had to postpone his first day of work until later in 1963 because he needed time to recover from an illness he acquired in India. In the interim, he worked elsewhere within the Canadian Department of Agriculture, surveying the biting flies of Thunder Bay, Ontario.

Soon after moving to Ottawa, he joined a Swiss hiking club in Gatineau, which is in Quebec on the opposite side of the Ottawa River from Ottawa. While in the club, he was introduced by a friend to his future partner, Monique Mettan, who grew up only a few villages away from him in Switzerland. Soon thereafter, Fernand and Monique moved in together in a house on Craig Street in “the Glebe” neighbourhood in Ottawa.

Fernand worked as a research scientist at the CNC from 1963 to 1985, although he would continue his research at the collection after his retirement until his death in 1998 at the age of 74. He was the only scientist at the collection ever hired to work specifically on Trichoptera (Lonsdale & Huber 2012). His obituary was written by Weaver & Nimmo (1999), who provided a full list of Schmid’s publications and authored species, and several details on Fernand’s life not duplicated here. Schmid explored western Canada and the northwestern United States in 1965, but his fieldwork essentially discontinued after that point when he began the immense task of processing and studying his collections. He continued to travel frequently with Monique on many vacations, however, and he particularly enjoyed his time in the French Islands and Costa Rica.

Part of Fernand’s motivation for moving to Canada was apparently to escape the rigidity of Swiss culture, which was very much at odds with his personality – a unique combination of free-willed, headstrong and eccentric. Having a very

strong sense of self and perhaps little interest for society at large, he did not seem to have much time for externally imposed rules (including the law or social etiquette), but instead relied on his own internal moral compass. He did not engage in departmental activities more than was necessary and was often left to himself to pursue his work. Despite this, he was able to work well most of the time with his colleagues at the Collection and the adjacent offices of the Canadian Food Inspection Agency.

Similarly, Fernand did not interact much with the international community of trichopterists and rarely attended meetings. Of all the triennial International Symposia on Trichoptera convened during his lifetime, Fernand participated in only the 4th (1983, in Clemson, South Carolina, USA) and the 5th (1986, in Lyon, France) (J. Morse, personal communication). He did, however, sometimes openly engage in lively (and sometimes unfiltered) debate when he disagreed with what his peers had published. This apparent social distance must have been counterbalanced by a sense of fellowship, as many *Stactobia* were named for friends and colleagues, and in his last systematic paper (Schmid 1997), 43 species of *Psychomyia* were similarly named, being one of the most impressive examples of patronyms ever given in a single publication.

Unsurprisingly, Fernand preferred isolation and austerity, but this was offset by an inner life that derived satisfaction from his near constant work and other interests that he sometimes pursued to excess. His great loves were classical music and books, especially rare books and books on fine art. Most of what he read was written in French, but he was familiar with several languages and is reported to have read the Dead Sea Scrolls in their original untranslated text. His hobbies of cross-stitching and needlepoint overlapped with his love of fine art, using these techniques to reproduce several full-size paintings by the European masters. For much of the day, Fernand was also inseparable from his pipe (Fig. 14), which he enjoyed smoking while building small fires in his ashtray. Fernand additionally preferred

to sit on the floor, a habit he picked up while travelling in Iran and India, and he was a practicing naturalist.

Most of Fernand's free days were spent at his cottage in Wakefield (Fig. 14), just over the border in Quebec north of Gatineau, where he enjoyed the peace and solitude. Many of his publications were written while ensconced there. He took great effort to clear the land and prepare it in a manner typical of a Swiss mountain chalet, including gardens complete with lupines. He also gardened at his home on Craig Street, where he maintained a greenhouse that housed cacti, *Bougainvillea*, and over 50 epiphytic orchids that grew on the wall. In one year, he planted 500 crocuses on the property, resulting in a spectacular spring emergence.

Schmid worked prodigiously on his systematic papers, producing 111 publications on Trichoptera that included descriptions of 1,442 species groups (Weaver & Nimmo 1999), representing almost 10% of all known Trichoptera species. The majority of Schmid's types are held at the CNC, including 900 Trichoptera holotypes that represent 62.4% of those he designated during his entire career. Schmid himself collected 908 Trichoptera specimens that ended up being designated as name-bearing types deposited at the CNC. These specimens were collected in 12 countries: Bosnia & Herzegovina (4), Canada (3), Guinea (4), India (744), Iran (33), Macedonia (6), Pakistan (79), Spain (21), Sri Lanka (1), Switzerland (5), the United States of America (7) and Yugoslavia (1).

Outside of Trichoptera, the CNC holds 37 additional type specimens collected by Schmid: 1 Dermaptera, 30 Diptera, 3 Hymenoptera, 1 Lepidoptera and 2 Megaloptera. Nineteen Diptera types of the family Thaumaleidae in the CNC were designated by Schmid, all but one of which he collected. The remaining thaumaleid types designated by Schmid, which were listed by Schmid (1970c), ended up at the California Academy of Sciences.

Schmid's species names should be readily recognizable to Trichoptera workers, even if they

do not know the individual names specifically, as these names tend to be characteristically lengthy, unwieldy and/or confusingly similar. While this interpretation is admittedly subjective, Schmid's distinctive naming system often led him to regularly misspell the names on his own type labels and/or in his publications. At least in the case of *Leptocerus sukhabddha* Schmid, misspellings necessitate a nomenclatural act to select the correct original spelling of the name. Many of these names belong to Schmid's numerous Indian species, which Holzenthal & Andersen (2007) noted were derived from Sanskrit (and subsequently Latinized to varying degrees of success). An interesting example of Schmid's naming system is his 1983 revision of the genus *Stactobia*, where he named most of his many new species for characters in J.R.R. Tolkien's book *The Hobbit*, which have names that are mostly short and highly similar. This playfulness with his taxa and his prodigious output until his last days indicate a love for Trichoptera and systematic work that the CNC, among other collections, certainly benefited from. His contributions were recognized by the community in part by dozens of patronyms in his honour. Types of both species of the genus *Fernandoschmidia* Holzenthal & Andersen are deposited in the CNC, and types for nine species that bear his name are also deposited there (see Figs. 3–6, for example).

While Schmid deposited or perhaps sold much of his collection to the CNC, large portions were also apparently sold or donated elsewhere. These specimens, for the most part, belong to specific orders or families, or they belong to collections from specific geographic regions. Unfortunately, no documentation regarding these transfers can be located, and no justification can be found to explain apparent exceptions for specimens from these collections retained by the CNC, but they are provisionally accepted until relevant paperwork is discovered. The Royal Ontario Museum apparently purchased types of only two families – Phryganeidae and Limnephilidae – although specimens of four species of Limnephilidae collected and described by Schmid were retained for the CNC: *Grammotaulius alascensis* Schmid, *G.*

subborealis Schmid, *Asynarchus tibetanus* Schmid, and *Limnephilus tibeticus* Schmid. Name-bearing types of species from Sri Lanka and the Neotropics were sold to the National Museum of Natural History in Washington, D.C., although the Sri Lankan *Gunungiella madakumbura* Schmid was retained for the CNC. A portion of Schmid's Pakistani material was deposited in the Musée de Zoologie, Lausanne, according to the museum's website, where it was likely either left behind or sold by Schmid.

In addition to his own specimens, Schmid frequently retained types he designated from new species sent to him by other collectors. These were incorporated into the CNC after he moved to Ottawa, but prior to this they were kept in his personal collection. Specimens are mostly paratypes, but several name-bearing types were also incorporated as such, including some Neotropical specimens. His approach to name-bearing type retention was irregular, where types from one collector (e.g., Foerster) in a single publication may have ultimately been sent to multiple depositories or back to the collector, but this may have been by individual arrangement.

MATERIALS & METHODS

Specimen entries follow that outlined in Lonsdale & Locke (2018), including the inclusion of alphanumeric codes. These codes include at the very least a unique identifier beginning with "CNC" that corresponds to a database entry. Other numbers may include the obsolete CNC type numbers ("CNC No." / "CNC Type No."), which are not unique and sometimes applied to multiple specimens in the type series.

All specimen records can be located by unique identifier or taxonomic name in the searchable CNC Database, which is available online at <https://cnc.agr.gc.ca/taxonomy/TaxonMain.php>; high-resolution photographs of all pinned types, including labels, are appended to the specimen records.

Specimens are presented alphabetically by original specific epithet within each family. Text

as it appears on labels is presented fully in the "Verbatim" field, with the present author's notes given in square brackets; labels including identifications or type information are included verbatim in the "Determination" field. Also as in Lonsdale & Locke (2018), the field "Interpreted data" will "use contemporary geopolitical units and provide latitude and longitude where named localities could be verified and geocoded with confidence, although the exact locations of field sites around these points are expected to differ somewhat; when a municipality is given as the collection site, latitude and longitude are derived from the approximate centre of the municipality. It will incorporate additional locality information from published descriptions and other sources, [and] convert feet to meters (when provided)". Elevation is only provided if stated directly on the collection label, and not added from either publications or field notes if otherwise available.

Geocoding was comparatively simple for Schmid's trips to Iran and Pakistan, as he published maps of his travels in subsequent publications, and the roads traversed in Pakistan are usually bordered by high mountains that limit accessibility to surrounding regions. No such maps exist for his more extensive travels in India, however, which occurred in more open and densely populated areas that made attempts to retrace his steps more difficult. To complicate matters, placenames recorded by Schmid sometimes also appear to have been misspelled or written phonetically, making them difficult or impossible to find on maps. Aside from these misspellings, verbatim and interpreted data will sometimes also differ severely because Schmid's original labels are sparse and predate the construction of modern political subdivisions for some countries, including India, Iran and Pakistan, which have undergone much restructuring since his visits.

It must also be noted that there are numerous discrepancies between Schmid's labels and his published data, further contributing to differences between verbatim and interpreted data. There are many transcription errors, especially for dates, and labels were sometimes incorrectly applied to specimens. There are also numerous misspellings

Table 1. Name-bearing types of Trichoptera deposited in the CNC.

FAMILY	# name-bearing types (holotypes) in CNC	# types designated by Schmid	# types collected by Schmid
Apataniidae	33	28	22
Beraeidae	3	2	3
Brachycentridae	14	13	13
Calamoceratidae	1	0	0
Dipseudopsidae	9	0	9
Ecnomidae	1	1	1
Glossosomatidae	31	29	27
Goeridae	24	24	22
Helicopsychidae	26	26	26
Hydrobiosidae	11	10	7
Hydropsychidae	34	30	25
Hydroptilidae	75	74	75
Lepidostomatidae	26	9	23
Leptoceridae	259	252	252
Limnephilidae	17	4	2
Molannidae	8	0	8
Odontoceridae	2	0	2
Philopotamidae	69	65	66
Phryganeidae	3	0	0
Polycentropodidae	10	7	6
Psychomyiidae	88	87	87
Ptilocolepidae	1	1	1
Rhyacophilidae	184	178	169
Sericostomatidae	3	3	3
Stenopsychidae	5	5	5
Uenoidae	6	3	5
Xiphocentronidae	44	44	44
<i>Unplaced</i>	6	5	5
TOTAL	993	900	908

on type labels, and a smaller number of misspellings in his publications (see entry below for *Leptocerus sukhabddha*, for example). Corrections to these errors and the identification of misspellings are made where possible, but a number of issues require further examination by taxonomic experts for proper resolution, if resolution is indeed

possible – see entries below for *Rhyacophila muktepa* Schmid, *Setodes ekachringa* Schmid and *Stactobia grolin* Schmid, among many others. When discrepancies between label and published collection data were encountered for Indian specimens, Schmid's field notes were used to aid in the verification of those data. It must also be

assumed that other errors, including those resulting from the initial misapplication of collection labels, may never be detected.

Other serious issues involve the improper designation of name-bearing types, exasperated by Schmid's tendency sometimes to designate types only indirectly, or to list only partial or no collection data in his descriptions. Elsewhere, holotypes are not explicitly chosen (e.g., *Hydroptila armathai* Schmid, *Agapetus turcomanorum* Schmid), or the specimen labeled as the holotype may not actually represent the actual type as designated in the description (e.g., *Setodes atiloma* Schmid, *Setodes bhimachringa* Schmid, *Psychomyia neboissi* Schmid, *Hydroptila fuentaldeala* Schmid, *Hydropsyche sakarawaka* Schmid). Resolution of these issues is not attempted here.

NAME-BEARING TYPE SPECIMEN CATALOGUE

APATANIIDAE

adhanya Schmid, 1968d, *Notania*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Sikkim Manu 10-V-1959 F.Schmid /examined W. Mey 1999/ CNC358536.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Manu, 27° 31'2"N 88°34'58"E, 10.v.1959, F. Schmid, CNC358536.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Notania adhanya* 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11199 *Not. adhanya*.

alberta Nimmo, 1971, *Apatania*

holotype+allotype (2 male/female, ethyl alcohol)

Verbatim: RAPIDS CK., T.C.Hwy. GAP, Alta Bridge, 10.30.a.m. 15/6/67, A.NIMMO / CNC 165736.

Interpretive data: **CANADA. Alberta**: Rapids Creek, Trans-Canada Highway, Gap, 10:30 AM, 15.vi.1967, A. Nimmo, CNC165736.

Determination: HOLOTYPE ♂ CNC No. 10,584 APATANIA ALBERTA NIMMO / ALLOTYPE ♀ CNC No.10,584 APATANIA ALBERTA NIMMO.

angarica (Schmid, 1953), *Baicalina* [Radema]

Valid name: *Baicalina bellicosa* Martynov, 1914 holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Ст. Танхий [=St. Tanhii] 3.VI.1913 Д. Гон [=D. Gon.] / CNC 481657.

Interpretive data: **RUSSIA**. Lake Baikal, 3.vi. 1913, D. Gon., CNC481657.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Radema angarica* 1952 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11450 *Rad. angarica*.

Comments: Description notes collection locality as "station Tanchoi".

avikritanga Schmid 1968d, *Moropsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Nungba 25-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 280210.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Nungba, 24°44'59"N 93°25'20"E, 25.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC280210.

Determination: Holotype ♂ *Moropsyche avikritanga* F. Schmid 1968 / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11197 *Mor. avikritanga*.

Comments: Description incorrectly listed date of collection as the 22nd.

avyddhagada Schmid 1968d, *Apatania*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Mangu Chatti 20-V-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 280198.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Pauri Garhwal District, Mangu Chatti, 20.v.1958, F. Schmid, CNC280198.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Apatania avyddhagada* F. Schmid 1968 / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11185 *Ap. avyddhagada*

bhimagada Schmid 1968d, *Apatania*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Sangti 12-IV-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 280199.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Sangti, 27°24'14"N 92°18'17"E, 12.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 280199.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Apatania bhimagada* F. Schmid 1968 / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11186 *Ap. bhimagada*.

carpathica Schmid 1954, Apatania

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Chomiak, pot. Barani. 31.-7.-1905 Dz. / CNC 280061.

Interpretive data: **UKRAINE.** Chomiak, pot. Barani., 31.vii.1905, Dziedzielewicz, CNC 280061.

Determination: *A. meridiana*, McL. / holotype ♂ *Apatania carpathica* 1952 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11452 Ap. *carpathica*.

Comments: Schmid (1954) did not list his material examined in the species description, but noted that the specimens were collected in "Czarnohora", a Carpathian mountain range. The locality of "Chomiak" likely refers to Mt. Khomyak (48°22'3.1"N, 24°29'47.3"E), in Ivano-Frankivsk Oblast.

chandrabuchita Schmid 1968d, Moropsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Laitlyngkot 17-III-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 280212.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** East Khasi Hills District, Laitlyngkot, 25°26'44.01"N 91°50'23"E, 17.iii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC280212.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Moropsyche Chandrabuchita* 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11194 Mor. *chandrabuchita*.

charadija Schmid 1968d, Apataniana

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Rata 14-IX-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 280200.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Pauri Garhwal District, Rata, 14.ix.1958, F. Schmid, CNC280200.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Apatania charadija* [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11187 Ap. *charadija*.

Comments: Locality further listed as "Kumaon, Almora" in description.

cidoipes (Schmid 1968d), Allomyia [Imania]

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: U.S.A., Wash. Whatcom Co. Baker Lodge 1-VII-1965 F.Schmid / CNC 758896.

Interpretive data: **USA. Washington:** Whatcom Co., Baker Lodge, 48°51'55.69"N 121°40'27.28"W, along small torrents descending from the sides of Mount Baker [from description], 1.vii.1965, F. Schmid, CNC758896.

Determination: HOLOTYPE ♂ CNCNo. 9646 *Imnia* 1967 *cidoipes* Schm.

Comments: Antennae glued on card paper on pin.

crassa Schmid 1953, Apatania

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Hokkaido Kuwayama / CNC 280054.

Interpretive data: **JAPAN. Hokkaido:** Kuwayama, CNC280054.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Apatania crassa* 1952 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11451 Ap. *crassa*.

devisaraspali Schmid 1968d, Apatania

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Lhamo Tso 25-VI-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 280204.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Lhamo Tao, 28°0'27"N 88°45'23"E, 25.vi.1959, F. Schmid, CNC280204.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Apatania devisaraspali* 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11183 Ap. *devisaraspali*.

dirghabahu Schmid 1968d, Apatania

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Tangshing 5-X-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 280203.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Tangshing, 5.x.1959, F. Schmid, CNC280203.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Apatania dirghabahu* 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11184 Ap. *dirghabahu*.

dirghakarni Schmid 1968d, Moropsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Rumkheng 20-23-III-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 280211.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** United Jaintia and Khasi Hills [now divided into East and West Khasi Hills Districts and East and West Jaintia Hills Districts], Rumkheng, 20-

23.iii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC280211.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Moropsyche dirghakarni* 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11189 Mor. dirghakarni.

gairichringiya* Schmid 1968d, *Moropsyche
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Sirohi Kashong 7-VI-1960 F. Schmid / CNC 280213.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Siruhi Kashong, 25°6'23.19"N 94°27'28.51"E, 7.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC280213.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Moropsyche gairichringiya* [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11195 Mor. gairichringiya.

girautcharichnu* Schmid 1968d, *Moropsyche
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Nyukmadong 21-IV-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 280215.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Nyukmadung, 27°25'1"N 92°7'57"E, 21.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 280215.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Moropsyche girautcharichnu* 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11193 Mor. girautcharichnu.

girikchit* Schmid 1968d, *Moropsyche
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Sirohi Kashong 7-VI-1960 F. Schmid / CNC 280214.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Siruhi Kashong, 25°6'23.19"N 94°27'28.51"E, 7.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC280214.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Moropsyche girikchit* 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11196 Mor. girikchit.

***hector* (Nimmo 1971), *Allomyia* [*Imania*]**
holotype (1 male/female, ethyl alcohol)
Verbatim: SUNSHINE LODGE, BANFF NAT.PK., ALTA, W.R.M.MASON 9/7/62 / CNC 165743.
Interpretive data: **CANADA. Alberta**: Banff National Park, Sunshine Lodge, 51°10'26.25"N 115°34'15.99"W, 9.vii.1962, W.R.M. Mason, CNC165743.

Determination: IMANIA HECTOR NIMMO N.SP. HOLOTYPE ♂ ALLOTYPE ♀.
Comments: Male HT wings slide mounted.

helvetica* Schmid 1954, *Apatania
holotype (1 female, pinned)
Verbatim: Suisse-Valais Zinai 20-VIII-1951 F. Schmid / CNC 280195.
Interpretive data: **SWITZERLAND. Valais**: Zinai, 46°8'3.33"N 7°37'43.26"E, 20.viii.1951, F. Schmid, CNC280195.
Determination: holotype ♀ *Apatania helvetica* 1952 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11455 Ap. helvetica.

ishikawai* Schmid 1964a, *Apatania
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: JAPAN, Nagano, Isedaki, Mt.Kiso Komagadake, 24.VIII.1962 R. Ishikawa / CNC 280055.
Interpretive data: **JAPAN. Nagano**: Isedaki, Mt. Kiso, Komagadake, 35°47'22.05"N 137°48'16.14"E, 24.viii.1962, R. Ishikawa, CNC 280055.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Apatania ishikawai* 1967 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11449 Ap. ishikawai.

itarichta* Schmid 1968d, *Notania
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Sikkim Dethang [sic] 1-IV-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 280223.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Deythang, 27°12'19"N 88°13'33.66"E, 1.iv.1959, F. Schmid, CNC280223.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Notania itharichta* [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11200 Not. itarichta.

kalariana* Schmid 1961, *Apatania
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Frontier Province] Lulu Sar 10-12-VII-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 280207.
Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa**: Lulusar Lake, 35°4'54"N 73°55'32.01"E, 10-12.vii.1953, F. Schmid, CNC 280207.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Apatania kalariana*
1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11447 Ap. kalariana.

kriča* Schmid 1968d, *Notania

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Nyukmadong 18-IV-
1961 F.Schmid / CNC 280224.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
West Kameng District, Nyukmadung, 27°25'1
"N 92°7'57"E, 18.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC
280224.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Notania kriča* [sic]
1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11198 Not. kriča.

kričnaruna* Schmid 1968d, *Moropsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Sikkim Lathong 15-V-1959 F.Schmid /
CNC 280216.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Latong, 27°
39'40"N 88°36'5"E, 15.v.1959, F. Schmid,
CNC280216.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Moropsyche kričnā-*
runa [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE
CNCNo. 11192 Mor. kričharuna [sic].

***moharamana* Schmid 1961, *Apatania* [*Apatani-*
ana]**

holotype (1 female, pinned)
Verbatim: Cachem.et Jam. Shigar 1-3-X-1953
F.Schmid / CNC 280208

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu &**
Kashmir: Shigar, 35°25'37"N 75°43'53"E, 1-
3.x.1953, F. Schmid, CNC280208.

Determination: holotype ♀ *Apatania moharamana*
1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11448 Ap. moharamana.

nielsenii* Schmid 1954, *Apatania

holotype (1 female, pinned)
Verbatim: Danemark / Rold Kilde April Ank
[illegible] Nielsen / CNC 280196.

Interpretive data: **DENMARK. Nordjylland**:
Rold Kilde, 56°46'0"N 9°53'0"E, April, A.
Nielsen, CNC280196.

Determination: HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11456 Ap.
nielsenii / holotype ♀ *Apatania nielsenii* 1952 F.
Schmid.

schmidii* Nishimoto 1988, *Apatania

holotype (1 male, ethyl alcohol)
Verbatim: NEPAL, N slope above Syabru [sic]
3800m 17-19.IV.85 A.Smetana N234 Trichop
/ CNC 165738.

Interpretive data: **NEPAL**. N slope above Syafru,
28°7'12"N 85°24'0"E, 3800m, 17-19.iv.1985,
A. Smetana, CNC165738.

Determination: *Apatania schmidii* / HOLOTYPE
[taped to outside of vial].

stylata* Navás 1916, *Apatania

holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: France / Benasque 26.VII.15 / CNC
280190.

Interpretive data: **SPAIN. Huesca**: Benasque, at
the Hospital, 42°41'2"N 0°36'45"E, 26.vii.
1915, CNC280190.

Determination: *Apatania stylata* Nav., Navás S.J.
det. / Typus / holotype ♂ *Apatania stylata* Nav.
/ HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11454 Ap. stylata.

Comments: While one of the male's locality labels
includes a typewritten "France", separate from
the handwritten label including "Benasque",
the description notes collection "at the hos-
pital", indicating collection in Benasque itself,
a town in Hueca Province, Spain.

***thomasi* (Nimmo 1977), *Allomyia* [*Imania*]**

holotype (1 male, ethyl alcohol)
Verbatim: Rowe Bk, nr Lower Rowe Lk, 6350',
Wat.Nat. Pk, Alberta.12/6/75. D.B.Donald /
CNC 165746.

Interpretive data: **CANADA. Alberta**: Waterton
Lakes National Park, Rowe Lk. nr Lower
Rowe Lake, 49°3'9"N 114°3'27"W, 1935m,
12.vi.1975, D.B. Donald, CNC165746.

Determination: **IMANIA THOMASI** Nimmo
HOLOTYPE ♂ CNC No. 15163 TRICHO-
PTERA: LIMNAPHILIDAE.

Comments: Right-side wings on slide.

trikonakarni* Schmid 1968d, *Moropsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Sikkim Singbeng 14-X-1959 F.Schmid
/ CNC 280222.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Singbeng, 14.
x.1959, F. Schmid, CNC280222.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Moropsyche trikona-*
karni 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11190 Mor. *trikonakarni*.

tsudai* Schmid 1954, *Apatania

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Japon Takasegawa Minamiazumi
Nagano-Ken 5-V-1951 M.Tsuda / CNC
280185.

Interpretive data: **JAPAN. Hokkaido**: Nagano
Prefecture, Takasegawa, Minamia Zumi, 36°
29'53.19"N 137°50'31.92"E, 5.v.1951, M.
Tsuda, CNC280185.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Apatania tsudai* 1952
F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11453 Ap.
tsudai.

Comments: Genitalia and remainder of body
mounted on separate slides on same pin.

urdhvakarni* Schmid 1968d, *Moropsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Sirohi Kashong 11-13-
VII-1960 F. Schmid / CNC 280219.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Siruhi
Kashong, 25°6'23.19"N 94°27'28.51"E 11-13.
vii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC280219.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Moropsyche urdhva-*
karni 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11188 Mor. *urdhvakarni*.

vanegudha* Schmid 1968d, *Moropsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Chug 15-IV-1961
F.Schmid / CNC 280221.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
West Kameng District, Chug, 27°25'4"N 92°
14'3"E, 15.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC280221.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Moropsyche vane-*
gudha 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11191 Mor. *vanegudha*.

BERAEIDAE

malahiguerra* Schmid 1952, *Beraea

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Espagne (Ma.) Cercedilla 8-VII-1950
F. Schmid / CNC 280390.

Interpretive data: **SPAIN. Madrid**: Cercedilla,

40°44'26.01"N 4°3'25"W, 8.vii.1950, F.
Schmid, CNC280390.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Beraea malahiguerra*
1951 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
12516 *Beraea malahiguerra*.

malatebrera* Schmid 1952, *Beraea

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Espagne (Ma.) Cercedilla 8-VII-1950
F. Schmid / CNC 280389.

Interpretive data: **SPAIN. Madrid**: Cercedilla,
40°44'26.01"N 4°3'25"W, 8.vii.1950, F.
Schmid, CNC280389.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Beraea malatebrera*
1951 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
12515 *Micrasema malatebrera*.

schmidi* Botoșăneanu 1960, *Beraemyia

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Bosnie Trnovo 23-VII-1955 F.Schmid /
CNC 280395.

Interpretive data: **BOSNIA AND HERZEG-**
OVINA. Trnovo, 43°39'55"N 18°22'24"E, 23.
vii.1955, F. Schmid, CNC280395.

Determination: *Beraemyia schmidi* Bots. Holo-
type ♂.

BRACHYCENTRIDAE

abhavyam* Schmid 1992, *Micrasema

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Chamiteng 24-VIII-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 280419.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Chamiteng,
24.viii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC280419.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Micrasema abhavyam*
1991 F. Schmid / Holotype ♂ *Micrasema ab-*
havyam Schm. CNC 21304.

adhacharam* Schmid 1992, *Micrasema

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Mattiyang 17-VI-1960
F.Schmid / CNC 280420.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Mattiyang,
17.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC280420.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Micrasema adha-*
charam 1991 F. Schmid / Holotype ♂ *Micra-*
sema adhacharam Schm. CNC 21298 [tye
number listed a "21304" in description].

adhiram Schmid 1992, *Micrasema*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Sikkim Tikjak 7-IV-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 280411.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Tikjak, 7.iv.1959, F. Schmid, CNC280411.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Micrasema adhiram* 1991 F. Schmid / Holotype ♂ *Micrasema adhiram* Sch. CNC 21301.

apratitam Schmid 1992, *Micrasema*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Chug 17-IV-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 280410.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Chug, 27°25'4"N 92°14'3"E, 17.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 280410.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Micrasema apratitam* 1991 F. Schmid / Holotype ♂ *Micrasema apratitam* Sch. CNC 21296.

asajjanam Schmid 1992, *Micrasema*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Rahung 25-IV-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 280413.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Rahung, 27°18'37"N 92°23'41"E, 25.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 280413.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Micrasema asajjanam* 1991 F. Schmid / Holotype ♂ *Micrasema asajjanam* Sch. CNC 21302.

avadhiritam Schmid 1992, *Micrasema*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: U.J.K.H. [=United Khasi and Jaintia Hills] Syndai / CNC 280416.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: Jaintia Hills District, Syndai, 25°11'8.01"N 92°8'25"E, 14.xii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC280416.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Micrasema avadhiritam* 1991 F. Schmid / Holotype ♂ *Micrasema avadhiritam* Sch. CNC 21303.

cenerentola Schmid 1952, *Micrasema*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Espagne (Av.) Lac de Gredos 16-23-

VII-1950 F. Schmid / CNC 280381.

Interpretive data: **SPAIN. Ávila**: above Lac de Gredos, 16-23.vii.1950, F. Schmid, CNC 280381.

Determination: holotype ♂ *M. cenerentola* 1950 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12513 *Micrasema cenerentola*.

dabhram Schmid 1992, *Micrasema*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Gaurikund 9-10-V-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 280412.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Rudraprayag District, Gaurikund, 30°39'10"N 79°1'33"E, 9-10.v.1958, F. Schmid, CNC280412.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Micrasema dabhram* 1991 F. Schmid / Holotype ♂ *Micrasema dabhram* Sch. CNC 21300.

gabusi Schmid 1952, *Micrasema*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Espagne (Gr.) Ht val du Naute 9-VIII-1950 F.Schmid / CNC 280383.

Interpretive data: **SPAIN. Granada**: Ht val du Naute, 9.viii.1950, F. Schmid, CNC280383.

Determination: holotype ♂ *M. gabusi* 1950 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12514 *Micrasema gabusi*.

jihmam Schmid 1992, *Micrasema*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Teng [sic] 12-V-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 280417.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Tung, 27°32'37"N 88°38'54"E, 12.v.1959, F. Schmid, CNC 280417.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Micrasema jihmam* 1991 F. Schmid / Holotype ♂ *Micrasema jihmam* Sch. CNC 21295.

karunam Schmid 1992, *Micrasema*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Chingsao 14-VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 280415.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Chingsao, 14.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC280415.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Micrasema karunam* 1991 F. Schmid / Holotype ♂ *Micrasema karunam* Sch. CNC 21297.

Comments: Locality possibly Chingshou, near Mapum (25°8'21"N 94°32'42"E).

kripanam Schmid 1992, Micrasema

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Dirang Dzong 21-22-VII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 280414.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Derangzong, 27°20' 31"N 92°16'22"E, 21-22.vii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC280414.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Micrasema kripanam* 1991 F. Schmid / Holotype ♂ *Micrasema kripanam* Schm. CNC 21299.

kuwayamai Wiggins, Tani & Tanida 1985, Brachycentrus

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: JAPAN, Fukushima, Ura-bandai, May 17, 1957 R. Ishikawa / CNC 280373.

Interpretive data: **JAPAN. Honshu:** Fukushima, Ura-bandai, 37°39'4"N 140°3'45"E, 17.v.1957, R. Ishikawa, CNC280373.

Determination: HOLOTYPE *Brachycentrus kuwayamai* Wiggins, Tani,& Tanida / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 19806 *Brachycentrus kuwayamai* Wig.

salardum Schmid 1952, Micrasema

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Espagne (Lér.) Salardu 26-VI-1950 F. Schmid / CNC 280398.

Interpretive data: **SPAIN. Lleida:** Salardu, 42° 42'26"N 0°54'4"E, 26.vi.1950, F. Schmid, CNC280398.

Determination: holotype M. *salardum* 1950 F. Schmid HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12512 *Micrasema salardum*.

Comments: Published date of collection 27.vi. 1950.

CALAMOCERATIDAE

quincemil Prather 2004, Banyallarga

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Peru, Cozco Quincemil VIII.1962 L.Pena / UMSP000065236 / CNC 311404.

Interpretive data: **PERU. Cusco:** Quincemil, 13° 13'2.86"S 70°44'27.48"W, viii.1962, L.E. Peña, CNC311404.

Determination: Holotype ♂ *Banyallarga (Histricoverpa) quincemil* Prather.

DIPSEUDOPSIDAE

bonaventura Malicky 2009, Pseudoneureclipsis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (C.) [=Cachar District] Bandarkhal 9-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236465.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Assam:** Cachar District, Bandarkhal, 25°3'30"N 92°48'4"E, 9.v. 1960, F. Schmid, CNC236465.

Determination: *Pseudoneureclipsis bonaventura* MALICKY 2009 HOLOTYPUS.

diogenes Malicky 2009, Pseudoneureclipsis

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.D.M.N.C.H.) [=United district of Mikir Hills and North Cachar] Sirtrang 28-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 481649.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Assam:** [United District now treated as separate Mikir Hills and Karbi Anglong Districts], Sirtrang, 28.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC481649.

Determination: *Pseudoneureclipsis diogenes* MALICKY 2009 HOLOTYPUS.

ezbon Malicky 2009, Pseudoneureclipsis

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Shilliang Myntang 21-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236467.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia Hills District, Shilliangmyntang, 25°33'55"N 92°21'27"E, 21.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 236467.

Determination: *Pseudoneureclipsis ezbon* MALICKY 2009 HOLOTYPUS.

hieronymus Malicky 2009, Pseudoneureclipsis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Vangai Chungpao 21-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236468.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Vangai

Chungpao, 24°45'23"N 93°10'40"E, 21.v. 1960, F. Schmid, CNC236468.
Determination: Pseudoneureclipsis hieronymus MALICKY 2009 HOLOTYPUS.

higleri Malicky 2009, Pseudoneureclipsis
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Thangrain 22-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236469.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: Jaintia Hills District, Thangrain, 25°34'48"N 92°26'22"E, 22.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236469.
Determination: Pseudoneureclipsis higleri MALICKY 2009 HOLOTYPUS.

porphyrios Malicky 2009, Pseudoneureclipsis
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal District, Duldhar 2-VI-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 236473.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Pauri Garhwal District, Duldhar, 2.vi.1958, F. Schmid, CNC236473.
Determination: Pseudoneureclipsis porphyrios MALICKY 2009 HOLOTYPUS.

sabta Malicky 2009, Pseudoneureclipsis
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Kunjankhuzi 2-I-1962 F.Schmid / CNC 236475.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Madras** [likely in either present day Kerala or Tamil Nadu State], Kunjankhuzi, 2.i.1962, F. Schmid, CNC 236475.
Determination: Pseudoneureclipsis sabta MALICKY 2009 HOLOTYPUS.

schmidi Weaver & Malicky 1994, Dipseudopsis
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Kaiphundai 20-V-1960 F.Schmid / Weaver illus. / CNC 236560.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Kaiphundai, 24°47'51"N 93°14'1"E, 20.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236560.
Determination: Dipseudopsis ♂ schmidi n. sp. Weaver & Malicky / HOLOTYP ♂ Dipseudopsis schmidi Weaver & Malicky / Dipseudopsis schmidi Weaver Holotype ♂ CNC [type no.] 21623.

ziphjon Malicky 2009, Pseudoneureclipsis
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Ottakada 5-I-1962 F.Schmid / CNC 236477.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu**: Othakadai, 10°24'15.81"N 78°14'20.66"E, 5.i.1962, F. Schmid, CNC236477.
Determination: Pseudoneureclipsis ziphjon MALICKY 2009 HOLOTYPUS.

ECNOMIDAE

penjabi Schmid 1961, Ecnomus
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Pakistan (Penjab) Hassan Abdal 27-XII-1954 F.Schmid / CNC 236568.
Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Punjab**: Hassan Abdal, 33°49'10"N 72°41'21"E, 27.xii.1954, F. Schmid, CNC236568.
Determination: holotype ♂ Ecnomus penjabi 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYP CNCNo. 12341 Ecnomus penjabi.

GLOSSOSOMATIDAE

abhikhara Schmid 1959a, Glossosoma
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Frontier Province] Besal 8-9-VII-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 235833.
Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa**: Besal, 35°3'5"N 73°56'16"E, 8-9.vii.1953, F. Schmid, CNC235833.
Determination: holotype ♂ Glossosoma abhikhara 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYP CNCNo. 11111 Gl. abhikhara [sic].

abhisares Schmid 1971, Glossosoma
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Kedarnath 13-15-V-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 235834.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Pauri Garhwal District, Kedarnath, 30°44'4"N 79°4'1"E, 13-15.v.1958, F. Schmid, CNC235834.
Determination: holotype ♂ Glossosoma abhisarès [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYP CNCNo. 11109 Gl. abhisares.

agarenorum Schmid 1959b, Glossosoma
holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Iran (Ost.1) Hassankif 28-IX-1956
F.Schmid / CNC 235845.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. Mazandaran**: Hassan-
kif, 36°30'28"N 51°9'42"E, 28.ix.1956, F.
Schmid, CNC235845.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Glossoma agarenorum*
1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11128 Gl. agarenorum.

dentatum akhandam Schmid 1971, *Glossosoma*
holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Talung Dzong 26-III-
1961 F.Schmid / CNC 235835.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
Kameng Frontier Division [now divided into
the districts of Tawang, East Kameng and
West Kameng], Talung Dzong, 26.iii.1961, F.
Schmid, CNC235835.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gloss. dentatum akh-*
anda [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC
No. 111124 [sic – actually 11124] Gl. *dentat-*
um akhandam.

ambhi Schmid 1959a, *Glossosoma*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Cachem. et Jam. Mahthantir Gah 9-10-
VIII-1954 F.Schmid / CNC 235846.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu &**
Kashmir: Mahthantir Gah, 9-10.viii.1954, F.
Schmid, CNC235846.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Glossosoma ambhi*
1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11110 Gl. ambhi.

Comments: Locality a stream past Chhantir Gah,
possibly at 36°34'20N 73°44'32"E.

antikena Schmid 1959a, *Agapetus*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Fron-
tier Province] Besal 8-9-VII-1953 F.Schmid /
CNC 235929.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakh-**
tunkhwa: Besal, 35°3'5"N 73°56'16"E, 8-9.
vii.1953, F. Schmid, CNC235929.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Agapetus antikena*
1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12314 *Agapetus*
antikena HOLOTYPE.

antiyaka Schmid 1959a, *Agapetus*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Cachem.et Jam. Teru 15-17-IX-1954
F.Schmid / CNC 235927.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu &**
Kashmir: Teru, 36°10'50.01"N 72°45'
38.01"E, 15-17.ix.1954, F. Schmid, CNC
235927.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Agapetus antiyaka*
1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12315 *Agapetus*
antiyaka HOLOTYPE.

atchintitam Schmid 1971, *Glossosoma*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Chug 14-IV-1961
F.Schmid / CNC 235847.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
West Kameng District, Chug, 27°25'4"N
92°14'3"E, 14.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC
235847.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Glossoma atchintitam*
1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11112 Gl. atchintitam.

Comments: Description incorrectly stated date of
collection as the 22nd.

atyalpa (Schmid 1991a), *Padunia* [*Poeciloptila*]

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Khasi-Jaintia
Hills District] Barato 24-IV-1960 F.Schmid /
CNC 235887.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: Jaintia
Hills District, Barato, 25°36'21"N 92°27'5"E,
24.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC235887.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Poeciloptila atyalpa*
1991 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Poeciloptila*
atyalpa CNC No. 21236.

bahukantakam Schmid 1971, *Glossosoma*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Nyukmadong 18-IV-
1961 F.Schmid / CNC 235848.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
West Kameng District, Nyukmadung, 27°25'
1"N 92°7'57"E, 18.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC
235848.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Glossoma bahukan*

takam 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11120 Gl. bahukantakam.

beaumonti Schmid 1947, Glossosoma

Valid name: Glossosoma bifidum McLachlan 1879

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Suisse-Vaud Vallorbe 27-VI-1943 F. Schmid / CNC 235866.

Interpretive data: **SWITZERLAND. Vaud:** Vallorbe, 46°42'43"N 6°22'46"E, 27.vi.1943, F. Schmid, CNC235866.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Glossosoma beaumonti* 1950 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11127 Gl. beaumonti.

chitraliorum Schmid 1959a, Agapetus

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Cachem. et Jam. Chatorkhand 30-VII-1954 F. Schmid / CNC 235928.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu & Kashmir:** Chatorkhand, 36°20'56"N 73°50'15"E, 30.vii.1954, F. Schmid, CNC235928.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Agapetus chitraliorum* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12313 *Agapetus chitraliorum* HOLOTYPE.

dirghakantakam Schmid 1971, Glossosoma

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Dirang Dzong 11-IV-1961 F. Schmid / CNC 235852.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Derangzong, 27°20'31"N 92°16'22"E, 11.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC235852.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Glossosoma dirghakantakam* 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11113 Gl. dirghakantakam.

expositionis Nimmo 1966, Protoptila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Île Ste. Helene, Montreal, Que., 21/VIII/64, Coll.A.P. Nimmo.

Interpretive data: **CANADA. Quebec:** Montreal, Île Ste-Hélène, 45°31'4"N 73°32'2"W, 21.viii.1964, A.P. Nimmo, CNC235884.

Determination: *Protoptila expoa* Nimmo [former manuscript name?] HOLOTYPE ♂ / *Protoptila*

la expoa Nimmo HOLOTYPE CNC No. 9163
Comments: Genitalia and remainder of body mounted on separate slides on same pin.

falcata (Schmid 1991), Padunia [Poeciloptila]

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Tipaimukh 6-7-IX-1960 F. Schmid / CNC 235888.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Tipaimukh, 24°14'5"N 93°1'13"E, 6-7.ix.1960, F. Schmid, CNC235888.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Poeciloptila falcata* 1991 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Poeciloptila falcata* CNC No. 21235.

heliakreya Schmid 1959a, Glossosoma

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Frontier Province] Kawai 24-VI-1953 F. Schmid / CNC 235855.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa:** Kiwai, 34°37'59.01"N 73°26'39"E, 24.vi.1953, F. Schmid, CNC235855.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Glossosoma heliakreya* 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11114 Gl. heliakreya.

hemantajam Schmid 1971, Glossosoma

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Borghat 2-3-I-1960 F. Schmid / CNC 235856.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia Hills District, Borghat, 25°9'36"N 92°15'36"E, 2-3.i.1960, F. Schmid, CNC235856.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Glossosoma hemantajam* 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11121 Gl. hemantajam.

kamarasikam Schmid 1971, Glossosoma

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Zomphuk 1-X-1959 F. Schmid / CNC 235858.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Zomphuk, 1.x.1959, F. Schmid, CNC235858.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Glossosoma kamarasikam* 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11122 Gl. kamarasikam.

kchinam Schmid 1971, *Glossosoma*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Tangshing 15-IV-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 235859.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Tangshing,
15.iv.1959, F. Schmid, CNC235859.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Glossosoma kchinam*
1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11115 Gl. kchinam.

krichnarunam Schmid 1971, *Glossosoma*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Jhum La 24-25-III-
1961 F. Schmid / CNC 235861.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
Kameng Frontier Division [now divided into
the districts of Tawang, East Kameng and
West Kameng], Jhum La, 24-25.iii.1961, F.
Schmid, CNC235861.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Glossosoma krichna-*
runam 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC
No. 11116 Gl. krichnarunam.

**mahadhyandika (Schmid 1959a), *Agapetus*
[*Synagapetus*]**

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Fron-
tier Province] Balakot 16-X-1953 F.Schmid /
CNC 235896.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakh-**
tunkhwa: Balakot, 34°32'22"N 73°21'2.01"E,
16.x.1953, F. Schmid, CNC235896.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Synagapetus maha-*
dhyandika 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12312
Synagapetus mahadhyandica [sic] HOLO-
TYPE.

**maharikhita (Schmid 1959a), *Agapetus* [*Syn-*
agapetus]**

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Cachem. et Jam. Shardi 1-13-VIII-1953
F.Schmid / CNC 235900.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu &**
Kashmir: Shardi, 34°47'35.17"N 74°11'
10.77"E, 1-13.viii.1953, F. Schmid, CNC
235900.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Synagapetus mahari-*
khita 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12312
Synagapetus maharikhita [sic] HOLOTYPE.

nichinkata Schmid 1971, *Glossosoma*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Japon (Honshu) Karuizawa 28-VIII-
1952 R. Ishikawa / CNC 235863.

Interpretive data: **JAPAN. Honshu**: Chūbu,
Nagano Prefecture, Karuizawa, 36°20'54.50"N
138°35'49.30"E, 28.viii.1952, R. Ishikawa,
CNC235863.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Glossosoma nichin-*
kata 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11119 Gl. nichinkata.

nigroroseum Schmid 1971, *Glossosoma*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Yabuk 27-V-1959 F.Schmid /
CNC 235865.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Yabuk, 27.v.
1959, F. Schmid, CNC235865.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Glossosoma nigroro-*
seum 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11117 Gl. nigroroseum.

segovicus Schmid 1952, *Agapetus*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Espagne (Seg.) Revenga 10-VII-1950
F. Schmid / CNC 235918.

Interpretive data: **SPAIN. Segovia**: Revenga, 40°
52'19"N 4°6'15"W, 10.vii.1950, F. Schmid,
CNC235918.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Agapetus segovicus*
1950 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12454 *Agapetus*
segovicus HOLOTYPE.

slavorum Botoșăneanu 1960, *Agapetus*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Bosnie Trnovo 23-VII-1955 F.Schmid /
CNC 481660.

Interpretive data: **BOSNIA AND HERZEGO-**
VINA. Trnovo, 43°39'55"N 18°22'24"E, 23.
vii.1955, F. Schmid, CNC481660.

Determination: *Agapetus slavorum* Bots. ♂. /
Holotype ♂. / CNCNo. 12456 *Agapetus slavo-*
rum HOLOTYPE.

subaequale Schmid 1971, *Glossosoma*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Tapaishan im Tsinling Sued-Shensi
(China) F 21.6 1935.H. Höne / CNC 235838.

Interpretive data: **CHINA. Shaanxi:** Qin Mountains, Tapai Shan, 33°57'0"N 107° 45'0"E, 21.vi.1935, H. Höne, CNC235838.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Glossoma subaequale* 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11125 Gl. subaequale.

tripartitum* Schmid 1971, *Glossosoma

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Kuatun(2300m) 27,40n. Br. 117,40ö.L. J.Klapperich 3. 4. 1938(Fukien) / CNC 235839.

Interpretive data: **CHINA. Fujian:** Kuatun, 27° 40'N 117°40'E, 2300m, 3.iv.1938, L.J. Klapperich, CNC235839.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Glossoma 3-partitum* 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11126 Gl. 3-partitum.

turcomanorum* Schmid 1959b, *Agapetus

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Iran (Ost.9) Bavaman 8, 10-VII-1956 F.Schmid / CNC 235931.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. North Khorasan:** Baba Aman, 37°28'37.71"N 57°26'22.83"E, 8,10.vii.1956, F. Schmid, CNC235931.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Agapetus turcomanorum* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12275 *Agapetus turcomanorum* HOLOTYPE.

Comments: A list of material examined, including type specimens, was not provided for this species in the original description.

vaneyam* Schmid 1971, *Glossosoma

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Nyukmadong 19-20-IV-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 235841.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Nyukmadung, 27° 25'1"N 92°7'57"E, 19-20.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC235841.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Glossoma vaneyam* 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11118 Gl. vaneyam.

varjakantakam* Schmid 1971, *Glossosoma

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Nongrim 28-III-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 235842.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** West Khasi Hills District, Nongrim, 25°34'1"N 91°54'9"E, 28.iii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 235842.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Glossosoma varjakantakam* 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11123 Gl. varjakantakam.

GOERIDAE

arisudana* Schmid 1991c, *Goera

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Lifakpo 29-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 280270.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Liphakpu, 27°4'7"N 92°7'26"E, 29.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 280270.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Goera arisudana* 1990 F.Schmid / *Goera arisudana* Sch CNC [type no.] 20940.

assamica* Schmid 1965b, *Larcaria

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Sirohi Kashong 6-7-VI-1960 F. Schmid / CNC 280283.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Sirohi Kashong, 25°6'23.19"N 94°27'28.51"E, 6-7.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC280283.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Larcaria assamica* 1965 F. Schmid.

dandaka* Schmid 1991c, *Goera

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Ugsara 29-V-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 280272.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Pauri Garhwal District, Ugsara, 29.v.1958, F. Schmid, CNC280272.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Goera dandaka* 1990 F. Schmid / *Goera dandaka* Sch CNC [type no.] 20944.

dilipa* Schmid 1991c, *Goera

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Barato 24-IV-1960 F.Schmid CNC 280279.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia Hills District, Barato, 25°36'21"N 92°27'5"E, 24.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC280279.

Determination: holotype ♂ Goera dilipa 1990 F. Schmid / Goera dilipa Schm CNC [type no.] 20936.

janaka Schmid 1991c, Goera

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Hkayam Boum 20-23-VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 280274.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Hkayam Boum, 20-23.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 280274.

Determination: holotype ♂ Goera janaka 1990 F. Schmid.

kausalya Schmid 1991c, Goera

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Rapham 2-IV-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 280271.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Rapham, 2.iv.1959, F. Schmid, CNC280271.

Determination: holotype ♂ Goera kausalya 1990 F. Schmid / Goera kausalya Sch CNC [type no.] 20941.

lepidoptera Schmid 1965a, Goera

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Japon Karuizawa 10-VIII-1952 R. Ishikawa / CNC 280253.

Interpretive data: **JAPAN. Honshu:** Chūbu, Nagano Prefecture, Karuizawa, 36°20'54.50"N 138°35'49.30"E, 10.viii.1952, R. Ishikawa, CNC280253.

Determination: holotype ♂ Goera lepidoptera 1990 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12223 Goera lepidoptera.

maithili Schmid 1991c, Goera

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Kalaktang 14-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 280275.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Kalaktang, 27°6'28"N 92°7'2"E, 14.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC280275.

Determination: holotype ♂ Goera maithili 1990 F.

Schmid / Goera maithili Schm CNC [type no.] 20946.

parabhava Schmid 1991c, Goera

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Nungba 25-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 280265.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Nungba, 24°44'59"N 93°25'20"E, 25.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC280265.

Determination: holotype ♂ Goera parabhava 1990 F. Schmid / Goera parabhava Sch CNC [type no.] 20932.

paracrita Schmid 1991c, Goera

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Kumaon) Loharket 19-IX-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 280262.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Bageshwar District, Loharkhet, 30°2'48"N 79°57'35"E, 19.ix.1958, F. Schmid, CNC280262.

Determination: holotype ♂ Goera paracrita 1990 F. Schmid / Goera paracrita Sch CNC [type no.] 20928.

parakiya Schmid 1991c, Goera

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (kerala) Kandalur 12-XII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 280259.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala:** Kandalur, 12.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC280259.

Determination: holotype ♂ Goera parakiya 1990 F. Schmid / Goera parakiya Schm CNC [type no.] 20934.

Comments: Locality possibly Kanthaloore (10°12'52"N 77°11'52"E).

paramahansa Schmid 1991c, Goera

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Chapai 26-II-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 280266.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** Kameng Frontier Division [now divided into the districts of Tawang, East Kameng and West Kameng], Chapai, 26.ii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC280266.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Goera paramahansa* 1990 F. Schmid / *Goera paramahansa* Sch CNC [type no.] 20931.

paramika* Schmid 1991c, *Goera

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Thangrain 22-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 280263.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: Jaintia Hills District, Thangrain, 25°34'48"N 92°26'22"E, 22.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC280263.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Goera paramika* 1990 F. Schmid / *Goera paramika* Sch CNC [type no.] 20930.

parayatta* Schmid 1991c, *Goera

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Mawpran 8-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 280264.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: East Khasi Hills District, Mawpran, 25°17'28"N 91°57'26"E, 8.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 280264.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Goera parayatta* 1990 F. Schmid / *Goera parayatta* Sch CNC [type no.] 20929.

paropadecha* Schmid 1991c, *Goera

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Perumalalai 7-XII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 280260.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu**: Perumal Malai, 10°15'57"N 77°32'42"E, 7.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC280260.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Goera paropadecha* 1990 F. Schmid / *Goera paropadecha* Sch CNC [type no.] 20933.

raghu* Schmid 1991c, *Goera

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Hi 3-IV-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 280269.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Hi, 3.iv.1959, F. Schmid, CNC280269.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Goera raghu* 1990 F. Schmid / *Goera raghu* Sch CNC [type no.] 20939.

rakchasa* Schmid 1991c, *Goera

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Langdang 5-VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 280273.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Langdang, 25°7'25"N 94°24'16"E, 5.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC280273.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Goera rakchsa* [sic] 1990 F. Schmid *Goera rakshasa* Sch CNC [type no.] 20938.

Comments: Description incorrectly listed date of collection as the 9th.

sarayu* Schmid 1991c, *Goera

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Teri Garhwal Gawana 22-24-V-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 280268.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Tehri Garhwal District, Gawana, 22-24.v.1958, F. Schmid, CNC280268.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Goera sarayu* 1990 F. Schmid / *Goera sarayu* Sch CNC [type no.] 20942.

spicata* Schmid 1965a, *Goera

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Japon (Honshu) Karuizawa 28-VIII-1952 R. Ishikawa / CNC 280256.

Interpretive data: **JAPAN. Honshu**: Chūbu, Nagano Prefecture, Karuizawa, 36°20'54.50"N 138°35'49.30"E, 29.viii.1952, R. Ishikawa, CNC280256.

Determination: holotype ♂ *goera spicata* 1990 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12501 *Goera spicata*.

vaichravana* Schmid 1991c, *Goera

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Kumaon) Loharket 19-IX-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 280280.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Bageshwar District, Loharkhet, 30°2'48"N 79°57'35"E, 19.ix.1958, F. Schmid, CNC280280.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Goera vaichravana* 1990 F. Schmid / *Goera vaichravana* Sch CNC [type no.] 20937.

vaidehi* Schmid 1991c, *Goera

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Khaorang 28-VIII-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 280276.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Khaorang, 28.viii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC280276.

Determination: holotype ♂ Goera vaidehi 1990 F. Schmid / Goera vaidehi Schm CNC [type no.] 20947.

valmiki Schmid 1991c, Goera

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Mawlang 12-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 280277.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: East Khasi Hills District, Mawlang, 25°39'44"N 91°50'30"E, 12.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 280277.

Determination: holotype ♂ Goera valmiki 1990 F. Schmid / Goera valmiki Schm CNC [type no.] 20935.

vinata Schmid 1991c, Goera

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Langdang 5-VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 280267.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Langdang, 25°7'25"N 94°24'16"E, 5.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC280267.

Determination: holotype ♂ Goera vinata 1990 F. Schmid / Goera vinata Sch CNC [type no.] 20943.

yajnadatta Schmid 1991c, Goera

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Chug 16-IV-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 280278.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Chug, 27°25'4"N 92°14'3"E, 16.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC280278.

Determination: holotype ♂ Goera yajnadatta 1990 F. Schmid / Goera yajnadatta Sch CNC [type no.] 20948.

HELICOPSYCHIDAE

antinoe Schmid 1993a, Cochliophylax

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (C.) [=Cachar District] Bandar-

khal 9-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311375.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Assam**: Cachar District, Bandarkhal, 25°3'30"N 92°48'4"E, 9.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311375.

Determination: holotype ♂ Cochliophylax antinoe 1992 F. Schmid / holotype ♂ Cochliophylax antinoe Schm. CNC 21490.

arsinoe Schmid 1993a, Cochliophylax

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Khanggoi 16-VII-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311374.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Khanggoi, 16.vii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311374.

Determination: holotype ♂ Cochliophylax arsinoe Schmid / CNC [type no.] 21485 holotype ♂ Cochliophylax arsinoe 1992 F. Schmid.

Comments: Locality possibly Khangkhui Khullen (25°5'58"N 94°23'44").

astynome Schmid 1993a, Cochliophylax

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Sikkim Sirwani 1-V-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311377.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Sirwani, 1.v.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311377.

Determination: holotype ♂ Cochliophylax astynome 1992 F. Schmid / holotype ♂ Cochliophylax astynome Schm. CNC [type no.] 21486.

calliope Schmid 1993a, Helicopsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Khopum [sic] 27-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311362.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Khoupum, 24°39'16"N 93°26'52"E, 27.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311362.

Determination: holotype ♂ Helicopsyche calliope 1992 F. Schmid / Helicopsyche calliope Schmid CNC [type no.] 21476.

callirrhoe Schmid 1993a, Helicopsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Khasi and Jaintia Hills] Syndai 26-XII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311364.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: Jaintia

- Hills District, Syndai, 25°11'8.01"N 92°8'25"E, 26.xii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311364.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Helicopsyche callirrhoe* 1992 F. Schmid / *Helicopsyche callirrhoe* Schmid CNC [type no.] 21475.
- chionodoce* Schmid 1993a, *Helicopsyche***
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Kattalaimala 16-17-I-1962 F.Schmid / CNC 311365.
Interpretive data: **INDIA**. Madras [likely in either present day Kerala or Tamil Nadu State], Kattalaimala, 16-17.i.1962, F. Schmid, CNC 311365.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Helicopsyche chionodoce* 1992 F. Schmid / Holotype ♂ *Helicopsyche chionodoce* Schmid CNC [type no.] 21478.
- chrysothoe* Schmid 1993a, *Cochliophylax***
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Warongpang 21-III-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311370.
Interpretive data: **INDIA**. **Arunachal Pradesh**: Kameng Frontier Division [now divided into the districts of Tawang, East Kameng and West Kameng], Warongpang, 21.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311370.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Cochliophylax chrysothoe* 1992 F. Schmid / holotype ♂ *Cochliophylax chrysothoe* Schmid CNC [type no.] 21482.
Comments: Locality possibly Warrangpam (27°6'19"N 92°5'2"E).
- cymodoce* Schmid 1993a, *Helicopsyche***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Inde (U.D.M.N.C.H.) [=United district of Mikir Hills and North Cachar] Rongkhong 27-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311358.
Interpretive data: **INDIA**. **Assam**: [United District now treated as separate Mikir Hills and Karbi Anglong Districts], Rongkhong, 27.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311358.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Helicopsyche cymodoce* 1992 F. Schmid / *Helicopsyche cymodoce* Schmid CNC [type no.] 21471.
Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.
- demodoce* Schmid 1993a, *Helicopsyche***
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Thangrain 22-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 280441.
Interpretive data: **INDIA**. **Meghalaya**: Jaintia Hills District, Thangrain, 25°34'48"N 92°26'22"E, 22.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC280441.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Helicopsyche demodoce* 1992 F. Schmid.
- erigone* Schmid 1993a, *Helicopsyche***
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: U.J.K.H. [=United Khasi and Jaintia Hills] Syndai / CNC 311363.
Interpretive data: **INDIA**. **Meghalaya**: Jaintia Hills District, Syndai, 25°11'8.01"N 92°8'25"E, 14.xii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311363.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Helicopsyche erigone* 1992 F. Schmid / *Helicopsyche erigone* Schmid CNC [type no.] 21473.
- erythronoe* Schmid 1993a, *Helicopsyche***
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Kaiphundai 20-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311360.
Interpretive data: **INDIA**. **Manipur**: Kaiphundai, 24°47'51"N 93°14'1"E, 20.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311360.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Helicopsyche erythronoe* 1992 F. Schmid / Holotype ♂ *Helicopsyche erythronoe* Schmid CNC [type no.] 21468.
- euryboe* Schmid 1993a, *Cochliophylax***
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Rupa 12-VI-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311371.
Interpretive data: **INDIA**. **Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Rupa, 27°12'11.01"N 92°23'55"E, 12.vi.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 311371.
Determination: holotype *Cochliophylax euryboe* 1992 F. Schmid / holotype ♂ *Cochliophylax euryboe* Schmid CNC [type no.] 21481.
- eurycrene* Schmid 1993a, *Helicopsyche***
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Perumalmai 3-6-XII-

1958 F.Schmid / CNC 311368.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu:** Perumal Malai, 10°15'56.01"N 77°32'42"E, 3-6.xii. 1958, F. Schmid, CNC311368.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Helicopsyche eurycrene* 1992 F. Schmid / holotype ♂ *Helicopsyche eurycrene* Schm. CNC [type no.] 21479.
Comments: two wings slide-mounted on pin.

eurynoe* Schmid 1993a, *Helicopsyche
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Assam Dhekiajuli 28-II-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 280439.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Assam:** Dhekiajuli, 26°41'55"N 92°29'7"E, 28.ii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC280439.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Helicopsyche eurynoe* 1992 F. Schmid / Holotype ♂ *Helicopsyche eurynoe* Schm CNC [type no.] 21468.

harmothoe* Schmid 1993a, *Cochliophylax
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (Lushai) [=Mizo Hills] Ratu 11-IX-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311372.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Mizoram:** Aizawl District, Ratu, 24°6'42"N 92°55'17"E, 11.ix. 1960, F. Schmid, CNC311372.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Cochliophylax harmothoe* 1992 F. Schmid / holotype ♂ *Cochliophylax harmothoe* Schmid CNC [type no.] 21483.

hippohoe* Schmid 1993a, *Cochliophylax
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Sikkim Rapham 2-IV-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311376.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Rapham, 2.iv. 1959, F. Schmid, CNC311376.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Cochliophylax hippohoe* 1992 F. Schmid / holotype ♂ *Cochliophylax hippohoe* Schm. CNC [type no.] 21489.

itonoe* Schmid 1993a, *Cochliophylax
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Mapum 12-VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311373.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Mapum, 25° 7'18"N 94°31'6"E, 12.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311373.

Determination: holotype *Cochliophylax harmothoe* [lapsus] 1992 F. Schmid / Holotype *Cochliophylax itonoe* Schmid, Det. O. Lonsdale / holotype ♂ *Cochliophylax itonoe* Schm CNC [type no.] 21484.

laothoe* Schmid 1993a, *Cochliophylax
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Khasi and Jaintia Hills] Syndai 25-XII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311380.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia Hills District, Syndai, 25°11'8.01"N 92°8' 25"E, 25.xii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311380.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Cochliophylax laothoe* 1992 F. Schmid / holotype ♂ *Cochliophylax laothoe* Schmid CNC [type no.] 21487.

leucothoe* Schmid 1993a, *Helicopsyche
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Vangai Chungpao 21-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311361.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Vangai Chungpao, 24°45'23"N 93°10'40"E, 21.v. 1960, F. Schmid, CNC311361.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Helicopsyche leucothoe* 1992 F. Schmid / *Helicopsyche leucothoe* Schmid CNC [type no.] 21472.

myrrhine* Schmid 1993a, *Helicopsyche
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Malbidu 18-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311366.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka:** Malbidu, 18.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311366.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Helicopsyche myrrhine* 1992 F. Schmid / Holotype ♂ *Helicopsyche myrrhine* Schmid CNC [type no.] 21477.
Comments: The locality possibly refers to Galibeedu (12°28'37"N 75°39'20"E), which is adjacent to the previous day's collection site (Monnangeri). Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

oenodoce* Schmid 1993a, *Helicopsyche
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Lagairong 26-V-1960 F.Schmid CNC 311359.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Lagairong, 24°42'0"N 93°32'0"E, 26.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311359.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Hel. oenodoce* 1992 F. Schmid / Holotype ♂ *Helicopsyche oenodoce* Schm CNC [type no.] 21467.

philodoce* Schmid 1993a, *Helicopsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Perumalmalai 9-XII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311367.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu:** Perumal Malai, 10°15'57"N 77°32'42"E, 9.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311367.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Helicopsyche philodoce* 1992 F. Schmid / holotype ♂ *Helicopsyche philodoce* Schm. CNC [type no.] 21480.

phoebe* Schmid 1993a, *Cochliophylax

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Sirohi Kashong 7-VI-1960 F. Schmid / CNC 311379.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Siruhi Kashong, 25°6'23.19"N 94°27'28.51"E, 7.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311379.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Cochliophylax phoebe* 1992 F. Schmid / holotype ♂ *Cochliophylax phoebe* Schmid CNC [type no.] 21491.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

theochoe* Schmid 1993a, *Helicopsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Amatulla 23-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 280440.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Amatulla, 26°55'47"N 92°7'18"E, 23.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 280440.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Helicopsyche theochoe* 1992 F. Schmid / holotype ♂ *Helicopsyche theochoe* Schm CNC [type no.] 21466.

thyonoe* Schmid 1993a, *Helicopsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Lifakpo 15-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311357.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. S Arunachal Pra-**

desh: West Kameng District, Liphakpu, 27°4'7"N 92°7'26"E, 15.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311357.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Helicopsyche thyonoe* 1992 F. Schmid / *Helicopsyche thyonoe* Schmid CNC [type no.] 21474.

xenothoe* Schmid 1993a, *Cochliophylax

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Khumayara 27-28-V-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 311378.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Pauri Garhwal District, Khumayara, 27-28.v.1958, F. Schmid, CNC311378.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Cochliophylax xenothoe* 1992 F. Schmid / holotype ♂ *Cochliophylax xenothoe* Schm. CNC [type no.] 21490.

HYDROBIOSIDAE

dakchinam* Schmid 1970a, *Apsilochorema

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Swamp Hill 10-XII-1961 F.Schmid.

Interpretive data: **INDIA.** Madras [likely in either present day Kerala or Tamil Nadu State], Swamp Hill, 10.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 235755.

Determination: holotype *Apsilochorema dakchinam* 1968 F. Schmid.

hrasvam* Schmid 1970a, *Apsilochorema

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Sirohi Kashong 9-VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 235756.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Siruhi Kashong, 25°6'23.19"N 94°27'28.51"E, 9.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC235756.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Apsilochorema hrasvam* 1968 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12306 *Apsilochorema hrasvam* HOLOTYPE.

iranicum* Schmid 1959b, *Apsilochorema

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Iran (Ost.2) Garna 9-10-V-1956 F.Schmid / CNC 235758.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. Mazandaran:** Garna, 35°53'47"N 52°11'2"E, 9-10.v.1956, F. Schmid, CNC235758.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Apsilochorema iranicum* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12274 *Apsilochorema iranicum* HOLOTYPE.

natibhinnam* Schmid 1970a, *Apsilochorema
holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: U.J.K.H. [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills], Nongjngi / CNC 235759.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: West Jaintia Hills District, Nongjngi, 25°32'32"N 92°16'20"E, 19.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 235759.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Apsilochorema natibhinnam* 1968 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12305 *Apsilochorema natibhinnam* HOLOTYPE.

neotropicalis* Schmid 1989, *Atopsyche
holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Peru (Cuzco) Quincemil VIII.62 L.E. Pena / CNC 235739.

Interpretive data: **PERU. Cusco**: Quincemil, 13°13'2.86"S 70°44'27.48"W, viii.1962, L.E. Peña, CNC235739.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Atopsyche neotropicalis* 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 19837 *Atopsyche neotropicalis* Sch.

socialis* Flint 1967, *Atopsyche
holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: 10 mi.W.El Salto Dgo.MEXICO,9000' 11.VIII.1964 J.E.H. Martin / CNC 235740.

Interpretive data: **MEXICO. Durango**: 16 km W El Salto, 23°43'9.69"N 105°29'21.66"W, 2743m, 11.viii.1964, J.E.H. Martin, CNC 235740.

Determination: Holotype ♂ *Atopsyche socialis* Flint / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 10.039 *Atopsyche socialis* Flint.

tanum* Schmid 1970a, *Apsilochorema
holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Sirohi Kashong 11-13-VII-1960 F. Schmid / CNC 235760.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Sirohi Kashong, 25°6'23.19"N 94°27'28.51"E, 11-13.vii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC235760.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Apsilochorema tanum* 1968 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12301 *Apsilochorema tanum* HOLOTYPE.

tigmatejanam* Schmid 1970a, *Apsilochorema
holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Saran [sic] 17-IX-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 235762.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Pauri Garhwal District, Sarana, 29°33'17"N 79°34'13"E, 17.ix.1958, F. Schmid, CNC235762.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Apsilochorema tigmatejanam* 1968 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12302 *Apsilochorema tigmatejanam* HOLOTYPE.

unculatum* Schmid 1970a, *Apsilochorema

Valid name: *Apsilochorema nigrum* (Navás 1932) holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Kuatun(2300m) 27,40n. Br. 117,40ö.L. J.Klapperich 3. 4. 1938(Fukien) / CNC 235763.

Interpretive data: **CHINA. Fujian**: Kuatun, 27°40'N 117°40'E, 2300m, 3.iv.1938, L.J. Klapperich, CNC235763.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Apsilochorema unculatum* 1968 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12304 *Apsilochorema unculatum* HOLOTYPE.

utchtchunam* Schmid 1970a, *Apsilochorema

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Chingsao 15-VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 235764.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Chingsao, 15.vi.1960, CNC235764.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Apsilochorema utchtchunam* 1968 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12303 *Apsilochorema utchtchunam* [sic] HOLOTYPE.

vaneyam* Schmid 1970a, *Apsilochorema

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Chug 15-IV-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 235765.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Chug, 27°25'4"N 92°14'3"E, 15.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC235765.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Apsilochorema vaneyam* 1968 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12300 *Apsilochorema vaneyam* HOLOTYPE.

HYDROPSYCHIDAE

***ambigua* Schmid** [in Botoşăneanu & Schmid (1973)], *Hydropsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Espagne (Av.) Val de Gredos 15-23-VII-1950 F. Schmid / CNC 236639.

Interpretive data: **SPAIN. Ávila**: Val de Gredos, 15-23.vii.1950, F. Schmid, CNC236639.

Determination: Holotype ♂ *Hydropsyche dubia* 1950 F. Schmid [replaced by *Hydropsyche ambigua* Schmid, 1952] / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 12488 *Hydropsyche ambigua* / Révision Botosaneanu + Gonzáles 1985.

Comments: Originally described as *H. dubia* Schmid 1952, but the name was preoccupied by *dubia* Walker, 1852. Published date of collection listed as 16.vii.1950.

arcuata* Schmid 1968b, *Arctopsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Dirang Dzong 18-VII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236578.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Derangzong, 27°20'31"N 92°16'22"E, 18.vii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC236578.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Arctopsyche arcuata* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11407 Arct. *arcuata*.

aureocephala* Schmid 1964a, *Parapsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Japon (Honshu) Karuizawa 28-VIII-1952 R. Ishikawa / CNC 236601.

Interpretive data: **JAPAN. Chūbu**, Nagano Prefecture, Karuizawa, 36°20'54.50"N 138°35'49.30"E, 28.viii.1952, R. Ishikawa, CNC 236601.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Parapsyche aureocephala* 1963 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11413 Par. *aureocephala*.

bicornis* Schmid 1968b, *Arctopsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Dirang Dzong 18-VII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236594.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Derangzong, 27°20'31"N 92°16'22"E, 16.vii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC236594.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Arctopsyche bicornis*

1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11404 Arct. 2-cornis.

bilobatum* Schmid 1964d, *Leptonema

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Colombie Cundinamarca Monterredonda 4-I-1960 J.E.Foerster / CNC 236774.

Interpretive data: **COLOMBIA. Cundinamarca**: Monterredonda, 4°15'19.72"N 73°49'27.27"W, 4.i.1960, J.E. Foerster, CNC236774.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptonema bilobatum* 1962 F. Schmid / Holotype ♂ *Leptonema 2-lobatum* Sch. CNC 19814.

burha* Schmid 1961, *Diplectrona

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Cachem.et Jam. Muzaffarabad 10-12-V-1954 F.Schmid / CNC 236742.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu & Kashmir**: Muzaffarabad, 34°21'35"N 73°28'17"E, 10-12.v.1954, F. Schmid, CNC236742.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Diplectrona bhura* [sic] 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12356 *Diplectrona bhura* [sic].

corbeti* Nimmo 1966, *Hydropsyche

Valid name: *Hydropsyche confusa* (Walker 1852)

holotype (1 male, ethyl alcohol)

Verbatim: Ile Ste. Helene, Montreal, Que., 28/VI/64, Coll. A.P.Nimmo / Ste Héléne Isl. Montréal RPIIc.39 28-VI-64 / CNC 165726.

Interpretive data: **CANADA. Quebec**: Montreal, Île Ste-Hélène, 45°31'4"N 73°32' 2"W, 28.vi.1964 [day erroneously listed as the 29th in the original description], A. Nimmo, HOLOTYPE CNC No. 9165, CNC165726.

Determination: *Hydropsyche corbeti* ♂ / is actually *H. guttata* Pictet (=H. *seperata* Banks) dict. A.P. Nimmo, 18/3/80.

djabai* Schmid 1959b, *Hydropsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Iran (Ost.1) Sama 13-15-X-1956 F.Schmid / CNC 236644.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. Mazandaran**: Sama', 36°22'54"N 51°23'31"E, 13-15.x.1956, F. Schmid, CNC236644.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Hydropsyche djabai*

- 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12291 *Hydropsyche* djabai.
- fissa Schmid 1968b, *Arctopsyche***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Sikkim Selep 27-VII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236593.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Selep, 27.vii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236593.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Arctopsyche fissa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11405 Arct. fissa.
- gautamitra Schmid 1961, *Hydropsyche***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Pakistan (Penjab) Hassan Abdal 27-XII-1954 F.Schmid / CNC 236646.
Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Punjab**: Hassan Abdal, 33°49'10"N 72°41'21"E, 27.xii.1954, F. Schmid, CNC236646.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Hydropsyche gautamitra* 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12355 *Hydropsyche gautamitra*.
- hibera Schmid 1952, *Hydropsyche***
Valid name: *Hydropsyche instabilis* (Curtis 1834)
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Sierra Nevada Val del Inferno 5-VIII-1950 F. Schmid / CNC 481643.
Interpretive data: **SPAIN. Granada**: Sierra Nevada, Val del Inferno, 37°6'0"N 3°20'0"W, 5.viii.1950, F. Schmid, CNC481643.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Hydropsyche hibera* 1950 F. Schmid / *Hydropsyche instabilis* (Curtis) ♂ revision: Botosaneanu & Gonzales, 1985 / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12489 *Hydropsyche hibera*.
- inaequispinosa Schmid 1968b, *Arctopsyche***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Sikkim Chongpung 27-IX-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236596.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Chongpung, 27°19'35"N 88°14'10"E, 27.ix.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236596.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Arctopsyche inaequispinosa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11402 Arct. inaequispinosa.
- infernalis Schmid 1952, *Hydropsyche***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Sierra Nevada Val del Inferno 5-VIII-1950 F.Schmid / CNC 236640.
Interpretive data: **SPAIN. Granada**: Sierra Nevada, Val del Inferno, 37°6'0"N 3°20'0"W, 5.viii.1950, F. Schmid, CNC236640.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Hydropsyche infernalis* 1950 F. Schmid / révision: Botosaneanu + González 1985 / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12490 *Hydropsyche infernalis*.
- inspiratum Flint, McAlpine & Ross 1987, *Leptonema***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: PERU Dept. Puno Rio Inambari/Loromayu 5-6.Sept.1962 L.E.Pena / CNC 236771.
Interpretive data: **PERU. Puno**: Río Inambari/Loromayu, 5-6.ix.1962, L.E. Peña, CNC 236771.
Determination: Holotype *Leptonema inspiratum* McA. + Ross / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 19816 *Leptonema inspiratum* Mc+R.
- integra Schmid 1968b, *Arctopsyche***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Chug 25-31-VII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236591.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Chug, 27°25'4"N 92°14'3"E, 25-31.vii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 236591.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Arctopsyche integra* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11406 Arct. integra.
- kchina Schmid 1968b, *Parapsyche***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Rahung 16-VII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236605.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Rahung, 27°18'37"N 92°23'41"E, 16.vii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 236605.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Parapsyche kchina* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11410 Par. kchina.

**kimalaksa (Schmid 1961), *Diplectrona*
[*Diplectronella*]**

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pakistan (Punjab) Hassan Abdal 27-XII-1954 F.Schmid / CNC 236741.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Punjab**: Hassan Abdal, 33°49'10"N 72°41'21"E, 27.xii.1954, F. Schmid, CNC236741.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Diplectronella kimalaksa* 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12357 *Diplectrona kimalaksa*.

mahati Schmid 1968b, *Parapsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Chachu 17-V-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236604.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Chachu, 17.v. 1959, F. Schmid, CNC236604.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Parapsyche mahati* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11411 *Par. mahati*.

mahrkusha Schmid 1959b, *Hydropsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Iran (Maz.) Quattekas 19-IX-1955 F.Schmid / CNC 236645.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. Mazandaran**: Gat-e-Kash, 36°25'28.12"N 51°32'21.57"E, 19.ix. 1955, F. Schmid, CNC236645.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Hydropsyche mahrkusha* 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12292 *Hydropsyche mahrkusha*.

montrealensis Nimmo 1966, *Cheumatopsyche*

Valid name: *Cheumatopsyche minuscula* (Banks 1907)

holotype (1 male, ethyl alcohol)

Verbatim: Ile Ste. Helene, Montreal, Que., 27/VI/64, Coll. A.P.Nimmo / CNC 165727.

Interpretive data: **CANADA. Quebec**: Montreal, Île Ste-Hélène, 45°31'4"N 73°32'2"W, 27.vi. 1964, A.P. Nimmo, CNC165727.

Determination: *Cheumatopsyche montrealensis* Nimmo HOLOTYPE CNC No. 9164 / *Cheumatopsyche minuscula* M, det. Gordon 1972.

moralesi Schmid 1952, *Diplectrona*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Espagne (Lugo) Sant. del Cebrero 26-VII-1950 E.Morales / CNC 481640.

Interpretive data: **SPAIN. Lugo**: Santuario del Cebrero, 42°42'25.82"N 7°2'35.14"W, 26.vii. 1950, E. Morales, CNC481640.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Diplectrona moralesi* 1956 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12491 *Diplectrona moralesi*.

nigrocephala Schmid 1964a, *Parapsyche*

Valid name: *Parapsyche maculata* (Ulmer 1907)

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: 31-VII-'15 YOSHINO A.NOHIRA / CNC 236602.

Interpretive data: **JAPAN. Nara Prefecture, Yoshino**, 34°23'40"N 135°51'34"E, 31.vii. 1915, A. Nohira, CNC236602.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Parapsyche nigrocephala* F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11412 *Par. nigrocephala*.

peristerica Botoșăneanu & Marinković-Gospodnetić 1968, *Hydropsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Macédoine Perister 12-16-VIII-1955 F.Schmid / CNC 236642.

Interpretive data: **MACEDONIA. Baba Mountain**, 41°0'12"N 21°11'3"E, 12-16.viii.1955, F. Schmid, CNC236642.

Determination: *Hydropsyche peristerica* Bots. + Marink. Holotype ♂. / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12487 *Hydropsyche peristerica*.

piliferum Schmid 1964d, *Leptonema*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Bolivie (Cochab.) Alto Palmar XI-1960 J.E.Foerster / CNC 279857.

Interpretive data: **BOLIVIA. Cochabamba**: Alto Palmar, 16°36'36"S 65°32'24"W, 1100m, xi. 1960, J.E. Foerster, CNC279857.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptonema piliferum* 1962 F. Schmid / Holotype ♂ *Leptonema piliferum* Sch. CNC 19825.

poushyamitra Schmid 1961, *Hydropsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Frontier Province] Kaghan 27-29-VI-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 236649.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa:** Kaghan, 34°46'40"N 73°31'32.01"E, 27-29.vi.1953, F. Schmid, CNC 236649.

Determination: holotype *Hydropsyche poushyamitra* 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12354 *Hydropsyche poushyamitra*.

sakarawaka Schmid 1959b, *Hydropsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Iran (Ost.1) Majlar [sic] 17-V-1956 F.Schmid / CNC 236658.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. Mazandaran:** Mejlar, 36°22'51.82"N 51°16'42.97"E, 17.v.1956, F. Schmid, CNC236658.

Determination: *Hydropsyche sakarawaka* Sch. holotype? O.L. / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12290 *Hydropsyche sakarawaka*.

Comments: No specimen with a determination or type label can be unambiguously attributed to this species, and only a single specimen in the CNC is curated in the unit tray for this species; while the holotype was collected on a published date of 18.v.1956, only a single specimen was listed in the original publication, making it most likely that this is the type specimen.

shanorum Schmid 1964a, *Trichomacronema*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Lushat 19-VII-1960 F.Schmid.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Lushat, 19.vii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC279897.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Trichomacronema shanorum* 1963 F. Schmid.

Comments: Description incorrectly listed month of collection as June, conflicting with data in the field notes and the specimen label.

tchandratchuda Schmid 1968b, *Parapsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Sirohi Kashong 6-7-VI-1960 F. Schmid / CNC 236606.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Sirohi Kashong, 25°6'23.19"N 94°27'28.51"E, 6-7.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236606.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Parapsyche tchandratshuda* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11409 Par. tchandratshuda.

tricornis Schmid 1968b, *Arctopsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: U.J.K.H. [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Laitlyngkot 15-III-1960 F.Schmid/ CNC 236597.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** East Khasi Hills District, Laitlyngkot, 25°26' 44.01"N 91°50'23"E, 15.iii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 236597.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Arctopsyche tricornis* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11403 Arct. 3-cornis.

turbinata Schmid 1968b, *Parapsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: U.S.A., Ore. Jackson Co. Prospect 6-VI-1965 F.Schmid / CNC 236608.

Interpretive data: **USA. Oregon:** Jackson Co., Prospect, 42°45'15"N 122°29'20"W, 6.vi.1965, F. Schmid, CNC236608.

Determination: *Parapsyche turbinata* Schm. HOLOTYPE ♂ CNCNo. 9383.

vairya Schmid 1959b, *Dipletrona*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Iran (Ost.3) Baharistan [sic] 10-IX-1956 F.Schmid / CNC 236737.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. Ardabil:** Baharestan, 38°24'3.60"N 48°43'18.12"E, 10.ix.1956, F. Schmid, CNC236737.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Dipletrona vairya* 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12293 *Dipletrona vairya*.

variyasi Schmid 1968b, *Parapsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Bomdi La 11-15-VII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236603.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Bomdila, 27°15'51"N 92°24'58"E, 11-15.vii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 236603.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Parapsyche variyasi* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11408 Par. variyasi.

vasoumitra Schmid 1961, *Hydropsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Cachem. et Jam. Shardi 1-13-VIII-1953
F. Schmid / CNC 236648.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu & Kashmir**: Shardi, 34°47'35.17"N 74°11'10.77"E, 1-13.viii.1953, F. Schmid, CNC 236648.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Hydropsyche vasoumittra* 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12353 *Hydropsyche vasoumittra*.

yazata Schmid 1959b, *Diplectrona*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Asia min. Merzifoun [sic] / CNC 236738.

Interpretive data: **TURKEY. Amasia**: Merzifon, 40°52'28"N 35°27'41"E, CNC236738.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Diplectrona yazata* 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12299 *Diplectrona yazata*.

HYDROPTILIDAE

apsara Schmid 1960, *Microptila*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Frontier Province] Balakot 23-VI-1953 F. Schmid / CNC 235945.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa**: Balakot, 34°32'22"N 73°21'2.01"E, 23.vi.1953, F. Schmid, CNC235945.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Microptila apsara* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12318 *Microptila apsara* HOLOTYPE.

armathai Schmid 1959b, *Hydroptila*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Iran (Ost. 2) Garna 2-IX-1955
F. Schmid / CNC 235982.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. Mazandaran**: Garna, 35°53'47"N 52°11'2"E, 2.ix.1955, F. Schmid, CNC235982.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Hydroptila armatai* [sic] 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12277 *Hydroptila armathai* HOLOTYPE.

Comments: The original description provided a list of specimens examined, but did not indicate from which collection event the type specimens were selected.

badhami Schmid 1960, *Chrysotrichia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pakistan (Penjab) Hassan Abdal 27-XII-1954 F. Schmid / CNC 236033.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Punjab**: Hassan Abdal, 33°49'10"N 72°41'21"E, 27.xii.1954, F. Schmid, CNC236033.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Chrysotrichia badhami* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12321 *Chrysotrichia badhami* HOLOTYPE.

bajgirana Botoșăneanu 1983, *Hydroptila*

Valid name: *Hydroptila angulata* Mosely 1922

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Iran (Ost.9) Bajgiran 3-VII-1956
F. Schmid / CNC 235961.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. Razavi Khorasan**: Bājgirān, 37°37'21"N 58°25'8"E, 3.vii.1956, F. Schmid, CNC235961.

Determination: HOLOTYPE / *Hydroptila bajgirana* Botosaneanu ♂ holotype.

balin Schmid 1983, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: point)

Verbatim: Inde (W.B.) Shepi 23-III-1959
F. Schmid / CNC 236062.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. West Bengal**: Shepi, 27°7'38.59"N 88°5'6.30"E, 23.iii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236062.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia balin* 1981 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17684 *Stactobia balin* HOLOTYPE.

ballur Schmid 1983, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Borghat 21-22-XII-1959
F. Schmid / CNC 236060.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: Jaintia Hills District, Borghat, 25°9'36"N 92°15'36"E, 21-22.xii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236060.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia balur* [sic] 1981 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17682 *Stactobia balur* [sic] HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

beor Schmid 1983, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Dirang Dzong 9-IV-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236082.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Derangzong, 27°20'31"N 92°16'22"E, 9.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 236082.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia beor* 1981 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17716 *Stactobia beor* HOLOTYPE.

beren Schmid 1983, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Gigaon 31-III-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236107.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Jigaon, 27°10'7"N 92°20'17.01"E, 31.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 236107.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia beren* 1982 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17707 *Stactobia beren* HOLOTYPE.

bifur Schmid 1983, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: point)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Umlangshor 18-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236099.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: Jaintia Hills District, Umlangshor, 25°28'27"N 92°12'52"E, 18.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236099.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia bifur* 1982 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17703 *Stactobia bifur* HOLOTYPE.

bofur Schmid 1983, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: point)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Lathan 11-VIII-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236101.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Lathan, 11.viii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236101.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia bofur* 1982 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17704 *Stactobia bofur* HOLOTYPE.

botosaneanui Schmid 1959c, *Stactobia*

Valid name: *Stactobia mclachlani* Kimmins 1949 holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Macédoine Perister 12-16-VIII-1955 F.Schmid / CNC 236048.

Interpretive data: **MACEDONIA**. Baba Mountain, 41°0'12"N 21°11'3"E, 12-16.viii.1955, F. Schmid, CNC236048.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia botosaneanui* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12474 *Stactobia botosaneanui* HOLOTYPE.

calin Schmid 1983, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Chug 15-IV-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236079.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Chug, 27°25'4"N 92°14'3"E, 15.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 236079.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia calin* 1981 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17710 *Stactobia calin* HOLOTYPE.

dain Schmid 1983, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: point)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Mawkhap 18-III-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236083.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: East Khasi Hills District, Mawkhap, 25°23'17.01"N 91°54'0"E, 18.iii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 236083.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia dain* 1981 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17714 *Stactobia dain* HOLOTYPE.

doehleri Schmid 1959c, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Cachem. et Jam. Katzarah Tso 5-X-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 236074.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu & Kashmir**: Kachura, 5.x.1953, 35°26'9"N 75°26'60"E, F. Schmid, CNC236074.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia doehleri* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12467 *Stactobia doehleri* HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Specific epithet published as "döhleri".

dori Schmid 1983, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: point)

Verbatim: Inde (U.P.) Rishikesh 25-31.III.1958 F.Schmid / CNC 236106.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Rishikesh, 30°5'3"N 78°15'53"E, 25-31.iii.1958, F. Schmid, CNC236106.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia dori* 1982 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17708 *Stactobia dori* HOLOTYPE.

durin* Schmid 1983, *Stactobia

holotype (1 male, pinned: point)

Verbatim: Inde (W.B.) Shepi 23-III-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236073.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. West Bengal:** Shepi, 27°7'38.59"N 88°5'6.30"E, 23.iii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236073.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia durin* 1981 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17689 *Stactobia durin* HOLOTYPE.

dwalin* Schmid 1983, *Stactobia

holotype (1 male, pinned: point)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Hanuman Chatti 30-VI-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 236063.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Chamoli District, Hanuman Chatti, 30°41'41"N 79°30'51"E, 30.vi.1958, F. Schmid, CNC236063.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia dwalin* 1981 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17683 *Stactobia dwalin* HOLOTYPE.

dwalur* Schmid 1983, *Stactobia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (W.B.) Dilpa 20-III-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236059.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. West Bengal:** Dilpa, 20.iii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236059.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia dwalur* 1981 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17681 *Stactobia dwalur* HOLOTYPE.

forsslundi* Schmid 1959c, *Stactobia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Iran (Ost.1) Waliabad 16-IX-1956 F.Schmid / CNC 236066.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. Mazandaran:** Waliabad, 36°15'7.07"N 51°18'5.81"E, 16.ix.1956, F. Schmid, CNC236066.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia forsslundi*

1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12461 *Stactobia forsslundi* HOLOTYPE.

Comment: The species name occurs in earlier in Schmid (1959b) as a *nomen nudum*.

froki* Schmid 1983, *Stactobia

holotype (1 male, pinned: point)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Lifakpo 15-III-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236088.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Liphakpu, 27°4'7"N 92°7'26"E, 15.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 236088.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia froki* 1982 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17718 *Stactobia froki* HOLOTYPE.

fualtaldeala* Schmid 1952, *Hydroptila

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Espagne (Av.) Val de Gredos 15-23-VII-1950 F. Schmid / CNC 235974.

Interpretive data: **SPAIN. Ávila:** Val de Gredos, 15-23.vii.1950, F. Schmid, CNC235974.

Determination: holotype ♂ *H. fualtaldeala* 1951 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12475 *Hydroptila fualtaldeala* HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Schmid, in his 1952 paper on Spanish Trichoptera, used an asterisk in his lists of material examined to denote which collection event contained the specimens he selected as holotype and allotype. For this species description, he placed the asterisk beside an event other than that from which the labeled holotype was selected ("Navarredonda, 24.VII"). In the description, the collection date for the Val de Gredos event is given as the 16th.

fuatejalona* Schmid 1952, *Oxyethira

Valid name: *Oxyethira unidentata* McLachlan 1884

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Espagne (Gr.) Gorges Guardalfeo 25-VIII-1950 F. Schmid / CNC 236007.

Interpretive data: **SPAIN. Granada:** Gorges Guardalfeo, 36°48'19"N 3°29'11"W, 25.viii.1950, F. Schmid, CNC236007.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Ox. fuatejalona* 1951 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12477 *Oxyethira fuatejalona* HOLOTYPE.

fuentelarbola Schmid 1952, Hydroptila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Espagne (Ma.) Cercedilla 8-VII-1950
F.Schmid / CNC 235955

Interpretive data: **SPAIN. Madrid:** Cercedilla,
40°44'26.01"N 4°3'25"W, 8.vii.1950, F.
Schmid, CNC235955.

Determination: holotype ♂ *H. fuentelarbola* 1951
F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12476 *Hydroptila* fuen-
tarbola HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Body excluding abdomen slide-
mounted on pin; location of abdomen un-
known.

gandhara Schmid 1960, Hydroptila

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Fron-
tier Province] Naran 30-VI,5-VII-1953
F.Schmid / CNC 235960.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakh-
tunkhwa:** Naran, 34°54'28"N 73°38'57"E, 30.
vi,5.vii.1953, F. Schmid, CNC235960.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Hydroptila* gandhara
1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12325 *Hydroptila*
gandhara HOLOTYPE.

gimli Schmid 1983, Stactobia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Akhrotkoti 17-18-V-
1958 F.Schmid / CNC 236064.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Pauri
Garhwal District, Akhrotkoti, 17-18.v.1958, F.
Schmid, CNC236064.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia* gimli 1981
F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17685 *Stactobia* gimli
HOLOTYPE.

gloin Schmid 1983, Stactobia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Teri Garhwal, Pau Kal 21-23-IV-1958
F.Schmid / CNC 236077.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Tehri
Garhwal District, Pau Kal, 21-23.iv.1958, F.
Schmid, CNC236077.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia* gloin 1981
F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17712 *Stactobia* gloin
HOLOTYPE.

grolin Schmid 1983, Stactobia

holotype (1 male, pinned: point)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and
Khasi Hills] Pynter 20-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC
236080.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** East Kha-
si Hills District, Pynter, 25°15'49"N 91°57'
49"E, 20.i.1959[?], F. Schmid, CNC236080.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia* grolin 1981
F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17713 *Stactobia* grolin
HOLOTYPE.

Comments: The date of collection in the descrip-
tion is 20.i.1958, and the date on the label is
20.i.1959, but Schmid's field notes indicate his
presence in Pynter in January 1960 from the
19th to the 23rd.

gwili Schmid 1983, Stactobia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Nyukmadong 22-IV-
1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236065.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:**
West Kameng District, Nyukmadung, 27°25'
1"N 92°7'57"E, 22.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC
236065.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia* gwili 1981
F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17686 *Stactobia* gwili
HOLOTYPE.

hochyangha Schmid 1959b, Hydroptila

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Iran (Ost.2) Firouzkuh 15-VII-1956
F.Schmid / CNC 235981.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. Tehran:** Firouzkuh, 35°
45'18"N 52°46'21"E, 15.vii.1956, F. Schmid,
CNC235981.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Hydroptila* hochyan-
gha 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12279 *Hydro-*
ptila hochyanga HOLOTYPE.

huor Schmid 1983, Stactobia

holotype (1 male, pinned: point)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Lungdur 14-III-1961
F.Schmid / CNC 236097.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:**
West Kameng District, Lungdur, 27°3'28"N
92°8'41"E, 14.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC236097.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia huor* 1982 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17701 *Stactobia huor* HOLOTYPE.

hurin Schmid 1983, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: point)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Dhur 8-9-IX-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 236096.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Pauri Garhwal District, Dhur, 8-9.ix.1958, F. Schmid, CNC236096.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia hurin* 1982 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17700 *Stactobia hurin* HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

indra Schmid 1960, *Microptila*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Cachem.et Jam. Shinghai Gah 6-8-VII-1954 F.Schmid / CNC 235944.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu & Kashmir:** Shinghai Gah, 6-8.vii.1954, F. Schmid, CNC235944.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Microptila indra* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12319 *Microptila indra* HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Locality a mountain stream near Gilgit, possibly 35°50'22.7"N 74°25'52.4"E or 35°50'23.3"N 74°22'32.7"E.

kala Schmid 1960, *Plethus*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Frontier Province] Balakot 23-VI-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 236032.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa:** Balakot, 34°32'22"N 73°21'2.01"E, 23.vi.1953, F. Schmid, CNC236032.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Plethus kala* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12322 *Plethus kala* HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Body and two wings on two separate slides on pin.

kimminsi Schmid 1959c, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Iran (Ost.3) Meyur 23-VIII-1956 F.Schmid / CNC 236045.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. Ardabil:** Moeil, 38° 17'44.60"N 47°42'58.63"E, 23.viii.1956, F. Schmid, CNC236045.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia kimminsi* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12460 *Stactobia kimminsi* HOLOTYPE.

Comment: The species name occurs in earlier in Schmid (1959b) as a *nomen nudum*.

klapaleki Schmid 1959c, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Cachem.et Jam. Chhantir Gah 5-7-VIII-1954 F.Schmid / CNC 236071.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu & Kashmir:** Chhantir Gah, 5-7.viii.1954, F. Schmid, CNC236071.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia klapaleki* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12465 *Stactobia klapaleki* HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Locality a river near Imit, possibly located at 36°33'58"N 73°47'45"E.

loki Schmid 1983, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Teri Garhwal, Pau Kal 21-23-IV-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 236084.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Tehri Garhwal District, Pau Kal, 21-23.iv.1958, F. Schmid, CNC236084.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia loki* 1981 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17717 *Stactobia loki* HOLOTYPE.

loni Schmid 1983, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: point)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Mawpran 9-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236078.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** East Khasi Hills District, Mawpran, 25°17'28"N 91°57'26"E, 9.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 236078.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia loni* 1981 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17711 *Stactobia loni* HOLOTYPE.

malacantosa Schmid 1952, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Espagne (Av.) Val de Gredos 15-23-VII-1950 F. Schmid / CNC 236050.

Interpretive data: **SPAIN**. **Ávila**: Val de Gredos, 15-23.vii.1950, F. Schmid, CNC236050.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia malacantosa* 1951 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12457 *Stactobia malacantosa* HOLOTYPE.

Comments: The type locality in the description is listed as "La Granja", with no date given.

marlieri Schmid 1959c, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Iran (Maz.) Polur 2-IX-1955 F.Schmid / CNC 236068.

Interpretive data: **IRAN**. **Mazandaran**: Polur, 35°50'47"N 52°2'52"E, 2.ix.1955, F. Schmid, CNC236068.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia marlieri* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12463 *Stactobia marlieri* HOLOTYPE.

Comment: The species name occurs in earlier in Schmid (1959b) as a *nomen nudum*.

martynovi Schmid 1959c, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Frontier Province] Lulu Sar 10-12-VII-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 236061.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN**. **Khyber Pakhtunkhwa**: Lulusar Lake, 35°4'54"N 73°55'32.01"E, 10-12.vii.1953, F. Schmid, CNC 236061.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia martynovi* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12464 *Stactobia martynovi* HOLOTYPE.

mayeri Schmid 1959c, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Iran (Ost.9) Bavaman 8, 10-VII-1956 F.Schmid / CNC 236067.

Interpretive data: **IRAN**. **North Khorasan**: Baba Aman, 37°28'37.71"N 57°26'22.83"E, 8,10.vii.1956, F. Schmid, CNC236067.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia mayeri* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12462 *Stactobia mayeri* HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Description listed collection dates of 9-10.vii.1956. The species name occurs earlier

in a work by Schmid (1959b) as a *nomen nudum*.

milinda (Schmid 1960), *Scelotrichia* [*Madioxyethira*]

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Cachem. et Jam. Shinghai Gah 6-8-VII-1954 F.Schmid / CNC 235953.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN**. **Azad Jammu & Kashmir**: Shinghai Gah, 6-8.vii.1954, F. Schmid, CNC235953.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Madioxyethira milinda* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12320 *Madioxyethira milinda* HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Locality a mountain stream near Gilgit, possibly 35°50'22.7"N 74°25'52.4"E or 35°50'23.3"N 74°22'32.7"E

morettii Schmid 1959c, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Frontier Province] Kawai [sic] 24-VI-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 236085.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN**. **Khyber Pakhtunkhwa**: Kiwai, 34°37'59.01"N 73°26'39"E, 24.vi.1953, F. Schmid, CNC236085.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia morettii* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12469 *Stactobia moretti* HOLOTYPE.

naili Schmid 1983, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (W.B.) Dilpa 20-III-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236100.

Interpretive data: **INDIA**. **West Bengal**: Dilpa, 20.iii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236100.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia naili* 1982 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17705 *Stactobia naili* HOLOTYPE.

nalin Schmid 1983, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: point)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Lungdur 14-III-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236081.

Interpretive data: **INDIA**. **Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Lungdur, 27°3'28"N 92°8'41"E, 14.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 236081.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia nalin* 1981
F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17715 *Stactobia nalin*
HOLOTYPE.

nielseni* Schmid 1959c, *Stactobia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Iran (Maz.) Zanuz 21-IX-1955
F.Schmid / CNC 236102.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. Mazandaran**: Zanoos,
36°19'59.42"N 51°32'37.03"E, 21.ix.1955, F.
Schmid, CNC236102.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia nielseni*
1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12470 *Stactobia*
nielseni HOLOTYPE.

Comment: The species name occurs in earlier in
Schmid (1959b) as a *nomen nudum*.

noldi* Schmid 1983, *Stactobia

holotype (1 male, pinned: point)
Verbatim: Inde (Kumaon) Loharket 19-IX-1958
F.Schmid / CNC 236090.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Bagesh-
war District, Loharkhet, 30°2'48"N 79°57'
35"E, 19.ix.1958, F. Schmid, CNC236090.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia noldi* 1982
F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17692 *Stactobia noldi*
HOLOTYPE.

nori* Schmid 1983, *Stactobia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Teri Garhwal, Pau Kal 21-23-IV-1958
F.Schmid / CNC 236104.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Tehri
Garhwal District, Pau Kal, 21-23.iv.1958, F.
Schmid, CNC236104.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia nori* 1982 F.
Schmid / CNCNo. 17709 *Stactobia nori* HO-
LOTYPE.

oin* Schmid 1983, *Stactobia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Pauri Gahrwal Rudraprayag 28-IV-
1958 F.Schmid / CNC 236087.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Rudra-
prayag District, Rudraprayag, 30°17'5"N 78°
58'52"E, 28.iv.1958, F. Schmid, CNC236087.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia oin* 1982 F.
Schmid / CNCNo. 17691 *Stactobia oin* HO-
LOTYPE.

ori* Schmid 1983, *Stactobia

holotype (1 male, pinned: point)
Verbatim: Sikkim Rhenok 5-IX-1959 F.Schmid /
CNC 236086.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Rhenock, 27°
10'31"N 88°38'40"E, 5.ix.1959, F. Schmid,
CNC236086.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia ori* 1982 F.
Schmid / CNCNo. 17690 *Stactobia ori* HOLO-
TYPE.

panchaoi* Schmid 1960, *Hydroptila

holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Cachem.et Jam. Kel 20-23-V-1954
F.Schmid / CNC 235967.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu &**
Kashmir: Cachem. et Jam., Kel, 34°49'31"N
74°21'16"E, 20-23.v.1954, F. Schmid, CNC
235967.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Hydroptila panchaoi*
1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12323 *Hydroptila*
panchaoi HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Published date of collection 16.viii.
1953; F. Schmid was at this locality during
both the label and published dates. The body
and abdomen are on two separate slides on the
pin.

paramartha* Schmid 1960, *Oxyethira

Valid name: *Oxyethira bogambara* Schmid 1958
holotype (1 male, pinned: point)
Verbatim: Bélouchistan Central Zarghun 1-3-V-
1953 F.Schmid / CNC 236006.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Balochistan**:
Central Zarghun, 1-3.v.1953, F. Schmid, CNC
236006.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oxyethira paramartha*
1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12328 *Oxyethira*
paramartha HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Genitalia, body and wings on three
separate slides on same pin.

parthava* Schmid 1959b, *Hydroptila

Valid name: *Hydroptila occulta* (Eaton 1873)
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Iran (Ost.9) Durb Adam 3-VII-1956
F.Schmid / CNC 235983.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. North Khorasan**: Dor-

badam, 37°29'30.60"N 58°27'51.94"E, 3.vii.1956, F. Schmid, CNC235983.

Determination: CNCNo. 12276 *Hydroptila parthava* Schmid HOLOTYPE / holotype ♂ *Hydroptila parthava* 1957 F. Schmid.

radovanovici Schmid 1959c, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pakistan (Chitral) Khoghozi 3-5-X-1954 F.Schmid / CNC 236109.

Interpretive data: PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa: Chitral District, Kaghazi, 35°56'36.97"N 71°56'3.83"E, 3-5.x.1954, F. Schmid, CNC236109.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia radovanovici* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12472 *Stactobia radovanovici* HOLOTYPE.

risiana Schmid 1959c, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Bélouchistan Central Zarghun 1-3-V-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 236103.

Interpretive data: PAKISTAN. Balochistan: Central Zarghun, 1-3.v.1953, F. Schmid, CNC 236103.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia risiana* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12471 *Stactobia risiana* HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Body and two wings on two separate slides on pin.

roudra Schmid 1960, *Microptila*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Frontier Province] Kawai 24-VI-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 235951.

Interpretive data: PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa: Kiwai, 34°37'59.01"N 73°26'39"E, 24.vi.1953, F. Schmid, CNC235951.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Microptila roudra* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12317 *Microptila roudra* HOLOTYPE.

sanghala Schmid 1960, *Hydroptila*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pakistan (Chitral) Shogor 16-X-1954 F.Schmid / CNC 235959.

Interpretive data: PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa:

tunkhwa: Chitral District, Shogor, 36°0'55"N 71°45'51"E, 16.x.1954, F. Schmid, CNC 235959.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Hydroptila sanghala* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12326 *Hydroptila sanghala* HOLOTYPE.

sengavi Schmid 1960, *Hydroptila*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Cachem. et Jam. Gilgit 9-27.VII.1954 F.Schmid / CNC 235965.

Interpretive data: PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu & Kashmir: Gilgit, 35°55'15"N 74°18'30"E, 9-27.vii.1954, F. Schmid, CNC235965.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Hydroptila sengavi* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12324 *Hydroptila sengavi* HOLOTYPE.

smoli Schmid 1983, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: point)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Lakadong 4-I-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236105.

Interpretive data: INDIA. Meghalaya: Jaintia Hills District, Lakadong, 4.i.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236105.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia smoli* 1982 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17706 *Stactobia smoli* HOLOTYPE.

snori Schmid 1983, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Nyukmadong 18-IV-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236094.

Interpretive data: INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh: West Kameng District, Nyukmadung, 27°25'1"N 92°7'57"E, 18.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 236094.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia snori* 1982 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17696 *Stactobia snori* HOLOTYPE.

snufi Schmid 1983, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Sikkim Karponang 23-VIII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236092.

Interpretive data: INDIA. Sikkim: Karponang, 23.viii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236092.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia snufi* 1982
F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17697 *Stactobia snufi*
HOLOTYPE.

sourya (Schmid 1960), *Ugandatrichia* [*Microptila*]

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Cachem. et Jam. Surgun 29-30-VII-1953 F. Schmid / CNC 235937.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu & Kashmir**: Surgun, 34°52'6.38"N 74°12'10.40"E, 29-30.vii.1953, F. Schmid, CNC 235937.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Microptila sourya* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12316 *Microptila sourya* HOLOTYPE.

teldi Schmid 1983, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Kumaon) Loharket 19-IX-1958 F. Schmid / CNC 236091.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Bageshwar District, Loharket, 30°2'48"N 79°57'35"E, 19.ix.1958, F. Schmid, CNC236091.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia teldi* 1982 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17693 *Stactobia teldi* HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Slide mounted on pin.

thorin Schmid 1983, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pauri Gahrwal Jungal Chatti 11-V-1958 F. Schmid / CNC 236069.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Pauri Garhwal District, Jungal Chatti, 11.v.1958, F. Schmid, CNC236069.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia thorin* 1981 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17687 *Stactobia thorin* HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Locality on road between Gaurikund and Kedarnath, ~30°42'25N 79°3'47"E. Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

thrain Schmid 1983, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Sikkim Karponang 23-VIII-1959 F. Schmid / CNC 236070.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Karponang,

23.viii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236070.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia thrain* 1981 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17688 *Stactobia thrain* HOLOTYPE.

throhir Schmid 1983, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Sirohi Kashong 7-VI-1960 F. Schmid / CNC 236095.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Sirohi Kashong, 25°6'23.19"N 94°27'28.51"E, 7.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236095.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia throhir* 1982 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17699 *Stactobia throhir* HOLOTYPE.

Comments: The description listed the day of collection as the 8th; during June 1960, Schmid was at Sirohi Kashong from the 6th to the 10th. Wings and abdomen slide-mounted on 2 slides on pin, location of remainder of body unknown.

throli Schmid 1983, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: point)

Verbatim: Sikkim Rangli [sic] 3-IX-1959 F. Schmid / CNC 236089.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Rangli, 27°12'12.06"N 88°42'9.85"E, 3.ix.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236089.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia throli* 1982 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17694 *Stactobia throli* HOLOTYPE.

thror Schmid 1983, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Chug 15-IV-1961 F. Schmid / CNC 236093.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Chug, 27°25'4"N 92°14'3"E, 15.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 236093.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia thror* 1982 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17698 *Stactobia thror* HOLOTYPE.

tjederi Schmid 1959c, *Stactobia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: point)

Verbatim: Cachem. et Jam. Dunga Nar 27-VII-1953 F. Schmid / CNC 236072.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu & Kashmir:** Dunga Nar, 27.vii.1953, F. Schmid, CNC236072.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia tjederi* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12466 *Stactobia tjederi* HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Locality a stream east of the border on the path to Surgun, possibly ~34°54'11"N 74°5'48"E.

touroumaya* Schmid 1960, *Hydroptila

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pakistan (Penjab) Hassan Abdal 27-XII-1954 F.Schmid / CNC 235966.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Punjab:** Hassan Abdal, 33°49'10"N 72°41'21"E, 27.xii.1954, F. Schmid, CNC235966.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Hydroptila touroumaya* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12327 *Hydroptila touroumaya* HOLOTYPE.

tuor* Schmid 1983, *Stactobia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Sihai Khulen [sic] 25-VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236098.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Sihai Khulen, 25°10'10"N 94°29'13"E, 25.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236098.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia tuor* 1982 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 17702 *Stactobia tuor* HOLOTYPE.

ulmeriana* Schmid 1959c, *Stactobia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Frontier Province] Mahandri 26-VI-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 236075.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa:** Mahandri, 34°41'40"N 73°34'27"E, 26.vi.1953, F. Schmid, CNC236075.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia ulmeriana* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12468 *Stactobia ulmeriana* HOLOTYPE.

vaillanti* Schmid 1959c, *Stactobia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Guinée franç. Kindia 1-15-V-1955 F.Schmid / CNC 236108.

Interpretive data: **GUINEA.** Kindia, under the hydro-electric road of the Pasteur Institute of Kindia, 10°2'26.01"N 12°51'46"W, 1-15.v.1955, F. Schmid, CNC236108.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stactobia vaillanti* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12473 *Stactobia vaillanti* HOLOTYPE.

valesiaca* Schmid 1947, *Hydroptila

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Suisse-Valais Praz de Fort 11-VII-1944 F. Schmid / CNC 235957.

Interpretive data: **SWITZERLAND. Valais:** Praz-de-Fort, Val Ferret, 45°57'0"N 7°8'0"E, 1200m, 11.vii.1944, F. Schmid, CNC235957.

Determination: holotype ♂ *H. valesiaca* 1947 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12479 *Hydroptila valesiaca* HOLOTYPE.

vichtaspa* Schmid 1959b, *Hydroptila

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Iran (Ost.2) Karasang [sic] 21-V-1956 F.Schmid / CNC 235964.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. Mazandaran:** Karsang, 36°18'18.80"N 52°22'20.18"E, 21.v.1956, F. Schmid, CNC235964.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Hydroptila vichtaspa* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12278 *Hydroptila vichtaspa* HOLOTYPE.

LEPIDOSTOMATIDAE

***arachosicum* (Schmid 1961), *Lepidostoma* [*Dinarthrum*]**

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Bélouchistan Central Zarghun 1-3-V-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 280328.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Balochistan:** Central Zarghun, 1-3.v.1953, F. Schmid, CNC 280328.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Dinarthrum arachosicum* 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12368 *Dinarthrum arachosicum*.

Comments: Wing mounted on separately pinned slide.

aykroydi* Weaver 1999, *Paraphlegopteryx

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Chingsao 13-VI-1960
F.Schmid / CNC 280356.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Chingsao,
13.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC280356.

Determination: Holotype ♂ Paraphlegopteryx
aykroydi Weaver 1994.

bhatarka (Schmid 1961), *Lepidostoma* [*Dinarthrum*]

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Cachem.et Jam. Langar 20-IX-1954
F.Schmid / CNC 280329.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu & Kashmir**:
Langar, 36°04'60.0"N 72°36'58.5"E, 20.ix.1954, F. Schmid, CNC280329.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Dinarthrum bhatarka*
1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
12366 *Dinarthrum bhatarka*.

bulbosa Weaver 1999, *Paraphlegopteryx*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Chingsao 13-VI-1960
F.Schmid / CNC 280357.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Chingsao,
13.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC280357.

Determination: Holotype ♂ *Paraphlegopteryx*
bulbosus Weaver.

chotta (Schmid 1961), *Lepidostoma* [*Dinarthrum*]

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Frontier
Province] Balakot 16-X-1953 F.Schmid /
CNC 280330.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa**:
Balakot, 34°32'22"N 73°21'2.01"E,
16.x.1953, F. Schmid, CNC280330.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Dinarthrum chotta*
1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
12364 *Dinarthrum chotta*.

divaricatum (Weaver 1989), *Lepidostoma* [*Goerodes*]

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.P.) Rishikesh 25-31-III-1958
F.Schmid / CNC 280349.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Rishikesh,
30°5'3"N 78°15'53"E, 25-31.iii.1958, F.
Schmid, CNC280349.

Determination: Holotype ♂ *Goerodes divaricata*
Weaver.

Comments: Four wings on slide attached to pin,
remainder of body in vial.

iranicum (Schmid 1959b), *Lepidostoma* [*Dinarthrum*]

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Iran (Maz.) Zanuz 21-IX-1955
F.Schmid / CNC 280333.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. Mazandaran**: Zanoos,
36°19'59.42"N 51°32'37.03"E, 21.ix.1955, F.
Schmid, CNC280333.

Determination: holotype *Dinarthrum iranicum*
1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
12296 *Dinarthrum iranicum*.

ivanovi Weaver 1999, *Paraphlegopteryx*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Tairenpokpi 31-V-1960
F.Schmid / CNC 481699.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Tairenpokpi,
24°49'30"N 93°48'11.01"E, 31.v.1960, F.
Schmid, CNC481699.

Determination: HOLOTYPE ♂ *Paraphlegopteryx*
curtinae sp. n. Weaver / TYPE ♂ *Paraphlegopteryx*
curtinae / *Paraphlegopteryx curtinae*
Weaver, sp. n. / *curtinae* = unpublished ms
name later replaced by *ivanovi* O.L.

Comments: Wings slide mounted on same pin.

kamengensis Weaver 1999, *Paraphlegopteryx*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Tampa La 2-IX-1961
F.Schmid / CNC 280354.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
Kameng Frontier Division [now divided into
the districts of Tawang, East Kameng and
West Kameng], Tampa La, 2.ix.1961, F.
Schmid, CNC280354.

Determination: Holotype ♂ *Paraphlegopteryx*
kamengensis Weaver.

karagraha (Schmid 1961), *Lepidostoma* [*Dinarthrum*]

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Cachem.et Jam. Dalti 7-IX-1954
F.Schmid / CNC 280331.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu &**

- Kashmir:** Dalti, 36°23'40"N 73°15'5"E, 7.ix.1954, F. Schmid, CNC280331.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Dinarthrum karagraha* 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12367 *Dinarthrum karagraha* [sic].
Comments: One wing separately slide-mounted on pin.
- khorrassanicum (Schmid 1959b), *Lepidostoma [Dinarthrum]***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Iran (Ost.9) Mughan 20-VI-1956 F.Schmid / CNC 280335.
Interpretive data: **IRAN. Razavi Khorasan:** Moghaan, 36°8'12.87"N 59°22'37.92"E, 20.vi.1956, F. Schmid, CNC280335.
Determination: holotype *Dinarthrum khorrassanicum* 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 12297 *Dinarthrum khorrassanicum* [sic].
- koutchik (Schmid 1959b), *Lepidostoma [Dinarthrum]***
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Iran (Ost. 2) Garna 9-10-V-1956 F.Schmid / CNC 280336.
Interpretive data: **IRAN. Mazandaran:** Garna, 35°53'47"N 52°11'2"E, 9-10.v.1956, F. Schmid, CNC280336.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Dinarthrum koutchik* 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12298 *Dinarthrum koutchik*.
- lacinatatum Flint 1967, *Lepidostoma***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: 10 mi.W.El Salto Dgo.MEXICO,9000' 2.VII.1964 J.E.H.Martin / CNC 280306.
Interpretive data: **MEXICO. Durango:** 16.1 km W El Salto, 23°43'9.69"N 105°29'21.66"W, 2743m, 2.vii.1964, J.E.H. Martin, CNC 280306.
Determination: HOLOTYPE ♂ *Lepidostoma lacinatatum* Flint / CNCNo. 12843 *Lepidostoma lacinatatum* HOLOTYPE.
- lindbergi (Schmid 1963b), *Lepidostoma [Dinarthrum]***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Afghanistan Doavi 4-VIII-1960 K. Lindberg / CNC 280337.
- Interpretive data:* **AFGHANISTAN. Badakhshan:** Doavi, Pamir de Schiva, 36°33'32.98"N 70°21'46.78"E, 2250m, 4.viii.1960, K. Lindberg, CNC280337.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Dinarthrum lindbergi* 1962 F. Schmid.
- martynovi Weaver 1999, *Paraphlegopteryx***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Mattiyang 17-VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 280358.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Mattiyang, 17.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC280358.
Determination: Holotype ♂ *Paraphlegopteryx martynovi* Weaver.
- monospina Botoșăneanu 1960, *Crunoecia***
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Macédoine Perister 12-16-VIII-1955 F.Schmid / CNC 758904.
Interpretive data: **MACEDONIA.** Baba Mountain, 41°0'12"N 21°11'3"E, 12-16.viii.1955, F. Schmid, CNC758904.
Determination: *Crunoecia monospina* Bots. ♂. / Holotype ♂.
- moselyi Weaver 1999, *Paraphlegopteryx***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Saran [sic] 17-IX-1958 F.Schmid / Weaver illust. M Kelly / CNC 481644.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Pauri Garhwal District, Sarana, 29°33'17"N 79°34'13"E, 17.ix.1958, F. Schmid, CNC481644.
Determination: HOLOTYPE ♂ *Paraphlegopteryx moselyi* Weaver.
- orestes Weaver 1999, *Paraphlegopteryx***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Sikkim Lachung 2-13-VII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 481645.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Lachung, 27°41'20"N 88°44'36"E, 2-13.vii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC481645.
Determination: HOLOTYPE ♂ *Paraphlegopteryx orestes* Weaver.
- pippini Weaver 1999, *Paraphlegopteryx***
holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Chamiteng 24-VIII-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 280359.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Chamiteng,
24.viii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC280359.

Determination: Holotype ♂ Paraphlegopteryx
pippini Weaver.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

porntipae Weaver 1999, Paraphlegopteryx

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Sirohi Kashong 7-VI-
1960 F. Schmid / CNC 481651.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Sirohi Kash-
ong, 25°6'23.19"N 94°27'28.51"E, 2133-2286
m, 7.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC481651.

Determination: HOLOTYPE ♂ Paraphlegopteryx
nagai n. sp. Weaver / nagai = unpublished ms
name later replaced by porntipae O.L.

rectangulare Flint 1967, Lepidostoma

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: 10 mi.W.El Salto Dgo.MEXICO,9000'
25.VII.1964 W.C.McGuffin / CNC 280313.

Interpretive data: **MEXICO. Durango**: 16.1 km
W El Salto, 23°43'9.69"N 105°29'21.66"W,
2743m, 25.vii.1964, W.C. McGuffin, CNC
280313.

Determination: HOLOTYPE ♂ Lepidostoma rec-
tangulare Flint / CNCNo. 12842 Lepidostoma
rectangularis HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Two wings on each of two slides, one
on pin with remainder of body and one sepa-
rate; abdomen in vial, vestige of remainder of
body remaining on pin.

schmidi Weaver 1993, Zephyropsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Nakhu 4-VII-1961
F.Schmid / ♂ in copula with paratype ♀ / CNC
280364.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
West Kameng District, Nakhu, 27°24'9"N
92°33'38.01"E, 4.vii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC
280364.

Determination: Holotype ♂ Zephyropsyche
schmidi Weaver.

schmidi Weaver 1999, Paraphlegopteryx

holotype (1 male, pinned) (Figs 5, 6)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Jhum La 1-2-VI-
1961 F.Schmid / CNC 280361.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
Kameng Frontier Division [now divided into
the districts of Tawang, East Kameng and
West Kameng], Jhum La, 1-2.vi.1961, F.
Schmid, CNC280361.

Determination: Holotype ♂ Paraphlegopteryx
schmidi Weaver.

squamalata Weaver 1999, Paraphlegopteryx

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Bombdi La 13-21-
VI-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 280355.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
West Kameng District, Bomdila, 27°15'51"N
92°24'58"E, 13-21.vi.1961, F. Schmid, CNC
280355.

Determination: Holotype ♂ Paraphlegopteryx
squamalata Weaver.

**surashtra (Schmid 1961), Lepidostoma [Din-
arthrum]**

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Cachem.et Jam. Janwai 29-VIII-1953
F.Schmid F.Schmid / CNC 280340.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu &
Kashmir**: Janwai, 34°47'40"N 74°32'0"E, 29.
viii.1953, F. Schmid, CNC280340.

Determination: holotype ♂ Dinarthrum surashtra
1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
12365 Dinarthrum surashtra.

ulmeri Weaver 1999, Paraphlegopteryx

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Saran [sic] 17-IX-1958
F. Schmid / CNC 280360.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Pauri
Garhwal District, Sarana, 29°33'17"N 79°34'
13"E, 17.ix.1958, F. Schmid, CNC280360.

Determination: Holotype ♂ Paraphlegopteryx ul-
meri Weaver.

LEPTOCERIDAE

abhichobhita Schmid 1987, Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Teri Garhwal Ampata 8-10-IV-1958
F.Schmid / CNC 311835.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Tehri Garhwal District, Ampata, 30°16'6"N 78°22'18"E, 8-10.iv.1958, F. Schmid, CNC311835.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes abhichobhita* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18901 *Setodes abhichobhita*.

abhinagupta* Schmid 1995b, *Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Mawpran 8-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311603.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** East Khasi Hills District, Mawpran, 25°17'28"N 91°57'26"E, 8.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 311603.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis abhinagupta* 1995 F. Schmid / *Oecetis abhinagupta* S. CNC No. 22096 HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

abhiramika* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Yodpai 16-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311845.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka:** Yodpai, 16.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311845.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes abhiramika* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18909 *Setodes abhiramika*.

abhirupa* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Teri Garhwal Ampata 8-10-IV-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 311850.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Tehri Garhwal District, Ampata, 30°16'6"N 78°22'18"E, 8-10.iv.1958, F. Schmid, CNC311850.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes abhirupa* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18914 *Setodes abhirupa*.

abhrayita* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Hariarpur 25-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311824.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka:** Hariharapura, 13°31'18"N 75°17'59.90"E, 25.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311824.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes abhrayita* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18892 *Setodes abhrayita*.

acchidra* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Gudalur 6-7-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311847.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu:** Gudalur, 11°30'13"N 76°29'29"E, 6-7.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311847.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes acchidra* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18911 *Setodes acchidra*.

acte* Schmid 1994c, *Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Khumyara 3-4-V-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 311555.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Pauri Garhwal District, Khumyara, 3-4.v.1958, F. Schmid, CNC311555.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella acte* 1993 F. Schmid / *Adicella acte* Schmid CNC [type no.] 21718 Holotype ♂.

Comments: Locality possibly Khumara (30°33'15"N 79°3'44"W).

adusita* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.D.M.N.C.H.) [=United district of Mikir Hills and North Cachar] Sirtrang 28-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311838.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Assam:** United District now treated as separate Mikir Hills and Karbi Anglong Districts, Sirtrang, 28.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311838.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes adusita* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18903 *Setodes adusita*.

aemulator* Schmid 1993b, *Leptoceriella

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Senbaganur 3-8-XII-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 311492.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu:** Senbaganur, 10°13'59.01"N 77°30'49"E, 3-8.xii.1958, F. Schmid, CNC311492.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptoceriella aemu-*

lator 1993 F. Schmid / Holotype ♂ *Leptoceriella aemulator* Sch. CNC [type no.] 21670.

agarhita Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Kongai 7-VII-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311849.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Kongai, 25°20'32"N 94°31'31"E, 7.vii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311849.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes agarhita* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18913 *Setodes agarhita*.

aglae Schmid 1994c, *Adicella*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Yodpai 16-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311577.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka**: (Mysore) Yodpai, 16.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311577.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella aglae* 1993 F. Schmid / *Adicella aglae* Sch. CNC 21743 Holotype ♂.

agunachila Schmid 1987, *Leptocerus*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Amatulla 24-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311711.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Amatulla, 26°55'47"N 92°7'18"E, 24.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 311711.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptocerus agunachila* 1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18981 *Leptocerus agunachila*.

akalanka Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Lungdur 14-III-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311801.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Lungdur, 27°3'28"N 92°8'41"E, 14.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 311801.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes akalanka* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18875 *Setodes akalanka*.

akchepana Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Kakankote 10-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311792.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka**: Kakankote, 11°54'0"N 76°12'0"E, 10.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311792.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes akchepana* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18872 *Setodes akchepana*.

akhunta Schmid 1987, *Leptocerus*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Rupa 12-VI-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311697.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Rupa, 27°12'11.01"N 92°23'55"E, 12.vi.1961, CNC311697.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptocerus akhunta* 1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18969 *Leptocerus akhunta*.

akilbicha Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Balamore 3-4-I-1962 F.Schmid / CNC 311848.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Madras** [likely in either present day Kerala or Tamil Nadu State], Balamore, 3-4.i.1962, F. Schmid, CNC311848.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes akilbicha* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18912 *Setodes akilbicha*.

akrura Gordon & Schmid 1987 [In: Schmid (1987)], ***Setodes***

holotype+allotype (2 male/female, ethyl alcohol)

Verbatim: THAILAND: chw. Kanchanaburi: amp. Si Sawat; Kwaeyay River at Salakphra Game Sanctuary, July 20, 1976 A.E. Gordon / CNC 165684.

Interpretive data: **THAILAND. Kanchanaburi**: Si Sawat, Kwaeyay River at Salakphra Game Sanctuary, 14°8'29"N 99°20'26.01"E, 20.vii.1976, A.E. Gordon, CNC165684.

Determination: *Setodes akrura*, n. sp. Gordon and Schmid, HOLOTYPE: MALE ALLOTYPE: FEMALE / *Setodes akrura* Gordon and Schmid Holotype ♂, allotype ♀.

Comments: Original publication notes depository as TISTR, Thailand.

akunchita Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Kattalaimala 25-26-XII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311886.

Interpretive data: **INDIA**. Madras [likely in either present day Kerala or Tamil Nadu State], Kattalaimala, 25-26.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 311886.

Determination: holotype *Setodes akunchita* [sic] 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18949 *Setodes akunchita*.

akutila Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Nagodi 28-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311879.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka**: Nagodi, 13°55'47"N 74°54'10"E, 28.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311879.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes akutila* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18942 *Setodes akutila*.

akutsita Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Lushai) [=Mizo Hills] Phaileng 14-IX-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311855.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Mizoram**: Phaileng, 23°42'1"N 92°29'22"E, 14.ix.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311855.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes akutsita* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18919 *Setodes akutsita*.

alampata Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Mawja 30-III-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311786.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: United Jaintia and Khasi Hills [now divided into East and West Khasi Hills Districts and East and West Jaintia Hills Districts], Mawja, 30.iii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311786.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes alampata* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18867 *Setodes alampata*.

alcyo Schmid 1994c, *Adicella*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Nongrim 28-III-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311587.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: West Khasi Hills District, Nongrim, 25°34'1"N 91°54'9"E, 28.iii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311587.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella alcyo* 1992 F. Schmid / *Adicella alcyo* Schm CNC [type no.] 21731 Holotype ♂.

alukcha Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.P.) Rishikesh 25-31-III-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 311822.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Rishikesh, 30°5'3"N 78°15'53"E, 25-31.iii.1958, F. Schmid, CNC311822.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes alukcha* 1983 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18889 *Setodes alukcha*.

amudita Holzenthal & Andersen 2007, *Fernandoschmidia*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Bhairabkunda 3-4, 7-III-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311665.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: Udalguri District, Bhairabkunda, 26°53'2"N 92°6'51"E, 3-4,7.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 311665.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tagalopsyche amudita* 1973 F. Schmid [folded label] / HOLOTYPE *Fernandoschmidia amudita* Holzenthal + Andersen 2007.

androconifera Schmid 1959b, *Adicella*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Iran (Ost.9) Mughan 20-VI-1956 F.Schmid / CNC 311544.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. Razavi Khorasan**: Mughan, 36°8'12.87"N 59°22'37.92"E, 20.vi.1956, F. Schmid, CNC311544.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella androconifera* 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12295 *Adicella androconifera*.

angirasa Schmid 1995c, Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Mawpran 8-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311645.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** East Khasi Hills District, Mawpran, 25°17'28"N 91°57'26"E, 8.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311645.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis angirasa* 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Oecetis angirasa* CNC No. 22155.

Comments: Description incorrectly listed date of collection as the 6th.

angriamani (Schmid 1959b), Athripsodes [Leptocerus]

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Iran (Ost. 9) Bavaman 8, 10-VII-1956 F. Schmid / F. Schmid Colln. / CNC 481652.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. North Khorasan:** Baba Aman, 37°28'37.71"N 57°26'22.83"E, 10.vii.1956, F. Schmid, CNC481652.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptocerus angriamani* F. Schmid 1957 HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12294 *Leptocerus angriamani*.

aniruddha Schmid 1995c, Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Imphal 22-26-VIII-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311642.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Imphal, 24°49'10"N 93°56'16"E, 22-26.viii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311642.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis aniruddha* 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Oecetis aniruddha* CNCNo. 22159.

ankuchagraha Schmid 1987, Leptocerus

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Amatulla 17-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311700.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Amatulla, 26°55'47"N 92°7'18"E, 17.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 311700.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptocerus ankuchagraha* 1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18972 *Leptocerus ankuchagraha*.

antardhana Schmid 1987, Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Nakhu 3-VII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311804.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Nakhu, 27°24'9"N 92°33'38.01"E, 3.vii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 311804.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes antardhana* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18878 *Setodes antardhana*.

aparimeya Schmid 1987, Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Bilo La 9-VI-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311864.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** Kameng Frontier Division [now divided into the districts of Tawang, East Kameng and West Kameng], Bilo La, 9.vi.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311864.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes aparimeya* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18928 *Setodes aparimeya*.

apinchanga Schmid 1987, Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Mawpran 9-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311769.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** East Khasi Hills District, Mawpran, 25°17'28"N 91°57'26"E, 9.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 311769.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes apinchanga* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18854 *Setodes apinchanga*.

apitayati Schmid 1987, Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Bokhar 28-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311770.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Boha, 27°1'2"N 92°9'54"E, 28.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311770.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes apitayati* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18855 *Setodes apitayati*.

aprachasta* Schmid 1987, *Leptocerus

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Longbi Khulen 30-VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311710.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Nungbi Khullen, 25°12'10"N 94°26'54"E, 30.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311710.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptocerus aprachasta* 1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18979 *Leptocerus aprachasta*.

apratita* Holzenthal & Andersen 2007, *Tagalopsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills], Nongjni [sic] 19-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311668.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: West Jaintia Hills District, Nongjngi, 25°32'32"N 92°16'20"E, 19.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 311668.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tagalopsyche apratita* 1973 F. Schmid [folded label] / HOLOTYPE ♂ *Tagalopsyche apratita* Holzenthal + Andersen 2007.

aramaniya* Holzenthal & Andersen 2007, *Fernandoschmidia

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Demthring 16-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC / CNC 311666.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: East Khasi Hills District, Demthring, 25°33'28"N 91°54'35"E, 16.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 311666.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tagalopsyche aramaniya* 1973 F. Schmid [folded label] / HOLOTYPE *Fernandoschmidia aramaniya* Holzenthal + Andersen 2007.

argentiguttatus* Gordon & Schmid 1987 [In: Schmid (1987)], *Setodes

holotype+allotype (2 male/female, ethyl alcohol)

Verbatim: THAILAND: Chw. Loei, amp. Muang Loei River, June 27, 1976 A.E. Gordon, light trap / CNC 165686.

Interpretive data: **THAILAND. Loei**: amp.

Muang, Loei River, 17°31'47"N 101°43'33"E, 27.vi.1976, A.E. Gordon, light trap, CNC 165686.

Determination: *Setodes argentiguttatus* Gordon and Schmid, HOLOTYPE: MALE; ALLOTYPE: FEMALE / *Setodes argentiguttatus* Gordon and Schmid, holotype ♂, Allotype ♀.

arjuna* Schmid 1968a, *Poecilopsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Nongrim 28-III-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311671.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: West Khasi Hills District, Nongrim, 25°34'1"N 91°54'9"E, 28.iii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311671.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Poecilopsyche arjuna* 1967 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11399 *Poec. arjuna*.

asadharana* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Senbaganur 3-8-XII-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 311877.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu**: Senbaganur, 10°13'59.01"N 77°30'49"E, 3-8.xii.1958, F. Schmid, CNC311877.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes asadharana* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18940 *Setodes asadharana*.

Comments: The description incorrectly stated the date of collection as 3-8.viii.1958. Schmid was actually in Senbaganur in December on the 3rd, 6th, 7th and 8th. Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

asammuaddha* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Kulgunda [sic] 21-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311815.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka**: Kulkunda, 12°41'15"N 75°36'35"E, 21.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311815.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes asammuaddha* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18883 *Setodes asammuaddha*.

nagarjouna assamicus* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Khasi and Jaintia Hills] Mawshun 6-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311819.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: East Khasi Hills District, Mawshun, 25°14'44.01"N 91°58'26"E, 6.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 311819.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Set. nagarjouna assamicus* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 18885 *Setodes nagarjouna assamicus*.

athys* Schmid 1994c, *Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Chattrik 21-VII-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311575.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Chattrik, 24°57'29.01"N 94°37'12"E, 21.vii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311575.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella athys* 1993 F. Schmid / *Adicella athys* Schm. CNC [type no.] 21736 Holotype ♂.

atibhadrata* Schmid 1987, *Trichosetodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Lagairong 26-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311894.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Lagairong, 24°42'0"N 93°32'0"E, 26.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311894.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Trichosetodes atibhadrata* 1984 F. Schmid / LECTOTYPE CNCNo. 18954 Tr. *atibhadrata*.

Comments: The additional Lectotype label associated with the holotype is misleading, as no lectotype has been designated, nor is it necessary, with the holotype explicitly listed in the original description.

atichayana* Schmid 1987, *Trichosetodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Leimatak 29-30-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311895.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Leimatak River [~24°40'58"N, 93°37'00"E], 29-30.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311895.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Trichosetodes atichayana* 1984 F. Schmid / LECTOTYPE CNCNo. 18955 Tr. *atichayana*.

Comments: The additional Lectotype label associated with the holotype is misleading, as no lectotype has been designated, nor is it necessary, with the holotype explicitly listed in the original description.

atidhanin* Schmid 1987, *Trichosetodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (W.B.) Singtam 11-III-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311892.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Singtam, 27°8'13"N 88°23'34"E, 11.iii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311892.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Trichosetodes atidhanin* 1984 F. Schmid / LECTOTYPE CNC No. 18952 Tr. *atidhanin*.

Comments: The additional Lectotype label associated with the holotype is misleading, as no lectotype has been designated, nor is it necessary, with the holotype explicitly listed in the original description.

atidvaya* Schmid 1987, *Leptocerus

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Amatulla 23-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311731.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Amatulla, 26°55'47"N 92°7'18"E, 23.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 311731.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptocerus atidvaya* [sic] 1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18993 *Leptocerus atidvaya*.

atiguna* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Jarain 13-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311859.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: Jaintia Hills District, Jarain, 25°22'50.01"N 92°8'58"E, 13.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311859.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes atiguna* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18923 *Setodes atiguna*.

atiharin* Schmid 1987, *Trichosetodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Bombay) Patan 3-II-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 311903.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Gujarat**: Patan, 23°
50'58"N 72°7'35"E, 3.ii.1959, F. Schmid,
CNC311903.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Trichosetodes* *atisukha* [*lapsus*] 1984 F. Schmid / Holotype *Trichosetodes atiharin* Schmid, Det. O. Lonsdale / LECTOTYPE CNCNo. 18961 Tr. atiharin.

Comments: The holotype labels for *T. atisukha* and *T. atiharin* appear to have been placed on the incorrect specimens by Schmid, as suggested by agreement between collection data in the descriptions and labels. The additional Lectotype label associated with the holotype is misleading, as no lectotype has been designated, nor is it necessary, with the holotype explicitly listed in the original description.

atiloma* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype[?] (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Uppinangadi 17-I-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 311883.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka**: Uppinangady, 12°50'23"N 75°23'52"E, 17.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311883.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes atiloma* 1985
F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18946
Setodes atiloma.

Comments: Data for the holotype in the description is "Mysore, Yodpai 16-I-1959", which among available specimens is found on ten nontypes, the female allotype, and seven male and four female paratypes. Uppinangadi is not mentioned in the description. The only remaining specimen identified as *S. atiloma* is one dissected specimen without a paratype label (Madras, Krishnappanayakkan, 21.i.1962, F. Schmid). Therefore, the specimen labeled as the holotype may not actually represent the holotype. Closer scrutiny of these specimens is required before type designation for this species is considered definitive.

atipunya* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Subrahmanya 20-I-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 311826.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka**: Subrahmanya, 12°40'9"N 75°36'38.01"E, 20.i.1959,
F. Schmid, CNC311826.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes atipunya* 1985
F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18890
Setodes atipunya.

atiramaniya* Schmid 1987, *Trichosetodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Serrarim 3-X-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311902.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: United Jaintia and Khasi Hills [now divided into East and West Khasi Hills Districts and East and West Jaintia Hills Districts], Serrarim, 3.x. 1960, F. Schmid, CNC311902.

Determination: LECTOTYPE CNCNo. 18956 Tr. *atiramaniya* / holotype ♂ *Trichosetodes atiramaniya* 1984 F. Schmid.

Comments: The locality is possibly Soharim (25°20'59"N 91°44'51"E), which is close to other localities visited in October 1960. The additional Lectotype label associated with the holotype is misleading, as no lectotype has been designated, nor is it necessary, with the holotype explicitly listed in the original description.

atiraskrita* Schmid 1987, *Leptocerus

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Yellapur 30-I-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 311727.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka**: Yellapur, 14°57'49"N 74°42'43"E, 30.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311727.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptocerus atiraskrita* 1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18977
Leptocerus atiraskrita.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

atirupa* Schmid 1987, *Trichosetodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Nongjni [sic] 19-IV-1960
F.Schmid / CNC 311896.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: West Jaintia Hills District, Nonggingi, 25°32'32"N 92°16'

20°E, 19.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311896.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Trichosetodes atirupa*
1984 F. Schmid / LECTOTYPE CNCNo.
18957 Tr. *atirupa*.

Comments: The additional Lectotype label associated with the holotype is misleading, as no lectotype has been designated, nor is it necessary, with the holotype explicitly listed in the original description.

atisubhaga* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Marou 14-VIII-1960
F.Schmid / CNC 311869.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Marou, 24°
54'28"N 94°15'0"E, 14.viii.1960, F. Schmid,
CNC311869.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes atisubhaga*
1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18932
Setodes atisubhaga.

atisudhara* Schmid 1987, *Trichosetodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Tipaimukh 6-7-IX-
1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311890.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Tipaimukh,
24°14'5"N 93°1'13"E, 6-7.ix.1960, F. Schmid,
CNC311890.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Trichosetodes*
atisudhara 1984 F. Schmid / LECTOTYPE
CNCNo. 18950 Tr. *atisudhara*.

Comments: The additional Lectotype label associated with the holotype is misleading, as no lectotype has been designated, nor is it necessary, with the holotype explicitly listed in the original description.

atisukchma* Schmid 1987, *Trichosetodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madhya Pr.) Satanwara [sic] 28-
XI-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311891.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Madhya Pradesh**: Sa-
tanwada, 25°44'51.21"N 77°24'29.44"E, 28.xi.
1961, F. Schmid, CNC311891.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Trichosetodes atisuk-*
chma 1984 F. Schmid / LECTOTYPE CNC
No. 18951 Tr. *atisukchma*.

Comments: Description incorrectly listed year of

collection as 1960. The additional Lectotype label associated with the holotype is misleading, as no lectotype has been designated, nor is it necessary, with the holotype explicitly listed in the original description.

atisukha* Schmid 1987, *Trichosetodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and
Khasi Hills] Thangrain 22-IV-1960 F.Schmid /
CNC 311893.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: Jaintia
Hills District, Thangrain, 25°34'48"N 92°26'
22"E, 22.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311893.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Trichosetodes atiharin*
[*lapsus*] 1984 F. Schmid / LECTOTYPE CNC
No. 18958 Tr. *atisukha* Holotype / *Trichose-*
todes atisukha Schmid, Det. O. Lonsdale.

Comments: The holotype labels for *T. atisukha*
and *T. atiharin* appear to have been placed on
the incorrect specimens by Schmid, as sug-
gested by agreement between collection data
in the descriptions and labels. The additional
Lectotype label associated with the holotype is
misleading, as no lectotype has been desig-
nated, nor is it necessary, with the holotype
explicitly listed in the original description.

atitejas* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Lushai) [=Mizo Hills] Sonai 15-
IX-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311772.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Mizoram**: Sonai, 15.
ix.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311772.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes atitejas* 1985
F. Schmid HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18857 *Se-*
todes atitejas.

atymanjula* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Perumalmalai 9-XII-
1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311878.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu**: Perumal
Malai, 10°15'57"N 77°32'42"E, 9.xii.1961, F.
Schmid, CNC311878.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes atymanjula*
1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18941
Setodes atymanjula.

atyudatta Schmid 1987, *Leptocerus*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Vangai Chungpao 21-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311734.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Vangai Chungpao, 24°45'23"N 93°10'40"E, 21.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311734.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptocerus atyudatta* 1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18992 *Leptocerus atyudatta*.

atyuktata Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Teri Garhwal Jakhanr 24-IV-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 311856.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Tehri Garhwal District, Jakhanr, 24.iv.1958, F. Schmid, CNC311856.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes atyuktata* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18920 *Setodes atyuktata*.

bagha Schmid 1968 a, *Poecilopsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Amatulla 17-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311672.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Amatulla, 26°55'47"N 92°7'18"E, 17.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 311672.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Poecilopsyche bagha* 1967 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11397 *Poec. bagha*.

bahuchaka Schmid 1987, *Leptocerus*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Khopum [sic] 27-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311703.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Khoupum, 24°39'16"N 93°26'52"E, 27.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311703.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptocerus bahuchaka* 1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18973 *Leptocerus bahuchaka*.

balcanica Botoșăneanu & Novák 1965, *Adicella*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Macédoine Capari 11-VIII-1955 F.Schmid / CNC 311545.

Interpretive data: **MACEDONIA**. Capari, 41°3'25"N 21°10'40"E, 11.viii.1955, F. Schmid, CNC 311545.

Determination: *Adicella balanica* Bots. & Nov. / Holotype ♂ / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12181 *Adicella balanica*.

bhairava Schmid 1995a, *Oecetis*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Komadi 18-19-I-1962 F.Schmid / CNC 311738.

Interpretive data: **INDIA**. Madras [likely in either present day Kerala or Tamil Nadu State], Komadi, 18-19.i.1962, F. Schmid, CNC 311738.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis bhairava* 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Oecetis bhairava* S. CNC No. 22075.

bhavabhuti Schmid 1995a, *Oecetis*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Tangkhul Hungdung 18-VIII-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311746.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Tangkhul Hungdung, 25°4'29.28"N 94°13'51.96"E, 18.viii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311746.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis bhavabhuti* 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Oecetis bhavabhuti* S. CNC No. 22083.

bhimachringa Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype[?] (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Bombay) Patan 3-II-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311816.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Gujarat**: Patan, 23°50'58"N 72°7'35"E, 3.ii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311816.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes bhimachringa* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18884 *Setodes bhimachringa*.

Comments: Data for the holotype in the description is "Mysore, Nagodi 28-I-1959", which is found on two males labeled as paratypes in the CNC; one of these, like the specimen labeled as the holotype, is dissected. Patan is not mentioned in the description, although it may be alluded to by reference of additional unlisted material examined from Bombay. Closer scru-

tiny of these specimens is required before type designation for this species is considered definitive.

bhimasena Schmid 1968a, *Poecilopsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Dethang [sic] 1-IV-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 311673.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Deythang, 27°
12'19"N 88°13'33.66"E, 1.iv.1959, F. Schmid,
CNC311673.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Poecilopsyche bhimasena* 1967 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11385 *Poec. bhimasena*.

capreolanus Schmid 1987, *Sericodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Guinée franç. Souapiti 15-20-V-1955
F.Schmid / CNC 311889.

Interpretive data: **GUINEA**. Souapiti, 10°25'
26.76"N 13°15'16.20"W, 15-20.v.1955, F.
Schmid, CNC311889.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Sericodes capreolanus*
1985 F. Schmid.

chaktika Schmid 1987, *Leptocerus*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.D.M.N.C.H.) [=United district
of Mikir Hills and North Cachar] Umbaso 26-
IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311719.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Assam**: Karbi Anglong
District, Umbaso, 25°43'48"N 92°31'34"E, 26.
iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311719.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptocerus chaktika*
1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18985
Leptocerus chaktika.

Comments: Description incorrectly listed date of
collection as the 22nd.

chandrakita Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Rahung 17-VII-1961
F.Schmid / CNC 311868.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
West Kameng District, Rahung, 27°18'37"N
92°23'41"E, 17.vii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC
311868.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes chandrakita*

1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18935
Setodes chandrakita.

chandravarana Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.D.M.N.C.H.) [=United district
of Mikir Hills and North Cachar] Inchaikang
6-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311823.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Assam**: Dima Hasao
District, Inchaikang, 25°7'42"N 92°59'
53.01"E, 6.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311823.

Determination: holotype *Setodes chandravarana*
1985 ♀ [sic] F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC
No. 18887 *Setodes chandravarana*.

chatadalaja Schmid 1987, *Leptocerus*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Bombay) Nandipur 1-II-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 311690.

Interpretive data: **INDIA**. Locality possibly refers
to Nandipur in present-day Maharashtra State
(19°58'29.14"N 77°37'19.60"E), 1.ii.1959, F.
Schmid, CNC311690.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptocerus chatada-
laja* 1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
18963 *Leptocerus chatadalaja*.

chloe Schmid 1994c, *Adicella*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Kujjalong 28-30-VI-
1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311574.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
Kameng Frontier Division [now divided into
the districts of Tawang, East Kameng and
West Kameng], Kujjalong, 28-30.vi.1961, F.
Schmid, CNC311574.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella chloe* 1993 F.
Schmid / *Adicella chloe* Schm. CNC [type no.]
21735 Holotype ♂.

chubhamyu Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Kerala) Ponmudi 12-I-1962
F.Schmid / CNC 311843.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala**: Ponmudi,
8°45'35"N 77°6'55"E, 12.i.1962, F. Schmid,
CNC311843.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes chubhamyu*
1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18908
Setodes chubhamyu.

chyamavadata Schmid 1987, Leptocerus

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Musianglamare 9-I-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311721.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia Hills District, Musianglamare, 9.i.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311721.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptocerus chyamavadata* 1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 18987 *Leptocerus chyamavadata*.

Comments: Description listed locality as "Musangliamare".

clelia Schmid 1994c, Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Fort Hamilton 12-XII-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 311560.

Interpretive data: **INDIA.** Madras [likely in either present day Kerala or Tamil Nadu State], Fort Hamilton, 12.xii.1958, F. Schmid, CNC 311560.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella clelia* 1993 F. Schmid / *Adicella clelia* Schm. CNC [type no.] 21719 Holotype ♂.

clio Schmid 1994c, Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Yodpai 16-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311553.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka:** Yodpai, 16.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311553.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella clio* 1993 F. Schmid / *Adicella clio* Schmid CNC [type no.] 21714 Holotype ♂.

clotho Schmid 1994c, Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (madras) Perumalmai 7-XII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311564.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu:** Perumal Malai, 10°15'57"N 77°32'42"E, 7.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311564.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella clotho* 1993 F. Schmid / *Adicella clotho* Schm CNC [type no.] 21723 Holotype ♂.

core Schmid 1994c, Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Tipaimukh 6-7-IX-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311573.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Tipaimukh, 24°14'5"N 93°1'13"E, 6-7.ix.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311573.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella core* 1993 F. Schmid / *Adicella core* Schm. CNC [type no.] 21734 Holotype ♂.

dakchineswara Schmid 1995c, Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Someshwar 27-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311613.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka:** Someshwar, 13°29'33"N 75°3'51"E, 27.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311613.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis pradyumna* [*lapsus*] 1995 F. Schmid / Holotype *Oecetis dakchineswara* Sch. Det. O. Lonsdale / HOLOTYPE *Oecetis dakchineswara* CNC No. 22141.

Comments: The incorrect type label was placed on the holotype, as suggested by the data on the label and in the description, and perhaps represents a manuscript name.

damchtragada Schmid 1987, Trichosetodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Subrahmanya 20-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311900.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka:** Subrahmanya, 12°40'9"N 75°36'38.01"E, 20.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311900.

Determination: holotype *Trichosetodes damchtragada* 1984 F. Schmid / LECTOTYPE CNC No. 18959 Tr. *damchtragada*.

Comments: The additional Lectotype label associated with the holotype is misleading, as no lectotype has been designated, nor is it necessary, with the holotype explicitly listed in the original description.

danae Schmid 1994c, Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Kattalaimala 25-26-XII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311551.

Interpretive data: **INDIA.** Madras [likely in either present day Kerala or Tamil Nadu State],

- Kattalaimala, 25-26.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311551.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella danae* 1993 F. Schmid / *Adicella danae* Schm CNC [type no.] 21712 Holotype ♂.
- dantavarna Schmid 1987, *Setodes***
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Someshwar 27-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311778.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka**: Someshwar, 13°29'33"N 75°3'51"E, 27.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311778.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes dantavarna* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18860 *Setodes dantavarna*.
- daphne Schmid 1994, *Adicella***
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (U.D.M.N.C.H.) [=United district of Mikir Hills and North Cachar] Umbaso 26-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311563.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Assam**: Karbi Anglong District, Umbaso, 25°43'48"N 92°31'34"E, 26. iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311563.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella daphne* 1993 F. Schmid / *Adicella daphne* Sch. CNC [type no.] 21724 Holotype ♂.
- datrayukta Schmid 1987, *Leptocerus***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Inde (C.) Jirighat 17,19-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311722.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Assam**: Cachar District, Jirighat, 24°48'30"N 93°6'23"E, 17-19.v. 1960, F. Schmid, CNC311722.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptocerus datrayukta* 1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18988 *Leptocerus datrayukta*.
- devakiputra Schmid 1995b, *Oecetis***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Inde (Madhya Pr.) Satanwara [sic] 28-XI-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311602.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Madhya Pradesh**: Satanwada, 25°44'51.21"N 77°24'29.44"E, 28. xi.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311602.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis devakiputra* 1995 F. Schmid / *Oecetis devakiputra* CNC No. 22092 HOLOTYPE.
Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.
- dhanavridha Schmid 1987, *Setodes***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Sikkim Ligship [sic] 28-IV-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311802.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Legship, 27°16'46"N 88°16'29"E, 28.iv.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311802.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes dhanavridha* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18877 *Setodes dhanavridha*.
- dhanika Schmid 1987, *Setodes***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Teri Garhwal Ampata 8-10-IV-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 311773.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Tehri Garhwal District, Ampata, 30°16'6"N 78°22' 18"E, 8-10.iv.1958, F. Schmid, CNC311773.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes dhanika* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18858 *Setodes dhanika*.
- dharasena Schmid 1961, *Adicella***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Cachem.et Jam. Nansoc 27-IX-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 311549.
Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu & Kashmir**: Nansoc, 27.ix.1953, F. Schmid, CNC311549.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella dharasena* 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12361 *Adicella dharasena*.
Comments: Locality appears to be equivalent to Sarfa Rangah (35°20'45"N 75°40'9"E).
- dhristadyumna Schmid 1968a, *Poecilopsyche***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Khamassom 24-VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311674.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Khamassom, 24.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311674.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Poecilopsyche dhristadyumna* 1967 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11387 *Poec. dhristadyumna*.

dhritarashtra Schmid 1968a, *Poecilopsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Khasi and Jaintia Hills] Syndai 26-XII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311675.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia Hills District, Syndai, 25°11'8.01"N 92°8'25"E, 26.xii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311675.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Poecilopsyche dhritarashtra* [sic] 1967 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11388 *Poec. dhritarashtra*.

dhruvasena Schmid 1961, *Adicella*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pakistan (Penjab) Hassan Abdal 27-XII-1954 F.Schmid / CNC 311548.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Punjab:** Hassan Abdal, 33°49'10"N 72°41'21"E, 27.xii.1954, F. Schmid, CNC311548.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella dhruvasena* 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12360 *Adicella dhruvasena*.

dicte Schmid 1994c, *Adicella*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Umpuh 6-I-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311568.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** United Jaintia and Khasi Hills [now divided into East and West Khasi Hills Districts and East and West Jaintia Hills Districts], Umpuh, 6.i.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311568.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella dicte* 1993 F. Schmid / *Adicella dicte* Schm CNC [type no.] 21727 Holotype ♂.

dirce Schmid 1994c, *Adicella*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Kechoiperi 9-IV-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311588.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Kechoiperi, 9.iv.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311588.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella dirce* 1993 F. Schmid / *Adicella dirce* Schm CNC [type no.] 21730 Holotype ♂.

dirghachuka Gordon & Schmid 1987 [In: Schmid (1987)], *Leptocerus*

holotype+allotype (2 male/female, ethyl alcohol)

Verbatim: THAILAND: chw. Makhon Ratchasima amp. Pakthongchai, Sakaerat Field Station, Mamkhieo Stream October 27, 1975 Gordon and Jullalerk, light trap / CNC 165690.

Interpretive data: **THAILAND. Nakhon Ratchasima:** amp. Pakthongchai, Sakaerat Field Station, Mamkhieo Stream, 14°30'32"N 101°57'15"E, 27.x.1975, Gordon & Jullalerk, light trap, CNC165690.

Determination: *Leptocerus dirghachuka*, n. sp. Gordon and Schmid, HOLOTYPE: MALE; ALLOTYPE: FEMALE / *Setodes argenti-guttatus* Gordon and Schmid, holotype ♂, Allotype ♀.

Comments: Original publication notes depository as TISTR, Thailand.

divyarupa Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Shergaon 9-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311806.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Shergaon, 27°6'18"N 92°16'20"E, 9.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 311806.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes divyarupa* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18880 *Setodes divyarupa*.

draupadi Schmid 1968a, *Poecilopsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (W.B.) Git Dabling [sic] 13-IX-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311676.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. West Bengal:** Git Dabling, 27°3'13"N 88°35'51"E, 13.ix.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311676.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Poecilopsyche draupadi* 1967 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11389 *Poec. draupadi*.

dryas Schmid 1994c, *Adicella*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.D.M.N.C.H.) [=United District of Mikir Hills and North Cachar] Nongjiron 25-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311558.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Assam:** Karbi Anglong District, Nongjiron, 25°28'16.66"N 92°4'

48.09"E, 25.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311558.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella dryas* 1993 F. Schmid / *Adicella dryas* Schm. CNC [type no.] 21717 Holotype ♂.

dryope* Schmid 1994c, *Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Khopum [sic] 27-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311584.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Khoupum, 24°39'16"N 93°26'52"E, 27.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311584.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella dryope* 1993 F. Schmid / holotype ♂ *Adicella dryope* Sch. CNC [type no.] 21752.

duhchasana* Schmid 1968a, *Poecilopsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Datum 3-VIII-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311678.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Datum, 3. viii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311678.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Poecilopsyche duhchasana* 1967 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11393 *Poec. duhchasana*.

durhyodhana* Schmid 1968a, *Poecilopsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Tairenpokpi 31-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311677.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Tairenpokpi, 24°49'30"N 93°48'11.01"E, 31.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311677.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Poecilopsyche durhyodhana* 1967 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11398 *Poec. durhyodhana*.

eburnea* Schmid 1961, *Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Pakistan (Penjab) Hassan Abdal 27-XII-1954 F.Schmid / CNC 311736.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Punjab**: Hassan Abdal, 33°49'10"N 72°41'21"E, 27.xii.1954, F. Schmid, CNC311736.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis eburnea* 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12363 *Oecetis eburnea*.

ekachringa* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka**: Mysore, Sangapalipam, [date unknown], F. Schmid, CNC481646.

Determination: Holotype CNC No. , *Setodes* 1-chringa, Vide altera pars.

Comments: Holotype lost, represented by a pin with a label, an empty minuten and a genitalia slide only bearing a question mark. The published collection date is 29.ii.1962 [date does not exist], and Schmid's field notes for India end at 6.ii.1962 when his travels were presumably completed. The locality cannot be found among his field notes for Mysore. A unique identifier has been added to the unit tray for eventual addition to specimen if located. The species may have been appropriately named by Schmid for an imaginary animal.

ekapita* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Inde (Kerala) Silent Valley 29-I-1962 F.Schmid / CNC 311768.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala**: Silent Valley, 10°5'11.73"N 77°3'46.49"E, 29.i.1962, F. Schmid, CNC311768.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes ekapita* 1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18853 *Setodes ekapita*.

eloa* Schmid 1994c, *Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Sikkim Yugang 24-VII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311562.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Yugang, 24. vii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311562.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella eloa* 1993 F. Schmid / *Adicella eloa* Schmid CNC [type no.] 21721 Holotype ♂.

enone* Schmid 1994c, *Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Sikkim Manu 5-6-VIII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311566.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Manu, 27°31' 2"N 88°34'58"E, 5-6.viii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311566.

Determination: holotype ♂ Adicella enone 1993
F. Schmid / Adicella enone Schmid CNC [type
no.] 21725 Holotype ♂.

erato Schmid 1994c, Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Chingsao 13-VI-1960
F.Schmid / CNC 311578.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Chingsao,
13.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311578.

Determination: holotype ♂ Adicella erato 1993 F.
Schmid / Adicella erato Sch. CNC [type no.]
21739 Holotype ♂.

eryx Schmid 1994c, Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Dirang Dzong 21-22-
VII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311561.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
West Kameng District, Derangzong, 27°20'
31"N 92°16'22"E, 21-22.vii.1961, F. Schmid,
CNC311561.

Determination: holotype ♂ Adicella eryx 1993 F.
Schmid / Adicella eryx Schmid CNC [type
no.] 21720 Holotype ♂.

eunoia Schmid 1994c, Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Chingsao 13-VI-1960
F.Schmid / CNC 311585.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Chingsao,
13.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311585.

Determination: holotype ♂ Adicella eunoia 1993
F. Schmid / holotype ♂ Adicella eunoia Sch.
CNC [type no.] 21751.

euphrosyne Schmid 1994b, Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Tung 2-VIII-1959 F.Schmid /
CNC 311594.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Tung, 27°32'
37"N 88°38'54"E, 2.viii.1959, F. Schmid,
CNC311594.

Determination: holotype ♂ Adicella euphrosyne
1993 F. Schmid / Adicella euphrosyne Sch
Holotype ♂ CNC [type no.] 217967.

euryale Schmid 1994b, Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and
Khasi Hills] Rumkheng 24-III-1960 F.Schmid
/ CNC 311591.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: United
Jaintia and Khasi Hills [now divided into East
and West Khasi Hills Districts and East and
West Jaintia Hills Districts], Rumkheng,
24.iii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311591.

Determination: holotype ♂ Adicella euryale 1993
F. Schmid / Adicella euryale Sch Holotype
♂ CNC [type no.] 21795.

eurynoe Schmid 1994c, Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Mollen 20-VIII-1960
F.Schmid / CNC 311583.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Mollen,
24°31'54"N 93°31'44"E, 20.viii.1960, F.
Schmid, CNC311583.

Determination: holotype ♂ Adicella eurynoe 1993
F. Schmid / Holotype ♂ Adicella eurynoe Sch
CNC [type no.] 21753.

eurynome Schmid 1994b, Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and
Khasi Hills] Shilliang Myntang 21-IV-1960
F.Schmid / CNC 311590.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: Jaintia
Hills District, Shilliangmyntang, 25°33'55"N
92°21'27"E, 21.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC
311590.

Determination: holotype ♂ Adicella eurynome
1993 F. Schmid / Adicella eurynome Sch
Holotype ♂ CNC [type no.] 21793.

euryppyle Schmid 1994b, Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Bongba [sic] Khunou
27-VII-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311592.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Bungpa
Khunou, 24°48'41"N 94°28'27"E, 27.vii.1960,
F. Schmid, CNC311592.

Determination: holotype ♂ Adicella euryppyle
1993 F. Schmid / Adicella euryppyle Sch Holo-
type ♂ CNC [type no.] 21794.

eurysthene Schmid 1994b, Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Shergaon 8-V-1961
F.Schmid / CNC 311593.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
West Kameng District, Shergaon, 8.v.1961, F.
Schmid, CNC311593.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella eurysthene*
1993 F. Schmid / *Adicella eurysthene* Sch
CNC [type no.] 21796 holotype ♂.

Comments: Description incorrectly listed month
of collection as June.

eurythemiste* Schmid 1994c, *Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Phaiphengmun 30-VIII-
1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311580.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Phaipheng,
24°20'27"N 93°27'28"E, 30.viii.1960, F.
Schmid, CNC311580.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella eurythemiste*
1993 F. Schmid / Holotype ♂ *Adicella eury-*
themiste Sch. CNC [type no.] 21754.

evadne* Schmid 1994c, *Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and
Khasi Hills] Shilliang Myntang 21-IV-1960
F.Schmid / CNC 311567.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: Jaintia
Hills District, Shilliangmyntang, 25°33'55"N
92°21'27"E, 21.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC
311567.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella evadne* 1993
F. Schmid / *Adicella evadne* Schm CNC [type
no.] 21726 Holotype ♂.

evohe* Schmid 1994c, *Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Lathong 26-VII-1958 F.Schmid
/ CNC 311571.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Latong, 26.
vii.1958, F. Schmid, CNC311571.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella evohe* 1993
F. Schmid / *Adicella evohe* Sch. CNC [type
no.] 21738 Holotype ♂.

Comments: At least part of the collection data are
incorrect, as Schmid was in Uttarakhand at the
date stated; Schmid was in Latong on 15.
v.1959.

eximius* Schmid 1994a, *Triadenodes

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Nagodi 28-I-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 311533.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka**: Nagodi,
13°55'47"N 74°54'10"E, 28.i.1959, F. Schmid,
CNC311533.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Triadenodes eximius*
1993 F. Schmid / Holotype ♂ *Triadenodes exi-*
mius Sch. CNC [type no.] 21769.

fantasio* Schmid 1994a, *Triadenodes

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal, Lingari 1-IX-1958
F.Schmid / CNC 311537.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Pauri
Garhwal District, Lingari, 1.ix.1958, F. Schmid,
CNC311537.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Triadenodes fantasio*
1993 F. Schmid / Holotype ♂ *Triadenodes fan-*
tasio Schm CNC [type no.] 21771.

fortunio* Schmid 1994a, *Triadenodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and
Khasi Hills] Mawlang 12-IV-1960 F.Schmid /
CNC 311536.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: East Khasi
Hills District, Mawlang, 25°39'44"N 91°50'
30"E, 12.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311536.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Triadenodes fortunio*
1993 F. Schmid / Holotype ♂ *Triadenodes*
fortunio Schm CNC [type no.] 21770.

***gangaja* Gordon & Schmid 1987 [In: Schmid
(1987)], *Setodes***

holotype+allotype (2 male/female, ethyl alcohol)

Verbatim: THAILAND: Chw. Loei, amp. Muang
Loei River, June 27, 1976 A.E. Gordon, light
trap / CNC 165692.

Interpretive data: **THAILAND. Loei**: amp. Mu-
ang, Loei River, 17°31'47"N 101°43'33"E, 27.
vi.1976, A.E. Gordon, light trap, CNC165692.

Determination: *Setodes gangaja* Gordon and
Schmid holotype ♂; Allotype ♀ *Setodes*
gangaja, n. sp. Gordon and Schmid HOLO-
TYPE: MALE; ALLOTYPE: FEMALE.

Comments: Original publication notes depository
as TISTR, Thailand.

gaurichachringa Schmid 1987, Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Kerala) Kolattupuzha 22-XII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311880.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala:** Kulathupuzha, 8°54'32.48"N 77°3'33.56"E, 22.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311880.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes gaurichachringa* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 189483 [*lapsus* for 18943] *Setodes gaurichachringa*.

gherni Schmid 1987, Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Nyukmadong 5-8-VIII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311805.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Nyukmadung, 27°25'1"N 92°7'57"E, 5-8.viii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311805.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes gherni* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18879 *Setodes gherni*.

goraknata Schmid 1995c, Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Khopum [sic] 27-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311610.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Khoupum, 24°39'16"N 93°26'52"E, 27.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311610.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis goraknata* 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Oecetis Sch. goraknata* CNC No. 22139.

gunapatya Schmid 1995c, Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Mattiyang 17-VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311633.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Mattiyang, 17.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311633.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis gunapatya* 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Oecetis gunapatya* CNC No. 22151.

Comments: Description incorrectly listed month of collection as April.

gutika Schmid 1987, Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Dirang Dzong 20-VII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311867.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Derangzong, 27°20'31"N 92°16'22"E, 20.vii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311867.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes gutika* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18930 *Setodes gutika*.

gutivridha Schmid 1987, Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Sirohi Kashong 11-13-VII-1960 F. Schmid / CNC 311866.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Sirohi Kashong, 25°6'23.19"N 94°27'28.51"E, 11-13.vii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311866.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes gutivridha* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18931 *Setodes gutivridha*.

harivamsa Schmid 1995b, Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Bombay) Nandipur 1-II-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311604.

Interpretive data: **INDIA.** Locality possibly refers to Nandipur in present-day Maharashtra State (19°58'29.14"N 77°37'19.60"E), 1.ii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311604.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis hariwansa* 1995 F. Schmid / *Oecetis hariwansa* CNC No. 22091 HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Description incorrectly listed date of collection as the 11th.

hayagriva Schmid 1995c, Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Bombay) Nandipur 1-II-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311624.

Interpretive data: **INDIA.** Locality possibly refers to Nandipur in present-day Maharashtra State (19°58'29.14"N 77°37'19.60"E), 1.ii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311624.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis hayagriva* 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Oecetis hayagriva* CNC No. 22145.

hebe Schmid 1994c, Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Khasi and Jaintia Hills] Syndai 15-XII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311569.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: Jaintia Hills District, Syndai, 25°11'8.01"N 92°8'25"E, 15.xii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311569.

Determination: holotype ♂ Adicella hebe 1993 F. Schmid / Adicella hebe Schm. CNC [type no.] 21728 Holotype ♂.

himaruna Schmid 1987, Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Subrahmanya 20-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311830.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka**: Subrahmanya, 12°40'9"N 75°36'38.01"E, 20.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311830.

Determination: holotype ♂ Setodes himaruna 1986 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18895 Setodes himaruna.

hiranyakachipu Schmid 1995c, Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Tairenpokpi 31-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311643.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Tairenpokpi, 24°49'30"N 93°48'11.01"E, 31.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311643.

Determination: holotype ♂ Oecetis hiranyakachipu 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE Oecetis hiranyakachipu CNC No. 22157.

Comments: Locality listed as "Tairenpokpi" in description.

hiranyaksa Schmid 1995a, Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Sikkim Nampung 8-V-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311747.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Nampung, 8.v.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311747.

Determination: holotype ♂ Oecetis hiranyaksa 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE Oecetis hiranyaksa [sic] S. CNC No. 22081.

Comments: Description incorrectly listed month of collection as October.

ichtadevata Schmid 1995c, Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Sirohi Kashong 8-VI-

1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311630.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Sirohi Kashong, 25°6'23.19"N 94°27'28.51"E, 8.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311630.

Determination: holotype ♂ Oecetis ichtadevata 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE Oecetis ichtadevata CNC No. 22149.

ichtadvaraka Schmid 1995c, Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Mawpyut 14-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311629.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: Jaintia Hills District, Mawpyut, 25°25'0"N 92°10'0"E, 14.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311629.

Determination: holotype ♂ Oecetis ichtadvaraka 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE Oecetis ichtadvaraka CNC No. 22148.

ichtasurama Schmid 1995c, Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Yodpai 16-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311640.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka**: Yodpai, 16.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311640.

Determination: holotype ♂ Oecetis ichtasurama 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE Oecetis ichtasurama CNC No. 22150.

ichvara Schmid 1995a, Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Khopum [sic] 27-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311741.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Khopum, 24°39'16"N 93°26'52"E, 27.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311741.

Determination: holotype ♂ Oecetis ichvara 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE Oecetis ichvara [sic] S. CNC No. 22078.

viridis iranensis Botoșăneanu & Gasith 1971, Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Iran (Ost.9) Garma Khan 7-VII-1956 F.Schmid / CNC 311808.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. North Khorasan**: Garma Khan, 37°31'33"N 57°28'25"E, 7.vii.1956, F. Schmid, CNC311808.

Determination: holotype ♂ Lecto. *S. viridis iranensis* F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18882 *Setodes viridis iranensis*.

jatisampanna* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Kerala) Silent Valley 14-XII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311876.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala**: Silent Valley, 10°5'11.73"N 77°3'46.49"E, 14.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311876.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes jatisampanna* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18939 *Setodes jatisampanna*.

jayadeva* Schmid 1995a, *Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Bilo La 9-VI-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311745.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: Kameng Frontier Division [now divided into the districts of Tawang, East Kameng and West Kameng], Bilo La, 9.vi.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311745.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis jayadeva* 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Oecetis jayadeva* S. CNC No. 22082.

kadrava* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Luanglong Khunou 28-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311779.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Luanglong Khunou, 28.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311779.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes kadrava* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18861 *Setodes kadrava*.

kalidasa* Schmid 1995c, *Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam Dhekiajuli 28-II-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311644.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Assam**: Dhekiajuli, 26°41'55"N 92°29'7"E, 28.ii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311644.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis kalidasa* 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Oecetis kalidasa* CNC No. 22158.

kalyana* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Hariarapur 25-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311840.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka**: Hariharapura, 13°31'18"N 75°17'59.90"E, 25.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311840.

Determination: HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18904 *Setodes kalyana*.

Comments: One wing slide-mounted on pin.

kalyuga* Schmid 1995b, *Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Langdang 5-VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311600.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Langdang, 25°7'25"N 94°24'16"E, 5.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311600.

Determination: *Oecetis kalyuga* s. CNC No. 22093 HOLOTYPE / holotype ♂ *Oecetis kalyuga* 1995 F. Schmid.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

kantiamrita* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Demthring 16-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311837.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: East Khasi Hills District, Demthring, 25°33'28"N 91°54'35"E, 16.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311837.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes kantiamrita* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18902 *Setodes kantiamrita* [sic].

kapchajalaja* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Kerala) Urti 15-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311884.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu**: Urti, 15.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311884.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes kapchajalaja* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18947 *Setodes kapchajalaja*.

karapatradhara* Schmid 1987, *Trichosetodes

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Someshwar 27-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311901.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka:** Someshwar, 13°29'33"N 75°3'51"E, 27.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311901.

Determination: holotype ♂ Trichosetodes karapatradhara 1984 F. Schmid / LECTOTYPE CNCNo. 18960 Tr. karapatradhara.

Comments: The additional Lectotype label associated with the holotype is misleading, as no lectotype has been designated, nor is it necessary, with the holotype explicitly listed in the original description.

kartavirya Schmid 1995c, Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Kerala) Kalpatti 13-I-1962 F.Schmid / CNC 311646.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala:** Kalpatti, 13.i.1962, F. Schmid, CNC311646.

Determination: holotype ♂ Oecetis kartavirya 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE Oecetis kartavirya CNC No. 22160.

karttikeya Schmid 1995c, Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Nongjngi 19-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311622.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** West Jaintia Hills District, Nongjngi, 25°32'32"N 92°16'20"E, 19.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 311622.

Determination: holotype ♂ Oecetis karttikeya 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE Oecetis karttikeya CNC No. 22142.

kchapavarna Schmid 1987, Leptocerus

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Haveri 2-XII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311692.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka:** Haveri, 14°47'47"N 75°23'49"E, 2.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311692.

Determination: holotype ♂ Leptocerus kchapavarna 1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18965 Leptocerus kchapavarna.

khechara Schmid 1987, Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Phaiphengmun 29-VIII-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311811.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Phaipheng, 24°20'27"N 93°27'28"E, 29.viii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311811.

Determination: holotype ♂ Setodes khechara 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18874 Setodes khechara.

kulasekhara Schmid 1995c, Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (C.) Lakhipur 14, 16-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311634.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Assam:** Cachar District, Lakhipur, 24°47'35.01"N 93°0'16"E, 14-16.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311634.

Determination: holotype ♂ Oecetis kulasekhara 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE Oecetis kulasekhara CNC No. 22152.

kumara Schmid 1987, Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Lushai) [=Mizo Hills] Sairang 21-IX-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311865.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Mizoram:** Aizawl District, Sairang, 23°48'35"N 92°39'23"E, 21.ix.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311865.

Determination: holotype ♂ Setodes kumara 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18929 Setodes kumara.

kurukchetra Schmid 1995c, Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Demthring 16-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311635.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** East Khasi Hills District, Demthring, 25°33'28"N 91°54'35"E, 16.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 311635.

Determination: holotype ♂ Oecetis kurukchetra 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE Oecetis kurukchetra CNC No. 22153.

lais Schmid 1994c, Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Chapai 26-II-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311565.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** Kameng Frontier Division [now divided into the districts of Tawang, East Kameng and West Kameng], Chapai, 26.ii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311565.

Determination: holotype ♂ Adicella lais 1993 F. Schmid / Adicella lais Schmid CNC [type no.] 21722 Holotype ♂.

***lampito* Schmid 1994c, Adicella**

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Nafra 26-VI-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311582.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Nafra, 27°22'20"N 92°32'45"E, 26.vi.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 311582.

Determination: holotype ♂ Adicella lampito 1993 F. Schmid / Adicella lampito Sch. CNC [type no.] 21743 Holotype ♂.

***leda* Schmid 1994c, Adicella**

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Rumkheng 20-23-III-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311570.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** United Jaintia and Khasi Hills [now divided into East and West Khasi Hills Districts and East and West Jaintia Hills Districts], Rumkheng, 20-23.iii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311570.

Determination: holotype ♂ Adicella leda 1993 F. Schmid / Adicella leda Sch. CNC [type no.] 21732 Holotype ♂.

***leto* Schmid 1994c, Adicella**

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Tipaimukh 6-7-IX-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311572.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Tipaimukh, 24°14'5"N 93°1'13"E, 6-7.ix.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311572.

Determination: holotype ♂ Adicella leto 1993 F. Schmid / Adicella leto Sch. CNC [type no.] 21733 Holotype ♂.

Comments: Collection dates listed as 5-7 in description.

***lokapala* Schmid 1995b, Oecetis**

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Kaiphundai 20-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311601.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Kaiphundai, 24°47'51"N 93°14'1"E, 20.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311601.

Determination: holotype ♂ Oecetis lokapala 1995 F. Schmid / Oecetis lokapala s. CNC No. 22090.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

***madhuvarna* Schmid 1987, Setodes**

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Kerala) Sangalipalam 20-21-XII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311782.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala:** Sangalipalam, 20-21.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311782.

Determination: holotype ♀ [sic] Setodes madhuvarna 1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18865 Setodes madhuvarna.

***madhyamika* (Schmid 1961), Leptocerus [Setodes]**

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Frontier Province] Balakot 16-X-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 311725.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa:** Balakot, 34°32'22"N 73°21'2.01"E, 16.x.1953, F. Schmid, CNC311725.

Determination: holotype ♂ Setodes madhyamika 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12359 Setodes madhyamika.

***mahabichu* Schmid 1987, Setodes**

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Kambiron 24-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311834.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Kambiron, 24°43'38"N 93°22'22"E, 24.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311834.

Determination: holotype ♂ Setodes mahabichu 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18899 Setodes mahabichu.

***mahadbhuta* Schmid 1987, Leptocerus**

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Lushai) [=Mizo Hills] Sonai 15-IX-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311733.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Mizoram**: Sonai, 15.ix.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311733.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptocerus mahadbhuta* 1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18991 *Leptocerus mahadbhuta*.

manichyana* Schmid 1987, *Leptocerus

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Luanglong Khunou 28-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311698.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Luanglong Khunou, 28.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311698.

Determination: HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18970 *Leptocerus manichyana* / holotype ♂ *Leptocerus manichyana* 1984 F. Schmid.

manimekhala* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.D.M.N.C.H.) [=United district of Mikir Hills and North Cachar] Haflong 5-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311836.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Assam**: Dima Hasao District, Haflong, 25°9'45"N 93°0'48"E, 5.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311836.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes manimekhala* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18900 *Setodes manimekhala*.

manivridha* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Lifakpo 15-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311807.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Liphakpu, 27°4'7"N 92°7'26"E, 15.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 311807.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes manivridha* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18881 *Setodes manivridha*.

mauktikavridha* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Serrarim 6-7-X-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311872.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: United

Jaintia and Khasi Hills [now divided into East and West Khasi Hills Districts and East and West Jaintia Hills Districts], Serrarim, 6-7.x.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311872.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes mauktivridha* [sic] 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18933 *Setodes mauktikavridha*.

mechakita* Schmid 1987, *Leptocerus

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Hat Nongshken 4-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311706.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: United Jaintia and Khasi Hills [now divided into East and West Khasi Hills Districts and East and West Jaintia Hills Districts], Hat Nongshken, 4.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311706.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptocerus mechakita* 1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18976 *Leptocerus mechakita*.

mechavrichana* Schmid 1987, *Leptocerus

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Kerala) Kolattupuzha 22-XII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311726.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala**: Kulathupuzha, 8°54'32.48"N 77°3'33.56"E, 22.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311726.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptocerus mechavrichana* [sic] 1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18989 *Leptocerus mechavrichana*.

meghavarna* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Kakankote 10-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311829.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka**: Kakankote, 11°54'0"N 76°12'0"E, 10.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311829.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes meghavarna* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18893 *Setodes meghavarna*.

monicae* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Yodpai 16-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311793.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka:** Yodpai, 16.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311793.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes monicae* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18873 *Setodes monicae*.

myrtho Schmid 1994c, Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Sikkim Nanga 3-4-VIII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311581.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Nanga, 3-4.viii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311581.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella myrtho* 1993 F. Schmid / *Adicella myrtho* Sch. CNC [type no.] 21741 Holotype ♂.

Comments: Locality possibly Naga-Namgor (27° 32'16"N 88°37'12"E).

nagarjouna Schmid 1961, Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Frontier Province] Balakot 23-VI-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 311818.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa:** Balakot, 34°32'22"N 73°21' 2.01"E, 23.vi.1953, F. Schmid, CNC311818.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes nagarjouna* 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12358 *Setodes nagarjouna*.

nakula Schmid 1968a, Poecilopsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Bhairabkunda 22-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311679.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** Udalguri District, Bhairabkunda, 26°53'2"N 92°6'51"E, 22.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 311679.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Poecilopsyche nakula* 1967 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11395 *Poec. nakula*.

narasimha Schmid 1995c, Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Nongjngi 19-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311626.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** West

Jaintia Hills District, Nongjngi, 25°32'32"N 92°16'20"E, 19.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 311626.

Determination: holotype *Oecetis narasimha* 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Oecetis narasimha* CNC No. 22146.

narendraya Schmid 1961, Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Cachem.et Jam. Shardi 1-13-VIII-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 311550.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu & Kashmir:** Shardi, 34°47'35.17"N 74°11' 10.77"E, 1-13.viii.1953, F. Schmid, CNC 311550.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella narendraya* 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12362 *Adicella narendraya*.

nasatya Schmid 1968a, Poecilopsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Shergaon 8-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311680.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Shergaon, 27°6'18"N 92°16'20"E, 8.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 311680.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Poecilopsyche nasatya* 1967 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11386 *Poec. nasatya*.

navanita Schmid 1987, Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Umsawmat 5-X-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311820.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** East Khasi Hills District, Umsawmat, 25°22'7"N 91°40'9"E, 5.x.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311820.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes navanita* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18886 *Setodes navanita*.

niobe Schmid 1994c, Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Ugsara 29-V-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 311586.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Pauri

- Garhwal District, Ugsara, 29.v.1958, F. Schmid, CNC311586.
Determination: holotype ♂ Adicella niobe 1993 F. Schmid / Adicella niobe Sch. CNC [type no.] 21729 Holotype ♂.
- nirmala Schmid 1987, *Setodes***
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Oinamlong 22-23-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311821.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Oinamlong, 24°46'33"N 93°17'3"E, 22-23.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311821.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes nirmala* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18888 *Setodes nirmala*.
- nyse Schmid 1994c, *Adicella***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Sikkim Rapham 2-IV-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311576.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Rapham, 2.iv.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311576.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella nyse* 1993 F. Schmid / *Adicella nyse* Sch. CNC [type no.] 21737 Holotype ♂.
- nyuna Schmid 1987, *Setodes***
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Uppinangadi 17-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311831.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka**: Uppinangady, 12°50'23"N 75°23'52"E, 17.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311831.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes nyuna* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18897 *Setodes nyuna*.
- pancharatra Schmid 1995c, *Oecetis***
Valid name: *Oecetis scutulata* Martynov 1936
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Inde (Madhya Pr.) Guna 7-II-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311614.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Madhya Pradesh**: Guna, 24°38'5"N 77°17'54"E, 7.ii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311614.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis pancharatra* 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Oecetis pancharatra* CNC No. 22143.
- pandara Schmid 1987, *Setodes***
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Maupata 2-IX-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 311771.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Pauri Garhwal District, Maupata, 2.ix.1958, F. Schmid, CNC311771.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes pandara* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18856 *Setodes pandara*.
- pandava Schmid 1968a, *Poecilopsyche***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Sikkim Dentam 4-IV-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311681.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Dentam, 27°15'17"N 88°8'12"E, 4.iv.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311681.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Poecilopsyche pandava* 1967 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11394 *Poec. pandava*.
- pandu Schmid 1968a, *Poecilopsyche***
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Nafra 26-VI-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311682.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Nafra, 27°22'20"N 92°32'45"E, 26.vi.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311682.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Poecilopsyche pandu* 1967 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11392 *Poec. pandu*.
- paribhuchita Schmid 1987, *Setodes***
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Nakhu 3-VII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311852.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Nakhu, 27°24'9"N 92°33'38.01"E, 3.vii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 311852.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes paribhuchita* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18916 *Setodes paribhuchita*.
- parichkrita Schmid 1987, *Setodes***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Ninghti 29-VII-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311791.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Ninghti, 24° 53'26.01"N 94°24'47.01"E, 29.vii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311791.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes parichkrita* 1986 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18870 *Setodes parichkrita*.

parilaghu* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Chingsao 13-VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311873.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Chingsao, 13.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311873.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes parilaghu* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18937 *Setodes parilaghu*.

parisamchuddha* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Chinnar 20-XII-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 311825.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala:** Chinnar, 10° 18'25"N 77°12'22"E, 20.xii.1958, F. Schmid, CNC311825.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes parisamchuddha* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 18891 *Setodes parisamchuddha*.

phoebe* Schmid 1994c, *Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Yongphu 11-VIII-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311579.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Yongphu, 11.viii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311579.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella phoebe* 1993 F. Schmid / *Adicella phoebe* Sch. CNC [type no.] 21740 Holotype ♂.

phryne* Schmid 1994c, *Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Shnongpdeng 6-XII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311552.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia Hills District, Shnongpdeng, 25°12'26"N 92°0' 35"E, 6.xii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311552.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Adicella phryne* 1993 F. Schmid / *Adicella phryne* Schmid CNC [type no.] 21713 Holotype ♂.

prabhatajalaja* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Kottagudi 23-I-1962 F.Schmid / CNC 311885.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu:** Kottagudi, 10°5'2"N 77°14'10"E, 23.i.1962, F. Schmid, CNC311885.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes prabhatajalaja* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18948 *Setodes prabhatajalaja*.

prahlada* Schmid 1995a, *Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Madhya Pr.) Satanwara [sic] 28-XI-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311739.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Madhya Pradesh:** Satanwada, 25°44'51.21"N 77°24'29.44"E, 28. xi.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311739.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis udayakara* 1995 F. Schmid / Holotype *Oecetis prahlada* Sch. Det. O. Lonsdale / HOLOTYPE *Oecetis prahlada* S. CNC No. 22076.

Comments: The holotype labels for *Oecetis prahlada* Sch. and *O. udayakara* were accidentally switched by Schmid, as suggested by collection data on the label and in the description. Description incorrectly listed month of collection as October.

pratachandradynti* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Sathuparai [sic] 22-I-1962 F.Schmid / CNC 311827.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu:** Sothuparai, 10°7'50.49"N 77°27'49.80"E, 22.i.1962, F. Schmid, CNC311827.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes pratachandradynti* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 18896 *Setodes pratachandradynti*.

pretakalpa* Schmid 1995c, *Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Oinamlong 22-23-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311615.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Oinamlong, 24°46'33"N 93°17'3"E, 22-23.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311615.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis pretakalpa* 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Oecetis pretakalpa* CNC No. 22144.

prithudhara Schmid 1987, *Leptocerus*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Thangrain 22-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311699.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia Hills District, Thangrain, 25°34'48"N 92°26'22"E, 22.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311699.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Lept. prithudhara* 1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18971 *Leptocerus prithudhara*.

priyadarcha Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Gaurikund 9-10-V-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 311803.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Rudraprayag District, Gaurikund, 30°39'10"N 79°1'33"E, 9-10.v.1958, F. Schmid, CNC311803.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes priyadarcha* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18876 *Setodes priyadarcha*.

Comments: Collection start date incorrectly listed as the 8th in description.

pryadyumna Schmid 1995a, *Oecetis*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Teri Garhwal Ampata 8-10-IV-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 311737.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Tehri Garhwal District, Ampata, 30°16'6"N 78°22'18"E, 8-10.iv.1958, F. Schmid, CNC311737.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis pryadyumna* 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Oecetis pryadyumna* S. CNC No. 22074.

Comments: One wing slide-mounted on pin.

puchkaraja Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Jarain 13-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311787.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia Hills District, Jarain, 25°22'50.01"N 92°8'58"E, 13.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311787.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes puchkaraja* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18868 *Setodes puchkaraja*.

purucha Schmid 1995c, *Oecetis*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Lagairong 26-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311611.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Lagairong, 24°42'0"N 93°32'0"E, 26.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311611.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis purucha* 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Oecetis purucha* Sch CNC No. 22140.

puruchringa Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Barato 24-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311790.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia Hills District, Barato, 25°36'21"N 92°27'5"E, 24.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311790.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes puruchringa* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18869 *Setodes puruchringa*.

purusamedha Schmid 1995b, *Oecetis*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Umlangshor 18-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311607.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia Hills District, Umlangshor, 25°28'27"N 92°12'52"E, 18.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311607.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis purusamedha* 1995 F. Schmid / *Oecetis purusamedha* Sch. CNC No. 22089 HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Description incorrectly listed month of collection as June.

raghava Schmid 1995b, *Oecetis*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Bhairabkunda 18-21-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311609.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** Udalguri District, Bhairabkunda, 26°53'2"N 92°6'51"E, 18-21.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 311609.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis raghava* 1995 F. Schmid / *Oecetis raghava* S. CNC No. 22088 HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Description listed dates of collection as 16-21.

rajasimha Schmid 1995c, Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Yodpai 16-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311625.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka:** Yodpai, 16.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311625.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis rajasimha* 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Oecetis rajasimha* CNC No. 22147.

sachrika Schmid 1987, Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Lushai) [=Mizo Hills] Sairang 20-IX-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311853.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Mizoram:** Aizawl District, Sairang, 23°48'35"N 92°39'23"E, 20.ix.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311853.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes sachrika* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18918 *Setodes sachrika*.

sadbhuta Schmid 1987, Leptocerus

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.D.M.N.C.H.) [=United district of Mikir Hills and North Cachar] Kalanga [sic] 1-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311729.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Assam:** Karbi Anglong District, Kalonga, 25°53'34"N 92°44'40"E, 1.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311729.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptocerus sadbhuta* 1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18990 *Leptocerus sadbhuta* [sic].

sahadeva Schmid 1968a, Poecilopsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Bohar [sic] 13-III-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311683.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Boha, 27°1'2"N 92°9'54"E, 13.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311683.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Poecilopsyche sahadeva* 1967 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11400 *Poec. sahadeva*.

sakantaka Schmid 1987, Leptocerus

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Subrahmanya 20-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311696.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka:** Subrahmanya, 12°40'9"N 75°36'38.01"E, 20.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311696.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptocerus sakantaka* 1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18968 *Leptocerus sakantaka*.

samchita Schmid 1987, Leptocerus

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Kerala) Kolattupuzha 22-XII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311691.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala:** Kulathupuzha, 8°54'32.48"N 77°3'33.56"E, 22.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311691.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptocerus samchita* 1984 F. Schmid HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18964 *Leptocerus samchita*.

Comments: CNC Type number erroneously listed as "19864" in description.

samnata Schmid 1987, Leptocerus

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Thangrain 22-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311704.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia Hills District, Thangrain, 25°34'48"N 92°26'22"E, 22.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311704.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptocerus samnata* 1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18975 *Leptocerus samnata*.

samphulla Schmid 1987, Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Meppadi 9-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311846.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala:** Meppadi, 11°33'17"N 76°8'7"E, 9.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC 311846.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes samphulla* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18910 *Setodes samphulla*.

samprabhinna Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Kattalaimala 16-17-I-1962 F.Schmid / CNC 311875.

Interpretive data: **INDIA.** Madras [likely in either present day Kerala or Tamil Nadu State], Kattalaimala, 16-17.i.1962, F. Schmid, CNC 311875.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes samprabhinna* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18938 *Setodes samprabhinna*.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

sarchtika Schmid 1987, *Leptocerus*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Chingsao 15-VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311702.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Chingsao, 15.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311702.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptocerus sarchtika* 1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18974 *Leptocerus sarchtika*.

Comments: CNC Type number erroneously listed as "19874" in description.

sarvapunya Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Kerala) Ponmudi 12-I-1962 F.Schmid / CNC 311882.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala:** Ponmudi, 8°45'35"N 77°6'55"E, 12.i.1962, F. Schmid, CNC311882.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes sarvapunya* 1986 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18945 *Setodes sarvapunya*.

satichaya Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Harmal 4-5-IX-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 311861.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Chamoli District, Harmal, 30°3'18.21"N 79°47'25.61"E, 4-5.ix.1958, F. Schmid, CNC311861.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes satichaya* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18925 *Setodes satichaya*.

satyagraha Schmid 1995a, *Oecetis*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Nafra 26-VI-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311744.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Nafra, 27°22'20"N 92°32'45"E, 26.vi.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 311744.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis satyagraha* 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Oecetis satyagraha* S. CNC No. 22084.

savibhrama Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Lagairong 26-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311854.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Lagairong, 24°42'0"N 93°32'0"E, 26.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311854.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes savibhrama* 1986 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18917 *Setodes savibhrama*.

schmidi (Manuel & Nimmo 1984), *Triaenodes* [*Ylodes*]

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Interpretive data: **CANADA. Yukon:** Seaforth Creek, Alaska Hwy. 72.6km W Teslin Bridge, 60°26'46"N 113°34'52"W, 24.vii.1979, A. Nimmo, CNC481654.

Comments: Specimen lost – unique identifier added to unit tray for eventual addition to specimen.

subhachita Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Kerala) Kolattupuzha 19-XII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311781.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala:** Kulathupuzha, 8°54'32.48"N 77°3'33.56"E, 19.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311781.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes subhachita* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18864 *Setodes subhachita*.

sucharu Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Kalaktang 14-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311870.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Kalaktang, 27°6'28"N

92°7'2"E, 14.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311870.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes sucharu* 1985
F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18934 *Setodes sucharu*.

sudhara Schmid 1987, *Leptocerus*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Someshwar 27-I-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 311693.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka**: Someshwar, 13°29'33"N 75°3'51"E, 27.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311693.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptocerus sudhara* 1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18966 *Leptocerus sudhara*.

sukhabaddha Schmid 1987, *Leptocerus*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten) (Figs 1, 2)
Verbatim: Inde (Kerala) Kalial 7-I-1962 F.Schmid / CNC 311695.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala**: Kalial, 7.i.1962, F. Schmid, CNC311695.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptocerus sukhabaddha* 1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18967 *Leptocerus sukhabaddha*.

Comments: The specific epithet for this taxon is spelled quite inconsistently by Schmid; it is presented as "sukhabadda" on the type label, "sukhabaddha" on the CNC type number label and in the original work by Schmid (1987) in both the index (p. 146) and the species list (p. 138); the actual species description (Schmid, 1987: 117) presents the name as "sukhabaddha", which is provisionally accepted here.

supattra Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Hariarpur 25-I-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 311842.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka**: Hariharapura, 13°31'18"N 75°17'59.90"E, 25.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311842.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes supattra* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18906 *Setodes supattra*.

suyodhana Schmid 1968a, *Poecilopsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Chumtang [sic] 13-V-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 311684.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Chungthang, 27°36'14"N 88°38'47"E, 13.v.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311684.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Poecilopsyche suyodhana* 1967 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11396 *Poec. suyadhana* [sic].

tarbaka Gordon & Schmid 1987 [In: Schmid (1987)], *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, ethyl alcohol)
Verbatim: THAILAND: chw. Chiang Mai, amp. Fang tambon Papah; Monungkate, April 19, 1975 A.E. Gordon, light trap / CNC 165695.

Interpretive data: **THAILAND. Chiang Mai**: amp. Fang, tambon Papah, Monungkate, 19.iv. 1975, A.E. Gordon, light trap, CNC165695.

Determination: *Setodes tarpaka*, n. sp. Gordon and Schmid HOLOTYPE: MALE / *Setodes tarpaka* Gordon et Schmid holotype ♂.

Comments: Original publication notes depository as TISTR, Thailand.

tchaturdanta Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Sikkim Tung 2-VIII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311851.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Tung, 27°32'37"N 88°38'54"E, 2.viii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311851.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes tchaturdanta* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18915 *Setodes tchaturdanta*.

tejasvin Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (Bombay) Sykes 5-II-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 311777.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Gujarat**: Sykes, 5.ii. 1959, F. Schmid, CNC311777.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes tejasvin* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18859 *Setodes tejasvin*.

thais Schmid 1994c, *Adicella*

holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Sirohi Kashong 7-VI- 1960 F. Schmid / CNC 311554.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Siruhi Kashong, 25°6'23.19"N 94°27'28.51"E, 7.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311554.

Determination: holotype ♂ Adicella thais 1993 F. Schmid / Adicella thais Schmid CNC [type no.] 21715 Holotype ♂.

thalie Schmid 1994c, Adicella

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Shergaon 7-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311557.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Shergaon, 27°6'18"N 92°16'20"E, 7.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 311557.

Determination: holotype ♂ Adicella thalie 1993 F. Schmid / Adicella thalie Schmid CNC [type no.] 21716 Holotype ♂.

tilakita Schmid 1987, Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.P.) Rishikesh 25-31-III-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 311783.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Rishikesh, 30°5'3"N 78°15'53"E, 25-31.iii.1958, F. Schmid, CNC311783.

Determination: holotype ♂ Setodes tilakita 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18866 Setodes tilakita.

tridanta Schmid 1987, Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Lifakpo 29-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311857.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Liphakpu, 27°4'7"N 92°7'26"E, 29.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 311857.

Determination: holotype ♂ Setodes tridanta 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18922 Setodes tridanta.

trikantayudha Schmid 1987, Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Kerala) Urti 15-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311881.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu:** Urti, 15.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311881.

Determination: holotype ♂ Setodes trikantayudha 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18944 Setodes trikantayuddha [sic].

trivulcio Schmid 1994a, Triaenodes

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Huiahu 1-VII-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311538.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Huishu, 25°14'47"N 94°33'10"E, 1.vii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311538.

Determination: Holotype ♂ Triaenodes trivulcio Schm CNC [type no.] 21772 / holotype ♂ Triaenodes trivulcio 1993 F. Schmid.

uchita Schmid 1987, Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Salari 10-VII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311860.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** Salari, 27°19'14.01"N 92°27'15"E, 10.vii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311860.

Determination: holotype ♂ Setodes uchita 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18924 Setodes uchita.

Comments: Description listed date of collection as 9-10.vii.1961.

udagama Holzenthal & Andersen 2007, Tagalopsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Anjadi 23-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311670.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka:** Anjadi, 23.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311670.

Determination: HOLOTYPE ♂ Tagalopsyche udagama Holzenthal + Andersen 2007.

udayakara Schmid 1995a, Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Kuttalam 15-I-1962 F.Schmid / CNC 311740.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu:** Courtalam, 8°56'1"N 77°16'40"E, 15.i.1962, F. Schmid, CNC311740.

Determination: holotype ♂ Oecetis prahlada 1995 F. Schmid / Holotype Oecetis udayakara Sch. Det. O. Lonsdale / HOLOTYPE Oecetis udayakara S. CNC No. 22077.

Comments: The holotype labels for *Oecetis prahlada* and *O. udayakara* were accidentally switched, as suggested by collection data on the label and in the description.

uddharcha Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Chingsao 15-VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311871.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Chingsao, 15.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311871.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes uddharcha* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18936 *Setodes uddharcha*.

udghona Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Khopum [sic] 27-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311862.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Khoupum, 24°39'16"N 93°26'52"E, 27.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311862.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes udghona* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18926 *Setodes udghona*.

ukchatara Schmid 1987, *Leptocerus*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal, Lingari 1-IX-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 311708.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Pauri Garhwal District, Lingari, 1.ix.1958, F. Schmid, CNC311708.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptocerus ukchatara* 1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18978 *Leptocerus ukchatara*.

upadana Schmid 1995a, *Oecetis*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Bilo La 10-VI-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311742.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** Kameng Frontier Division [now divided into the districts of Tawang, East Kameng and West Kameng], Bilo La, 10.vi.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311742.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis upadana* 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Oecetis upadana* S. CNC No. 22079.

uttamavarna Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Kerala) Sangalipalam 20-21-XII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311767.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala:** Sangalipalam, 20-21.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311767.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes uttamavarna* 1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18852 *Setodes uttamavarna*.

vakrita Schmid 1987, *Leptocerus*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Lagairong 26-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311709.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Lagairong, 24°42'0"N 93°32'0"E, 26.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311709.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Leptocerus vakrita* 1984 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18980 *Leptocerus vakrita*.

Comments: Description incorrectly listed day of collection as the 28th.

vanaprachta Schmid 1995b, *Oecetis*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Yongphu 12-VIII-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311605.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Yongphu, 12.viii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311605.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis vanaprachta* 1995 F. Schmid / *Oecetis vanaprachta* S. CNC No. 22095.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

vasugupta Schmid 1995b, *Oecetis*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Khasi and Jaintia Hills], Thangrain 22-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311608.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia Hills District, Thangrain, 25°34'48"N 92°26'22"E, 22.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311608.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis vasugupta* 1995 F. Schmid / *Oecetis vasugupta* S. CNC No. 22094 HOLOTYPE.

vayu Schmid 1968a, *Poecilopsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Phutang 28-IX-1961
F.Schmid / CNC 311686.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
West Kameng District, Phutang, 27°14'0"N
92°14'0"E, 28.ix.1961, F. Schmid, CNC
311686.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Poecilopsyche* vayu
1967 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11390 *Poec.* vayu.

vichitrita* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Pykara 31-XII-1958
F.Schmid / CNC 311844.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu**: Pykara,
11°27'23"N 76°35'52"E, 31.xii.1958, F.
Schmid, CNC311844.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes* vichitrita
1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
18907 *Setodes* vichitrita.

vidhyadara* Schmid 1995c, *Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and
Khasi Hills] Mawlang 12-IV-1960 F.Schmid /
CNC 311638.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: East
Khasi Hills District, Mawlang, 25°39'44"N
91°50'30"E, 12.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC
311638.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis* vidhyadara
1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Oecetis* vidhy-
adara CNC No. 22154.

vidura* Schmid 1968a, *Poecilopsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Lifakpo 15-V-1961
F.Schmid / CNC 311685.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
West Kameng District, Liphakpu, 27°4'7"N
92°7'26"E, 15.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC
311685.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Poecilopsyche* vidura
1967 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11391 *Poec.* vidura.

vijayaditya* Schmid 1995b, *Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Nagodi 28-I-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 311621.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka**: Nagodi,
13°55'47"N 74°54'10"E, 28.i.1959, F. Schmid,
CNC311621.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis* vijayaditya
1995 F. Schmid / *Oecetis* vijayaditya S. CNC
No. 22097 HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

vikramaditya* Schmid 1995b, *Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Kattalaimala 25-26-XII-
1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311620.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Madras** [likely in either
present day Kerala or Tamil Nadu State],
Kattalaimala, 25-26.xii.1961, F. Schmid,
CNC311620.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis* vikramaditya
1995 F. Schmid / *Oecetis* vikramaditya S.
CNC No. 22098 HOLOTYPE.

vitanka* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Malbidu 18-I-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 311841.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka**: Malbidu,
18.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311841.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes* vitanka 1985
F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18905 *Se-*
todes vitanka.

vratachakora* Schmid 1987, *Setodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Kerala) Sangalipalam 20-21-XII-
1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311828.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala**: Sangalipalam,
20-21.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311828.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes* vratachakora
1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
18894 *Setodes* vratachakora.

vrindawama* Schmid 1995c, *Oecetis

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Yodpai 16-I-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 311641.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka**: Yodpai,
16.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311641.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis vrindawama* 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Oecetis vrindawama* CNC No. 22156.

yatharupa Schmid 1987, *Setodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Sikkim Mangang 9-V-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311858.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Mangang, 9.v.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311858.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Setodes yatharupa* 1985 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 18921 *Setodes yatharupa*.

Comments: Locality possibly refers to Mangan (27°29'54"N 88°32'3"E).

yogechwara Schmid 1995a, *Oecetis*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Ligship [sic] 28-IV-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311743.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Legship, 27° 16'46"N 88°16'29"E, 28.iv.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311743.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Oecetis yogechwara* [sic] 1995 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Oecetis yogechwara* S. CNC No. 22080.

yudhishthira Schmid 1968a, *Poecilopsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Bhairabkunda 5-6-III-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311687.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: Udalguri District, Bhairabkunda, 26°53'2"N 92°6'51"E, 5-6.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 311687.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Poecilopsyche yudhishthira* 1967 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11401 *Poec. yudhishthira*.

Comments: Description stated dates of collection as "8-6-III-1961".

LIMNEPHILIDAE

alascensis Schmid 1964b, *Grammotaulius*

Valid name: *Grammotaulius signatipennis* McLachlan 1876

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Summit L.Alaska Isabella Pass Mi. 199

3-VIII-1951 Mason & McGillis / CNC 481647.

Interpretive data: **USA. Alaska**: Summit Lake, Isabelle Pass, mi 199, 3.viii.1951, Mason & McGillis, CNC481647.

Determination: HOLOTYPE ♂ CNCNo. 8427 *Grammotaulius alascensis* F. Schmid 1963.

alba (Nimmo 1977), *Montiphylax* [*Philocasca*]

holotype (1 male, ethyl alcohol)

Verbatim: Row Bk, nr Lower Rowe Lk, 6350', Wat. Nat.Pk., Alberta.12/6/75 D.B.Donald / CNC 165756.

Interpretive data: **CANADA. Alberta**: Waterton Lakes National Park, Rowe Lake, nr Lower Rowe Lake, 49°3'9"N 114°3'27"W, 1935m, 12.vi.1975, D.B. Donald, CNC165756.

Determination: PHILOSASCA ALBA Nimmo Holotype ♂ CNC No. 15165 TRICHOPTERA: LIMNEPHILIDAE.

Comments: Right-side wings on slide.

baldur Nimmo 1971, *Homophylax*

holotype (1 male, ethyl alcohol)

Verbatim: CAMERON Lk., WAT.NAT.PK. ALTA8.45.p.m. 19/8/65, A.NIMMO / CNC 165741.

Interpretive data: **CANADA. Alberta**: Waterton Lakes National Park, Cameron Lake, 49°0'13"N 114°5'34"W, 19.viii.1965, A. Nimmo, CNC165741.

Determination: HOLOTYPE ♂ CNC No. 10,585 HOMOPHYLAX BALDUR NIMMO.

beges Oláh 2019, *Homophylax*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Squamish, B.C. Diamond Head Trail 3200 ft. Aug. 26 Edith Mason 1953/ CNC 934438.

Interpretive data: **CANADA. British Columbia**: Garibaldi Provincial Park, Diamond Head Trail, near Squamish, 975 m, 49°45'36"N 123°1'48"W, 26.viii.1953, E. Mason, CNC 934438.

Determination: *Homophylax beges* sp. nov. Holotype [J. Olah].

coros Oláh 2019, *Homophylax*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Mt. Revelstoke B.C. 17-VIII-'52 G.J. Spencer 5400' / CNC 934437.

Interpretive data: **CANADA. British Columbia**: Mount Revelstoke, 1645 m, 58°43'0"N 132°54'0"W, 17.viii.1952, G.J. Spencer, CNC 934437.

Determination: Homophylax coros sp. nov. Holotype [J. Olah].

ctenifer Flint 1967, *Limnephilus*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: 10 mi.W.El Salto Dgo.MEXICO,9000' 26.VI.1964 W.C.McGuffin / CNC 280021.

Interpretive data: **MEXICO. Durango**: 16.1 km W El Salto, 23°43'9.69"N 105°29'21.66"W, 2743m, 26.vi.1964, W.C. McGuffin, CNC 280021.

Determination: Holotype ♂ *Limnephilus ctenifer* Flint / CNCNo. 12845 *Limnephilus ctenifer* HOLOTYPE.

emarginata (Banks 1919), *Asynarchus* [*Anabolia*]

Valid name: *Asynarchus iteratus* McLachlan 1880 holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Teller July, 2,9,13 Alaska / Canadian Arctic Expedition F. [illegible]. 1913 / 705 / SLIDE No. 74 / CNC 481701.

Interpretive data: **USA. Alaska**: Teller, 65°15'51"N 166°21'42"W, 29.vii.1913, F. Johansen, CNC481701.

Determination: *Anabolia emarginata* type Bks TYPE No.1207.

mexicanus Flint 1967, *Limnephilus*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: 10 mi.W.El Salto Dgo.MEXICO,9000' 8.VI.1964 J.E.H.Martin / CNC 280018.

Interpretive data: **MEXICO. Durango**: 16.1 km W El Salto, 23°43'9.69"N 105°29'21.66"W, 2743m, 8.vi.1964, J.E.H. Martin, CNC280018.

Determination: Holotype ♂ *Limnephilus mexicanus* Flint / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 12846 *Limnephilus mexicanus*.

pollux Flint 1967, *Limnephilus*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: 10 mi.W.El Salto Dgo.MEXICO,9000' 17.VII.1964 J.E.H.Martin / CNC 280024.

Interpretive data: **MEXICO. Durango**: 16.1 km W El Salto, 23°43'9.69"N 105°29'21.66"W, 2743m, 17.vii.1964, J.E.H. Martin, CNC 280024.

Determination: Holotype ♂ *Limnephilus pollux* Flint / CNCNo. 12844 *Limnephilus pollux* HOLOTYPE.

schmidi Nimmo 1965, *Psychoglypha*

holotype (1 male, ethyl alcohol)

Verbatim: Kickinghorse Campground, under Castle Mtn., Yoho Nat-ional Park, B.C.,5/X/63,Coll. A.P.Nimmo / CNC165759.

Interpretive data: **CANADA. British Columbia**: Kicking Horse Campground, under Castle Mtn., Yoho National Park, 51°25'28.79"N 116°25'58.68"W, 5.x.1963, A.P. Nimmo, CNC 165759.

Determination: *Psychoglypha schmidi* Nimmo Holotype ♂ / *Psychoglypha schmidi* Nimmo HOLOTYPE CNC No. 9166.

Comments: Specific locality listed as "directly below Mt. Stephen" in description.

subborealis Schmid 1964b, *Grammotaulius*

Valid name: *Grammotaulius signatipennis* McLachlan 1876

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: King Salmon, Naknek R.Alaska 9-VIII-1952 W.R.Mason / CNC 481648.

Interpretive data: **USA. Alaska**: King Salmon, Naknek River, 58°41'20"N 156°39'35"W, 9.viii.1952, W.R. Mason, CNC481648.

Determination: HOLOTYPE ♂ CNCNo. 8428 *Grammotaulius subborealis* F. Schmid 1963.

susana Nimmo 1971, *Limnephilus*

Valid name: *Limnephilus sackeni* Banks 1930

holotype+allotype (2 male/female, ethyl alcohol)

Verbatim: For.TR.Rd.,at Pembina R., Alta., sedge swamp, 22/9/68. A. Nimmo / CNC 165749.

Interpretive data: **CANADA. Alberta**: Forestry Trunk Road about 1 mile north of crossing of Pembina River, 52°56'42.08"N 116°35'3.39"W, sedge, swamp, 22.ix.1968, A. Nimmo, CNC165749.

Determination: HOLOTYPE ♂ CNC No. 10,586 LIMNEPHILUS SUSANA NIMMO / ALLO-

TYPE ♀ CNC No. 10,586 LIMNEPHILUS
SUSANA NIMMO.

thor (Nimmo 1971), *Montiphylax* [*Philocasca*]

holotype (1 male, ethyl alcohol)

Verbatim: Path to Apl. Meadows, Edith Cavel,
Jasper Nat. Pk. Hab. [illegible], 10-12.a.m.
4/7/65, A. NIMMO / AR / CNC 165757.

Interpretive data: CANADA. Alberta: Jasper
National Park, Path to alpine meadows, east of
Mt. Edith Cavell, 52°40'58.32"N 118°2'
51.19"W, hab. [illegible, not noted in de-
scription], 4.vii.1965, A. Nimmo, CNC
165757.

Determination: HOLOTYPE CNC No. 10,588
PHILOCASCA THOR NIMMO.

tibetanus Schmid 1966, *Asynarchus*

holotype (1 male, pinned:card)

Verbatim: Sikkim Goma Sechen 3-VI-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 280111.

Interpretive data: INDIA. Sikkim: Goma Sechen,
3.vi.1959, F. Schmid, CNC280111.

Determination: *Asynarchus tibetanus* Schm.
HOLOTYPE ♂ CNCNo. 8900.

Comments: Poor condition, with two wings and
part of thorax on glue board.

tibeticus Schmid 1966, *Limnephilus*

holotype (1 female, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Phurunda 24-VI-1958
F.Schmid / CNC 280011.

Interpretive data: INDIA. Uttarakhand: Pauri
Garhwal District, Phurunda, 24.vi.1958, F.
Schmid, CNC280011.

Determination: *Limnephilus tibeticus* Schm. HO-
LOTYPE ♀ CNCNo. 8899.

valhalla Nimmo, *Limnephilus*

Valid name: *Limnephilus moestus* Banks 1908

holotype (1 male, ethyl alcohol)

Verbatim: 1st POOLS, PATH to ALPINE
MEADOWS, MT.EDITH CAVELL,J.N.P.,
ALTA., 12,50.p.m. 25/7/66, A. NIMMO /
CNC 165750.

Interpretive data: CANADA. Alberta: Jasper
National Park, Mt. Edith, 1st pools, path to Mt.
Edith Cavell, alpine meadows, 52°40'58.32"N

118°2'51.19"W, 2072m, 25.vii.1969, A.
Nimmo, CNC165750.

Determination: HOLOTYPE ♂ CNC No.10,587 /
ALLOTYPE ♀ CNC No.10,587.

vernalis Nimmo, *Limnephilus*

Valid name: *Limnephilus argenteus* Banks 1914

holotype (1 male, ethyl alcohol)

Verbatim: Grande Prairie, Alberta, 25/6/75. Alta
Agric. Lite Trap / CNC 165754.

Interpretive data: CANADA. Alberta: Grande
Prairie, 55°10'15"N 118°47'41"W, 25.vi.1975,
Agric. Lite Trap, CNC165754.

Determination: LIMNEPHILUS VERNALIS
NIMMO HOLOTYPE ♂ CNC No. 15164
TRICHOPTERA:LIMNEPHILIDAE.

Comments: Right side wings on slide.

MOLANNIDAE

comans (Wiggins 1968), *Molannodes* [*Indomolannodes*]

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and
Khasi Hills] Umlangshor 18-IV-1960 F.Schmid /
Illustrated - G.B.W. / CNC 311421.

Interpretive data: INDIA. Meghalaya: Jaintia
Hills District, Umlangshor, 25°28'27"N 92°
12'52"E, 18.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311421.

Determination: Holotype *Indomolannodes*
comans Wiggins 1968 / HOLOTYPE / HO-
LOTYPE CNCNo. 11383b Ind. comans.

crinita Wiggins 1968, *Molanna*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Chug 16-IV-1961
F.Schmid / CNC 311456.

Interpretive data: INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:
West Kameng District, Chug, 27°25'4"N
92°14'3"E, 16.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC
311456.

Determination: Holotype *Molanna crinita*
Wiggins 1968 / HOLOTYPE / HOLOTYPE
CNCNo. 11378 M. crinita.

decurvatus (Wiggins 1968), *Molannodes* [*Indomolannodes*]

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Chingsao 15-VI-1960 F.Schmid / Illustrated - G.B.W. / CNC 311418.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Chingsao, 15.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311418.

Determination: Holotype Indomolannodes decurvatus Wiggins 1968 / HOLOTYPE / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11380 Ind. decurvatus.

excavatus (Wiggins 1968), Molannodes [Indomolannodes]

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Poi 4-VII-1960 F. Schmid / Illustrated - G.B.W. / CNC 311417.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Poi, 25°16' 35"N 94°33'26"E, 4.vii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311417.

Determination: Holotype Indomolannodes excavatus Wiggins 1968 / HOLOTYPE / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11382 Ind. excavatus.

falcifer (Wiggins 1968), Molannodes [Indomolannodes]

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Rumkheng 24-III-1960 F.Schmid / Illustrated - G.B.W. / CNC 311419.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: United Jaintia and Khasi Hills [now divided into East and West Khasi Hills Districts and East and West Jaintia Hills Districts], Rumkheng, 24.iii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC311419.

Determination: Holotype Indomolannodes falcifer Wiggins 1968 / HOLOTYPE / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11383 Ind. falcifer.

incurvatus (Wiggins 1968), Molannodes [Indomolannodes]

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Shergaon 9-V-1961 F.Schmid / Illustrated - G.B.W. / CNC 311420.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Shergaon, 27°6'18"N 92°16'20"E, 9.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 311420.

Determination: Holotype Indomolannodes incurvatus Wiggins 1968 / HOLOTYPE / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11381 Ind. incurvatus.

paramoesta Wiggins 1968, Molanna

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Madhya Pr.) Satanwara [sic] 28-XI-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311460.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Madhya Pradesh**: Satanwada, 25°44'51.21"N 77°24'29.44"E, 28.xi.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311460.

Determination: Holotype Molanna paramoesta Wiggins 1968 / HOLOTYPE / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11377 M. paramoesta.

saetigera Wiggins 1968, Molanna

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Mawlang 12-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 311455.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: East Khasi Hills District, Mawlang, 25°39'44"N 91°50'30"E, 12.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 311455.

Determination: Holotype Molanna saetigera Wiggins 1968 / HOLOTYPE / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11379 M. saetigera.

ODONTOCERIDAE

assamensis Parker & Wiggins 1987, Psilotreta

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Rahung 17-VII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311391.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Rahung, 27°18'37"N 92°23'41"E, 17.vii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 311391.

Determination: Holotype ♂ Psilotreta assamensis Parker & Wiggins / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 19804 Psilotreta assamensis Wigg.

schmidi Parker & Wiggins 1987, Psilotreta

holotype (1 male, pinned) (Figs 3, 4)

Verbatim: Sikkim Padamchen [sic] 30-VIII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311390.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Padamchey, 27°12'44.46"N 88°37'13.88"E, 30.viii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311390.

Determination: Holotype ♂ Psilotreta schmidi Parker & Wiggins / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 19803 Psilotreta schmidi Wiggins.

PHILOPOTAMIDAE

achemenus Schmid 1959b, *Philopotamus*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Iran (Ost. 2) Garna 2-IX-1955
F.Schmid / CNC 236262.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. Mazandaran**: Garna,
35°53'47"N 52°11'2"E, 2.ix.1955, F. Schmid,
CNC236262.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Philopotamus* *achemenus* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12280 *Philopotamus* *achemenus* HOLOTYPE.

achtadachi Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and
Khasi Hills] Nongrim 10-X-1960 F.Schmid /
CNC 236167.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: West
Khasi Hills District, Nongrim, 25°34'1"N 91°
54'9"E, 10.x.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236167.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella* *achtadachi*
[sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11163 G. 8-dachi.

achtami Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and
Khasi Hills] Purnasampara 23-24-XII-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 236157.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: United
Jaintia and Khasi Hills [now divided into East
and West Khasi Hills Districts and East and
West Jaintia Hills Districts], Purnasampara,
23-24.xii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236157.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella* *achtami*
1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11153 G. achtami.

achtatrimchi Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Lifakpo 15-V-1961
F.Schmid / CNC 236186.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
West Kameng District, Liphakpu, 27°4'7"N
92°7'26"E, 15.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC
236186.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella* *achta-*

trinçi [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE
CNCNo.11181 G. 8-trimchi.

Comments: Description incorrectly listed date of
collection as the 13th. Body slide mounted on
pin.

achtavimchi Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Kottagudi 23-I-1962
F.Schmid / CNC 236176.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu**: Kotta-
gudi, 10°5'2"N 77°14'10"E, 23.i.1962, F.
Schmid, CNC236176.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella* *achta-*
vimçi [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE
CNCNo. 11172 G. 8-vimchi.

acteon (Schmid 1991b), *Wormaldia* [*Doloclans*]

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Swamp Hill 10-XII-
1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236140.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Madras** [likely in either
present day Kerala or Tamil Nadu State],
Swamp Hill, 10.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC
236140.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Doloclans* *acteon*
1991 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Doloclans*
acteon Schm. CNC No. 21223.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

alcmeon (Schmid 1991b), *Wormaldia* [*Doloclans*]

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Swamp Hill 10-XII-
1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236139.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Madras** [likely in either
present day Kerala or Tamil Nadu State],
Swamp Hill, 10.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC
236139.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Doloclans* *alcmeon*
1991 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Doloclans* *alc-*
meon CNC Co. 21224.

anactorion (Schmid 1991b), *Wormaldia* [*Doloclans*]

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Perumalmai 5-XII-
1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236142.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu:** Perumal Malai, 10°15'57"N 77°32'42"E, 5.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC236142.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Doloclanes anactorion* 1991 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Doloclanes anactorion* Schm. CNC No. 21225.

beaumonti* Schmid 1952, *Wormaldia

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Espagne (Seg.) La Granja 23-IX-1950 F. Schmid / CNC 236121.

Interpretive data: **SPAIN. Segovia:** au-dessus de La Granja Parc Nat. 40°53'52"N 4°0'17"W, 23.ix.1950, F. Schmid, CNC236121.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Wormaldia beaumonti* 1950 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12426 *Wormaldia beaumonti* HOLOTYPE.

bicoloroides* Flint 1967, *Chimarra

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: 10 mi.W.El Salto Dgo.MEXICO,9000' 28.VIII.1964 J.E.H.Martin / CNC 236223.

Interpretive data: **MEXICO. Durango:** 16.1 km W. El Salto, 23°43'9.69"N 105°29'21.66"W, 2743m, 28.viii.1964, J.E.H. Martin, CNC 236223.

Determination: Holotype ♂ *Chimarra bicoloroides* Flint / *Chimarra bicoloroides* HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 19254.

bodhidarma* Schmid 1960, *Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Frontier Province] Balakot 23-VI-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 236171.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa:** Balakot, 34°32'22"N 73°21'2.01"E, 23.vi.1953, F. Schmid, CNC236171.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella bodhidarma* 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11168 G. bodhidarma.

Comments: Second slide on pin with coverslip and mounted parts (presumably two wings) missing; first slide with genitalia.

occipitalis bosniaca* Botoșăneanu 1960, *Wormaldia

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Bosnie Trebevic 15-VII-1955 F.Schmid / CNC 236120.

Interpretive data: **BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA.** Trebević, 43°47'47"N 18°28'44"E, 15.vii.1955, F. Schmid, CNC236120.

Determination: Holotype ♂ / *Wormaldia occipitalis bosniaca* ♂ Bots. / CNCNo. 12425 *Wormaldia bosniaca* HOLOTYPE.

chodachi* Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (W.B.) Lingsoka 7-IX-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236165.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. West Bengal:** Lingsoka, 27°8'59.92"N 88°40'22.25"E, 7.ix.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236165.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella chodaçi* [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11161 G. 6-dachi.

chotrimchi* Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Bokhar 28-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236183.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Boha, 27°1'2"N 92°9'54"E, 28.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC236183.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella chotrimchi* 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11179 G. 6-trimchi.

chovimchi* Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Meppadi 9-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236174.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala:** Meppadi, 11°33'17"N 76°8'7"E, 9.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236174.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella chovimchi* 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11171 G. 6-vimchi.

dachami* Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Kerala) Vellala Mudi 15-XII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236159.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala:** Vellala Mudi, 15.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC236159.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella daçami* [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11155 G. dachami.

***dexileon* (Schmid 1991b), *Wormaldia* [*Doloclanes*]**

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Khasi and Jaintia Hills] Syndai 25-XII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236138.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: Jaintia Hills District, Syndai, 25°11'8.01"N 92°8'25"E, 25.xii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236138.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Doloclanes dexileon* 1991 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Doloclanes dexileon* CNC Co. 21232.

Comments: Description listed date of collection as the 26th, another day when Schmid was at that locality. Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

dharmakala* Schmid 1960, *Dolophilodes

Valid name: *Dolophilodes ornata* Ulmer 1909

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Frontier Province] Balakot 16-X-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 236266.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa**: Balakot, 34°32'22"N 73°21'2.01"E, 16.x.1953, F. Schmid, CNC236266.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Dolophilodes dharmakala* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12329 *Dolophilodes dharmakala* HOLOTYPE.

dharmamitra* Schmid 1960, *Dolophilodes

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Frontier Province] Naran 30-VI,5-VII-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 236264.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa**: Naran, 34°54'28"N 73°38'57"E, 30.vi-5.vii.1953, F. Schmid, CNC236264.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Dolophilodes dharmamitra* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12331 *Dolophilodes dharmamitra* HOLOTYPE.

dharmaraksa* Schmid 1960, *Dolophilodes

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Fron-

tier Province] Naran 30-VI,5-VII-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 236265.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa**: Naran, 34°54'28"N 73°38'57"E, 30.vi-5.vii.1953, F. Schmid, CNC236265.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Dolophilodes dharmaraksa* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12330 *Dolophilodes dharmaraksa* HOLOTYPE.

***dolophion* (Schmid 1991b), *Wormaldia* [*Doloclanes*]**

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Khumyara 3-4-V-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 236148.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Pauri Garhwal District, Khumyara, 3-4.v.1958, F. Schmid, CNC236148.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Doloclanes dolophion* 1991 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Doloclanes dolophion* Sch. CNC No. 21231.

Comments: Locality possibly Khumara (30°33'15"N 79°3'44"W). Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

dvadachi* Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Malbidu 18-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236161.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka**: Malbidu, 18.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236161.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella dvadaçi* [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11157 G. 2-dachi.

dvatrimchi* Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Kerala) Vellala Mudi 15-XII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236180.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala**: Vellala Mudi, 15.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC236180.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella dvatrimçi* [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11175 G. 2-trimchi.

dvitiya* Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Khasi and Jaintia Hills] Muktapur 11-12-XII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236152.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia Hills District, Muktapur, 25°9'35"N 92°7'54"E, 11-12.xii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236152.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella* dvitiya 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11148 G. dvitiya.

ekadachi Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Kerala) Tenmalai [sic] 26-XI-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 236160.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala:** Thenmala, 8°57'48"N 77°3'54"E, 26.xi.1958, F. Schmid, CNC236160.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella* ekadaçi [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11156 G. 1-dachi.

ekatrimchi Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Mormangeri [sic] 16-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236179.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka:** Monnangeri, 12°28'49.86"N 75°36'46.76"E, 16.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236179.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella* ekatrimçi [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11174 G. 1-trimchi.

ekavimchi Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.D.M.N.C.H.) [=United district of Mikir Hills and North Cachar] Bangku 7-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236168.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Assam:** [United District now treated as separate Mikir Hills and Karbi Anglong Districts], Bangku, 7.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236168.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella* ekavimçi [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11166 G. 1-vimchi.

endymion (Schmid 1991b), *Wormaldia* [*Doloclanes*]

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Rumkheng 26-III-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236143.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** United Jaintia and Khasi Hills [now divided into East and West Khasi Hills Districts and East and West Jaintia Hills Districts], Rumkheng, 26.iii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236143.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Doloclanes* endymion 1991 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Doloclanes* endymion Schm. CNC No. 21227.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

epestion Schmid 1991b, *Wormaldia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Gudalur 6-7-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236124.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu:** Gudalur, 11°30'13"N 76°29'29"E, 6-7.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236124.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Wormaldia* epestion 1991 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Wormaldia* epestion Schm CNC No. 21219.

Comments: Description incorrectly listed month of collection as October. Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

gesugta Schmid 1968e, *Wormaldia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: U.S.A. Cal. Del Norte Co. Gasquet 4-VI-1965 F.Schmid / CNC 236132.

Interpretive data: **USA. California:** Del Norte Co., Gasquet, 41°50'44.01"N 123°58'10"W, 4.vi.1965, F. Schmid, CNC236132.

Determination: holotype ♂ CNCNo. 9645 1967 *Wormaldia* gesugta Schm.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

houvichka Schmid 1960, *Chimarra*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pakistan (Penjab) Murree 8-VI-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 236197.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Punjab:** Murree, 33°54'31"N 73°23'35.01"E, 8.vi.1953, F. Schmid, CNC236197.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Chimarra* houvichka 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12335 *Chimarra* houvichka HOLOTYPE.

hyperion (Schmid 1991b), *Wormaldia* [*Doloclanes*]

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Khopum [sic] 27-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236141.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Khoupum, 24°39'16"N 93°26'52"E, 27.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236141.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Doloclans hyperion* 1991 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Doloclans hyperion* Schm. CNC No. 21226.

***ixion* (Schmid 1991b), *Wormaldia* [*Doloclans*]**
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Pynter 21-22-I-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236144.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: East Khasi Hills District, Pynter, 25°15'49"N 91°57'49"E, 21-22.i.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 236144.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Doloclans ixion* 1991 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Doloclans ixion* Schm. CNC No. 21230.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

kalmasa* Schmid 1991b, *Dolomyia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (C.) [=Cachar District] Bandarkhal 9-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236149.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Assam**: Cachar District, Bandarkhal, 25°3'30"N 92°48'4"E, 9.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236149.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Dolomyia kalmasa* 1991 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Dolomyia kalmasa* Schm. CNC No. 21218.

kalmasita* Schmid 1991b, *Dolopsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Nongrim 28-III-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236150.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: West Khasi Hills District, Nongrim, 25°34'1"N 91°54'9"E, 28.iii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 236150.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Dolopsyche kalmasita* 1991 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Dolopsyche kalmasita* Schm. CNC No. 21217.

khourmai* Schmid 1959b, *Wormaldia

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Iran (Maz.) Zanus 21-IX-1955 F.Schmid / CNC 236118.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. Mazandaran**: Zanoos, 36°19'59.42"N 51°32'37.03"E, 21.ix.1955, F. Schmid, CNC236118.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Wormaldia khourmai* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12281 *Wormaldia khourmai* HOLOTYPE.

triangulifera kimminsi* Botoșăneanu 1960, *Wormaldia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Macédoine Perister 12-16-VIII-1955 F.Schmid / CNC 236122.

Interpretive data: **MACEDONIA**. Baba Mountain, 41°0'12"N 21°11'3"E, 12-16.viii.1955, F. Schmid, CNC236122.

Determination: Holotype ♂ / *Wormaldia triangulifera kimminsi* ♂ Bots. / CNCNo. 12424 *Wormaldia kimminsi* HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Elevated to species by H. Malicky (1977).

madakumbura* Schmid 1958, *Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Ceylan (Sab.) Rondura 3-III-1954 F.Schmid / CNC 236173.

Interpretive data: **SRI LANKA. Sabaragamuwa Province**: Rondura, 6°59'43.44"N 80°27'40.68"E, 3.iii.1954, F. Schmid, CNC236173.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella madakumbura* 1956 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11170 *G. madakumbura*.

madhyamika* Schmid 1960, *Dolophilodes

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Frontier Province] Kawai [sic] 17-X-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 236249.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa**: Kiwai, 34°37'59.01"N 73°26'39"E, 17.x.1953, F. Schmid, CNC236249.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Dolophilodes madhyamika* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12332 *Kisaura madhyamika* HOLOTYPE.

mattheyi* Schmid 1952, *Wormaldia

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Espagne (Ma.) Puerto El Paular 24-IX-1950 F. Schmid / CNC 236119.

Interpretive data: **SPAIN. Madrid**: Puerto El Paular, 40°27'19"N 3°48'20.01"W, 24.ix.1950, F. Schmid, CNC236119.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Wormaldia mattheyi* 1950 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12427 *Wormaldia mattheyi* HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Treated as subspecies of *Wormaldia variegata* Mosely 1930 by Kimmins (1953).

melanion* Schmid 1991b, *Wormaldia

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Hi 3-IV-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236136.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Hi, 3.iv.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236136.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Wormaldia melanion* 1991 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Wormaldia melanion* Schm. CNC No. 21221.

Comments: Type label incorrectly stated type number as 21220.

navadachi* Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Langdang 5-VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236169.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Langdang, 25°7'25"N 94°24'16"E, 5.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236169.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella navadaçi* [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11164 G. 9-dachi.

navami* Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (C.) [=Cachar District] Damchara 10-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236158.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Assam**: Cachar District, Damchara, 25°0'47.01"N 92°45'0"E, 10.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236158.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella navami* 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11154 G. navami.

navavimchi* Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Malbidu 18-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236177.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka**: Malbidu, 18.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236177.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella navavimçi* [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11173 G. 9-vimchi.

nigrorosea* Schmid 1960, *Chimarra

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Bélouchistan Central Zarghun 28-IV-1954 F.Schmid / CNC 236204.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Balochistan**: Central Zarghun, 28.iv.1954, F. Schmid, CNC 236204.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Chimarra nigrorosea* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12334 *Chimarra nigrorosea* HOLOTYPE.

nigrorosea* Schmid 1991b, *Wormaldia

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Jhum La 1-2-VI-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236137.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: Kameng Frontier Division [now divided into the districts of Tawang, East Kameng and West Kameng], Jhum La, 1-2.vi.1961, F. Schmid, CNC236137.

Determination: HOLOTYPE *Wormaldia nigrorosea* Sch CNC No. 21222 / holotype ♂ *Wormaldia nigrorosea* 1991 F. Schmid.

nora* Nimmo 1977, *Dolophilodes

Valid name: *Dolophilodes pallidipes* Banks 1936 holotype (1 male, ethyl alcohol)

Verbatim: Bertha Bk, 6000', Wat. Nat. Pk.Alberta 30/8/75 D.B. Donald / CNC 165674.

Interpretive data: **CANADA. Alberta**: Waterton Lakes National Park, Bertha Lake, 49°1'36"N 113°55'38"W, 1828m, 30.viii.1975, D.B. Donald, CNC165674.

Determination: *Dolophilodes nora* Nimmo HOLOTYPE ♂ CNC No. 15166 Trichoptera: Philopotamidae.

Comments: Right side wings on slide.

***nyctimon* (Schmid 1991b), *Wormaldia* [*Dolocla-*
nes]**

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Lithan 10-VIII-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236146.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Litan, 10. viii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236146.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Doloclanes nyctimon* 1991 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Doloclanes nyctimon* Schm. CNC No. 21229.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

pachtchima* Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Nyukmadong 23-IV-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236187.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Nyukmadung, 27°25' 1"N 92°7'57"E, 23.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 236187.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella paçtchima* [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11182 G. *pachtchima*.

pantchadachi* Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Sihai Khulen [sic] 25-VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236164.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Sihai Khulen, 25°10'10"N 94°29'13"E, 25.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236164.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella pantchadaçi* [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11160 G. 5-dachi.

pantchami* Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Nongrim 28-III-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236155.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** West Khasi Hills District, Nongrim, 25°34'1"N 91° 54'9"E, 28.iii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236155.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella pantchami* 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11151 G. *pantchami*.

pantchatrimchi* Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Lushai) Waiten 8-IX-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236185.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Mizoram:** Waiten, 24° 13'17"N 92°58'32"E, 8.ix.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236185.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella pantchatrimçi* [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11178 G. 5-trimchi.

prathama* Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Bhairabkunda 8-III-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236151.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** Udalguri District, Bhairabkunda, 26°53'2"N 92°6'51"E, 8.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC236151.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella prathama* 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11147 G. *prathama*.

saptadachi* Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: West Tien-mu-shan Prov. Chekiang 6.6.1932.H.Höne / CNC 236166.

Interpretive data: **CHINA. Zhejiang:** West Tien-mu-shan, 6.vi.1932, H. Höne, CNC236166.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella saptadaçi* [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11162 G. 7-dachi.

saptami* Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Mawpran 9-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236156.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** East Khasi Hills District, Mawpran, 25°17'28"N 91°57'26"E, 9.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 236156.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella saptami* 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11152 G. *saptami*.

saptatrimchi* Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Kalaktang 14-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236184.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Kalaktang, 27°6'28"N 92°7'2"E, 14.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC236184.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella saptatrimçi* [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11180 G. 7-trimchi.

saptavimchi Schmid 1968c, Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Gudalur 6-7-I-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 236175.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu:** Gudalur,
11°30'13"N 76°29'29"E, 6-7.i.1959, F. Schmid,
CNC236175.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella saptavimchi* [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE
CNCNo. 11167 G. 7-vimchi.

suryasena Schmid 1960, Chimarra

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Frontier Province] Balakot 16-X-1953 F.Schmid /
CNC 236206.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa:** Balakot, 34°32'22"N 73°21'2.01"E,
16.x.1953, F. Schmid, CNC236206.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Chimarra souryasena*
1957 F.Schmid / [CNC Type No. 12336]
Chimarra souryasena Schmid HOLOTYPE.

tchaturdachi Schmid 1968c, Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Loni 16-VI-1960
F.Schmid / CNC 236163.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Loni, 16.vi.
1960, F. Schmid, CNC236163.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella tchaturdachi* [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE
CNCNo. 11159 G. 4-dachi.

tchaturti Schmid 1968c, Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Nakhu 3-VII-1961
F.Schmid / CNC 236154.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:**
West Kameng District, Nakhu, 27°24'9"N
92°33'38.01"E, 3.vii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC
236154.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella tchaturti*
1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11150 G. tchaturti.

tchaturtrimchi Schmid 1968c, Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Kerala) Kandalur 31-I-1962
F.Schmid / CNC 236182.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala:** Kandalur,
31.i.1962, F. Schmid, CNC236182.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella tchaturtrimchi* [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE
CNCNo. 11177 G. 4-trimchi.

therapion Schmid 1991b, Wormaldia

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Jhum La 24-25-III-
1961 F. Schmid / CNC 236128.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:**
Kameng Frontier Division [now divided into
the districts of Tawang, East Kameng and
West Kameng], Jhum La, 24-25.iii.1961, F.
Schmid, CNC236128.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Wormaldia therapion*
1991 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Wormaldia*
therapion Schm CNC No. 21220.

Comments: Description incorrectly listed year of
collection as 1960.

timoleon (Schmid 1991b), Wormaldia [Doloclanes]

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Hkayam Boum 20-23-
VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236145.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Hkayam
Boum, 20-23.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC
236145.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Doloclanes timoleon*
1991 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Doloclanes*
timoleon Schm. CNC No. 21228.

tridachi Schmid 1968c, Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Kottagudi 23-I-1962
F.Schmid / CNC 236162.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu:** Kotta-
gudi, 10°5'2"N 77°14'10"E, 23.i.1962, F.
Schmid, CNC236162.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella tridachi*
1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11158 G. 3-dachi.

tritiya Schmid 1968c, Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Ninghti 30-VII-1960
F.Schmid / CNC 236153.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Ninghti, 24°53'26.01"N 94°24'47.01"E, 30.vii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236153.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella tritiya* 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11149 G. tritiya.

Comments: Description incorrectly listed month of collection as June.

tririmchi* Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Bhairabkunda 18-21-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236181.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** Udalguri District, Bhairabkunda, 26°53'2"N 92°6'51"E, 18-21.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 236181.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella tririmchi* [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11176 G. 3-trimchi.

trivimchi* Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam Dhekiajuli 28-II-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236172.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Assam:** Dhekiajuli, 26°41'55"N 92°29'7"E, 28.ii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC236172.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella trivimchi* [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11169 G. 3-vimchi.

vasoudeva* Schmid 1960, *Chimarra

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Frontier Province] Balakot 23-VI-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 236210.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa:** Balakot, 34°32'22"N 73°21'2.01"E, 23.vi.1953, F. Schmid, CNC236210.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Chimarra vasoudeva* 1957 F.Schmid / [CNC Type No. 12337] *Chimarra vasoudeva* HOLOTYPE.

vimchi* Schmid 1968c, *Gunungiella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Dirang Dzong 19-VII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236170.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Derangzong, 27°20'31"N 92°16'22"E, 19.vii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC236170.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gunungiella vimchi* [sic] 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11165 G. vimchi.

PHRYGANEIDAE

***bradorata* (Milne 1931), *Agrypnia* [*Prophryganea*]**

Valid name: *Agrypnia colorata* Hagen 1873

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Bradore Bay, Que. 12.VII.1930 W.J.Brown / SLIDE No.Ph.6a / CNC 279905.

Interpretive data: **CANADA. Quebec:** Bradore Bay, 51°27'59.76"N 57°13'59.88"W, 12.vii.1930, W.J. Brown, CNC279905.

Determination: HOLO-TYPE *Prophryganea bradorata* Milne No.3344.

***deflata* (Milne 1931), *Agrypnia* [*Prophryganea*]**

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Indian Head, Sask. 9.VII.1925. J.J.de Gryse / SLIDE No.Ph.3 / CNC 279903.

Interpretive data: **CANADA. Saskatchewan:** Indian Head, 50°32'0"N 103°40'0"W, 9.vii.1925, J.J. de Gryse, CNC279903.

Determination: HOLO-TYPE *Prophryganea deflata* Milne No.3342.

***macdunnoughi* (Milne 1931), *Agrypnia* [*Prophryganea*]**

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Nordegg, Alta. 28 VI 1921 J.McDunnough / SLIDE No.Ph.5 / CNC 279904.

Interpretive data: **CANADA. Alberta:** Nordegg, 52°28'14.16"N 116°4'31.08"W, 28.vi.1921, J. McDunnough, CNC279904.

Determination: HOLO-TYPE *Prophryganea macdunnoughi* Milne No.3343.

POLYCENTROPODIDAE

almanzor* Schmid 1952, *Polycentropus

Valid name: *Polycentropus intricatus* Morton 1910

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Espagne (Av.) Val de Gredos 15-23-VII-1950 F. Schmid / 9V / CNC 280162.

Interpretive data: **SPAIN**. **Ávila**: Val de Gredos, 15-23.vii.1950, F. Schmid, CNC280162.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Polycentropus almanzor* 1951 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12480 *Polycentropus almanzor* HOLOTYPE.

gracilligonopoda* Botoșăneanu 1960, *Plectrocnemia

Valid name: *Plectrocnemia brevis* McLachlan 1871 holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Macédoine Perister 12-16-VIII-1955 F.Schmid / CNC 758897.

Interpretive data: **MACEDONIA**. Baba Mountain, 41°0'12"N 21°11'3"E, 12-16.viii.1955, F. Schmid, CNC758897.

Determination: *Plectrocnemia* ssp. *brevis* McL. *gracilligonopoda* Bots. ♂. / Holotype ♂ / CNC No. 12179 *Plectrocnemia gracilligonopoda* HOLOTYPE.

kalachorum* Schmid 1961, *Plectrocnemia

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pakistan (N.W.F.P.) Rumbur [sic] 19-XI-1954 F.Schmid / CNC 280141.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN**. **Khyber Pakhtunkhwa**: Kalash Valleys, Rambur Valley, Grum, 35°46'29.76"N 71°41'36.38"E, 19.xi.1954, F. Schmid, CNC280141.

Determination: Holotype ♂ *Plectrocnemia kalachorum* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12339 *Plectrocnemia kalachorum* HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Published date of collection 16.xi.1954.

mazdacus* Schmid 1959b, *Polycentropus

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Iran (Ost.1) Ramsar 2-X-1956 F.Schmid / CNC 280166.

Interpretive data: **IRAN**. **Mazandaran**: Ramsar, 36°55'37"N 50°38'37"E, 2.x.1956, F. Schmid, CNC280166.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Polycentropus mazdacus* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12282 *Polycentropus mazdacus* HOLOTYPE.

nagayamai* Schmid 1964a, *Plectrocnemia

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Nagayama Prov Ishikari [corresponds to portions of present-day Ishikari, Sorachi and Kamikawa Subprefectures] 1-VIII-1935 S.KUWAYAMA / CNC 280145.

Interpretive data: **JAPAN**. Hokkaido, Nagayama, 1.viii.1935, S. Kuwayama, CNC280145.

Determination: Holotype ♂ *Plectrocnemia nagayamai* 1963 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12222 *Plectrocnemia nagayamai* HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Locality possibly corresponds to Nagayamacho (43°49'32"N, 142°27'40"E), Asahikawa, Kamikawa Subprefecture.

palmitus* Flint 1967, *Polycentropus

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: 8 mi.W.El Palmito, Sin.MEX.VII.19.64 H.F.Howden / CNC 236459.

Interpretive data: **MEXICO**. **Sinaloa**: 12.9 km W El Palmito, 23°33'45.26"N 105°57'40.85"W, 19.vii.1964, H.F. Howden, CNC236459.

Determination: Holotype ♂ *Polycentropus palmitus* Flint. CNC 19855 / HOLOTYPE ♂ *Polycentropus palmitus* Flint.

schmidi* Novák & Botoșăneanu 1965, *Polycentropus

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Vrátna Dr.Pazsiczky / CNC 280171.

Interpretive data: **SLOVAKIA**. Vrátna, 49°12'31"N 19°2'32"E, vii.1919, Dr. Pazsiczky, CNC280171.

Determination: *Polycentropus schmidi* Nov. & Bots. / Holotype ♂ / CNCNo. 12180 *Polycentropus schmidi* HOLOTYPE.

sourya* Schmid 1960, *Polyplectropus

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Frontier Province] Balakot 16-X-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 280172.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN**. **Khyber Pakhtunkhwa**: Balakot, 34°32'22"N 73°21'2.01"E, 16.x.1953, F. Schmid, CNC280172.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Polyplectropus sourya* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12338 *Polycentropus sourya* HOLOTYPE.

tochimotoi Schmid 1964a, *Plectrocnemia*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Japon Tochimoto 19-VII-1955 R. Ishikawa / CNC 280148.

Interpretive data: **JAPAN. Shikoku**: Kōchi Prefecture, Tochimoto, 33°39'44.33"N 133°52'36.10"E, 19.vii.1955, R. Ishikawa, CNC 280148.

Determination: Holotype ♂ *Plectrocnemia tochimotoi* 1963 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12221 *Plectrocnemia toshimotoi* HOLOTYPE.

varouna Schmid 1961, *Plectrocnemia*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Frontier Province] Kawai [sic] 24-VI-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 280150.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa**: Kiwai, 34°37'59.01"N 73°26'39"E, 24.vi.1953, F. Schmid, CNC280150.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Plectrocnemia varouna* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12340 *Plectrocnemia varouna* HOLOTYPE.

PSYCHOMYIIDAE

achtachastra Schmid 1972, *Tinodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Sikkim Chongpung 27-IX-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236495.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Chongpung, 27°19'35"N 88°14'10"E, 27.ix.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236495.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes achtachastra* 1970 F. Schmid / *Tinodes achtachastra* HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11.906.

adhrichta Schmid 1972, *Tinodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Bhairabkunda 3-4, 7-III-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236496.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: Udalguri District, Bhairabkunda, 26°53'2"N 92°6'51"E, 3-4, 7.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 236496.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes adhrichta* 1970 F. Schmid / *Tinodes adhrichta* HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11.915.

aequispinosus Schmid 1972, *Tinodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Guinée franç. Kindia 1-15-V-1955 F.Schmid / CNC 236497.

Interpretive data: **GUINEA**. Kindia, 10°2'26.01"N 12°51'46"W, 1-15.v.1955, F. Schmid, CNC236497.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes aequispinosa* 1970 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12483 *Tinodes aequispinosa* HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Morse (2017) listed epithet as "*aequispinosus*", with the ending corrected to agree with the gender of the genus.

akanda Schmid 1972, *Tinodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Mawlang 12-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236498.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: East Khasi Hills District, Mawlang, 25°39'44"N 91°50'30"E, 12.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 236498.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes akanda* 1970 F. Schmid / *Tinodes akanda* HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11.912.

akantaka Schmid 1972, *Tinodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Teri Garhwal Ampata 8-10-IV-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 236499.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Tehri Garhwal District, Ampata, 30°16'6"N 78°22'18"E, 8-10.iv.1958, F. Schmid, CNC236499.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes akantaka* 1970 F. Schmid / *Tinodes akantaka* HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11.914.

akrichalakchmi Schmid 1972, *Eoneureclipsis*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Chingsao 13-VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236478.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Chingsao, 13.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236478.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Eoneureclipsis akrichalakchmi* 1970 F. Schmid / *Eoneureclipsis akrichalakchmi* HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11.900.

alpachastra Schmid 1972, Tinodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Sikkim Rongne 21-VIII-1959 F. Schmid / CNC 236504.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Rongne, 21.viii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236504.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes alpachastra* 1970 F. Schmid / *Tinodes alpachastra* HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11.909.

amadai Schmid 1959b, Tinodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Iran (Ost.3) Baharistan [sic] 20-VIII-1956 F.Schmid / CNC 236502.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. Ardabil:** Baharestan, 38°24'3.60"N 48°43'18.12"E, 20.viii.1956, F. Schmid, CNC236502.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes amadai* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12284 *Tinodes amadai* HOLOTYPE.

analoka Schmid 1972, Tinodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Erumakolli 10-I-1959 F. Schmid / CNC 236501.

Interpretive data: **INDIA.** [likely in either in present day Kerala or Tamil Nadu State], Erumakolli, 10.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC 236501.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes analoka* 1971 F. Schmid / *Tinodes analoka* HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11.911.

anibhrita Schmid 1972, Tinodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (W.B.) Git Dabling [sic] 14-IX-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236503.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. West Bengal:** Git Dabling, 27°3'13"N 88°35'51"E, 14.ix.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236503.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes anibhrita* 1971 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11.935 *Tinodes abibhrita* Schm. 1971.

antequeruela Schmid 1952, Tinodes

Valid name: *Tinodes foedellus* McLachlan 1884

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Espagne (Ma.) Cercedilla 8-VII-1950 F. Schmid / CNC 236489.

Interpretive data: **SPAIN. Madrid:** Cercedilla, 40°44'26.01"N 4°3'25"W, 8.vii.1950, F. Schmid, CNC236489.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes antequeruela* 1951 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12482 *Tinodes antequeruela* HOLOTYPE.

aprakrita Schmid 1972, Tinodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Lushai) [=Mizo Hills] Waiten 8-IX-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236506.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Mizoram:** Vaiten, 24°13'17"N 92°58'32"E, 8.ix.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236506.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes aprakrita* 1970 F. Schmid / *Tinodes aprakrita* HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11.920.

arala Schmid 1972, Tinodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Mawshuid 12-X-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236505.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** United Jaintia and Khasi Hills [now divided into East and West Khasi Hills Districts and East and West Jaintia Hills Districts], Mawshuid, 12.x.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236505.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes arala* 1970 F. Schmid / *Tinodes arala* HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11.910.

arefinae Schmid 1997, Psychomyia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Teri Garhwal Agra 5-6-IV-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 236318.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhnad:** Tehri Garhwal District, Agra, 5-6.iv.1958, F. Schmid, CNC236318.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia arefinae* 1996 F. Schmid.

Comments: Locality possibly Agrakhal (30° 12'50"N 78°19'41"E).

armata Schmid 1964a, Psychomyia

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Japan Sendai 22-V-1952 K. Nagayama / CNC 236355.

Interpretive data: **JAPAN.** Miyagi Prefecture, Sendai, 38°16'12"N 140°52'1"E, 22.v.1952, K. Nagayama, CNC236355.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia armata* 1963 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12220 *Psychomyia armata* HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Description stated locality as "Sen-sai". Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

armitagei Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Laitryngew 13-X-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236363.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** East Khasi Hills District, Laitryngew, 25°19'26"N 91°43'55"E, 13.x.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 236363.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia armitagei* 1996 F. Schmid.

Comments: CNC Type No. listed as "22259" in description.

asangha Schmid 1961, *Tinodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pakistan (Penjab) Murree 8-VI-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 236507.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Punjab:** Murree, 33°54'31"N 73°23'35.01"E, 8.vi.1953, F. Schmid, CNC236507.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes asangha* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 121343 [sic – actually 12343] *Tinodes asangha* HOLOTYPE.

asvagosha Schmid 1961, *Psychomyia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Frontier Province] Balakot 16-X-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 236357.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa:** Balakot, 34°32'22"N 73°21'2.01"E, 16.x.1953, F. Schmid, CNC236357.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia asvagosha* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12349 *Psychomyia asvagosha* HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Year of collection erroneously published as 1954.

atichastra Schmid 1972, *Tinodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Zomphuk 11-IV-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236508.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Zomphuk, 11.iv.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236508.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes atichastra* 1970 F. Schmid / *Tinodes atichastra* HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11.904.

botosaneanui Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Chingsao 14-VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236338.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Chingsao, 14.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236338.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia botosaneanui* 1996 F. Schmid.

cheitani Schmid 1959b, *Tinodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Iran (Ost.1) Waliabad [sic] 16-IX-1956 F.Schmid / CNC 236510.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. Mazandaran:** Valiabad, 36°15'7.07"N 51°18'5.81"E, 16.ix.1956, F. Schmid, CNC236510.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes cheitani* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12289 *Tinodes cheitani* HOLOTYPE.

chrinidhara Schmid 1972, *Tinodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Lungdur 16-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236511.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Lungdur, 27°3'28"N 92°8'41"E, 16.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 236511.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes chrinidhara* 1970 F. Schmid / *Tinodes chrinidhara* HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11.922.

curriei Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Perumalmai 5-XII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236349.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu:** Perumal Malai, 10°15'57"N 77°32'42"E, 5.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC236349.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia curriei*
1996 F. Schmid.

Comments: Description listed dates of collection
as December 5-7.

denisi Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Vangai Chungpao 21-
V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236365.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Vangai
Chungpao, 24°45'23"N 93°10'40"E, 21.v.
1960, F. Schmid, CNC236365.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia denisi*
1996 F. Schmid.

Comments: CNC Type No. 22261, but listed as
"22262" in description.

dhumravarna Schmid 1972, *Lype*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Marou 14-VIII-1960
F.Schmid / CNC 236542.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Marou,
24°54'28"N 94°15'0"E, 14.viii.1960, F.
Schmid, CNC236542.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Lype dhumravarna*
1971 F. Schmid / *Lype dhumravarna* HOLO-
TYPE CNCNo. 11.903.

dirghachastra Schmid 1972, *Tinodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Amatulla 24-V-1961
F.Schmid / CNC 236513.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
West Kameng District, Amatulla, 26°55'47"N
92°7'18"E, 24.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC
236513.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes dirghachastra*
1970 F. Schmid / *Tinodes dirghachastra* HO-
LOTYPE CNCNo. 11.907.

flinti Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Kerala) Kalpatti 13-I-1962
F.Schmid / CNC 236348.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala**: Kalpatti,
13.i.1962, F. Schmid, CNC236348.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia flinti*
1996 F. Schmid.

fratakara Schmid 1959b, *Tinodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Iran (Ost.1) Javardi 7-X-1956
F.Schmid / CNC 236514.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. Mazandaran**: Javaher
deh, 36°51'12.68"N 50°28'29.14"E, 7.x.1956,
F. Schmid, CNC236514.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes fratakara*
1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12287 *Tinodes fra-*
takara HOLOTYPE.

galli Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Khasi and
Jaintia Hills] Thangrain 22-IV-1960 F.Schmid
/ CNC 236362.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: Jaintia
Hills District, Thangrain, 25°34'48"N 92°26'
22"E, 22.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236362.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia galli*
1996 F. Schmid.

Comments: CNC Type No. 22257, but listed as
"22258" in description.

ghobarama Schmid 1961, *Tinodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Cachen.et Jam. Kharigam 18-V-1954
F.Schmid / CNC 236515.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu &
Kashmir**: Kharigam, 34°47'0"N 74°9'0"E, 18.
v.1954, F. Schmid, CNC236515.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes ghobarama*
1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12344 *Tinodes*
ghobarama HOLOTYPE.

giboni Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Malbidu 18-I-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 236345.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka**: Malbidu,
18.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236345.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia giboni*
1996 F. Schmid / [CNC Type No. 22244]

gonzalezi Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Bhairabkunda 5-6-
III-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236370.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** Udalguri District, Bhairabkunda, 26°53'2"N 92°6'51"E, 5-6.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 236370.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia gonzalezi* 1996 F. Schmid.

Comments: CNC Type No. 22264, but listed as "22265" in description.

higleri* Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Teri Garhwal Ampata 8-10-IV-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 236337.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Tehri Garhwal District, Ampata, 30°16'6"N 78°22'18"E, 8-10.iv.1958, F. Schmid, CNC236337.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia higleri* 1996 F. Schmid / [CNC Type No. 22236]

holzenthali* Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Borghat 19-XII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236315.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia Hills District, Borghat, 25°9'36"N 92°15'36"E, 19.xii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236315.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia holzenthali* 1996 F. Schmid / [CNC Type No. 22223]

Comments: Description incorrectly listed date of collection as the 10th.

inaequispinosus* Schmid 1972, *Tinodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Guinée Franc. Souapiti 15-20-V-1955 F.Schmid / CNC 236534.

Interpretive data: **GUINEA.** Souapiti, 10°25'26.76"N 13°15'16.20"W, 15-20.v.1955, F. Schmid, CNC236534.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes inaequispinosa* 1970 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12484 *Tinodes inaequispinosa* HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Morse (2017) listed epithet as "*inaequispinosus*", with the ending corrected to agree with the gender of the genus.

itoae* Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Barato 24-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236366.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia Hills District, Barato, 25°36'21"N 92°27'5"E, 24.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236366.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia itoae* 1996 F. Schmid.

Comments: CNC Type No. 22260, but listed as "22261" in description.

ivanovi* Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Kottagudi 23-I-1962 F.Schmid / CNC 236346.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu:** Kottagudi, 10°5'2"N 77°14'10"E, 23.i.1962, F. Schmid, CNC236346.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia ivanovi* 1996 F. Schmid / [CNC Type No. 22245].

kanerquorum* Schmid 1961, *Tinodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Frontier Province] Mahandri 26-VI-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 236516.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa:** Mahandri, 34°41'40"N 73°34'27"E, 26.vi.1953, F. Schmid, CNC236516.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes kanerquorum* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12342 *Tinodes kanerquorum* HOLOTYPE.

kumanskii* Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Sihai Khulen [sic] 25-VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236336.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Sihai Khulen, 25°10'10"N 94°29'13"E, 25.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236336.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia kumanski* [sic] 1996 F. Schmid / [CNC Type No. 22235].

kumari* Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Simra 1-2-X-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 236319.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Pauri

- Garhwal District, Simra, 1-2.x.1958, F. Schmid, CNC236319.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia kumari* 1996 F. Schmid / [CNC Type No. 22224].
- kuranishi* Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia***
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Mynso 20-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236360.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: Jaintia Hills District, Mynso, 25°31'27"N 92°17'56"E, 20.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236360.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia kuranishii* [sic] 1996 F. Schmid.
Comments: Description incorrectly listed month of collection as February. CNC Type No. 22255, but listed as "22256" in description.
- lavidhara* Schmid 1972, *Tinodes***
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Chingsao 13-VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236517.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Chingsao, 13.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236517.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes lavidhara* 1970 F. Schmid / *Tinodes lavidhara* HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11.913.
- levanidovae* Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia***
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Dirang Dzong 24-IV-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236322.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Derangzong, 27°20'31"N 92°16'22"E, 24.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC236322.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia levanidovae* 1996 F. Schmid / [CNC Type No. 22227].
- lii* Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia***
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (U.D.M.N.C.H.) [=United district of Mikir Hills and North Cachar] Umbaso 26-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236372.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Assam**: Karbi Anglong District, Umbaso, 25°43'48"N 92°31'34"E, 26.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236372.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia lii* 1996 F. Schmid / [CNC Type No. 22265].
- magadha* Schmid 1961, *Paduniella***
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Cachim. et Jam. Muzaffarabad 16-21-VI-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 236545.
Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu & Kashmir**: Muzaffarabad, 34°21'35"N 73°28'17"E, 16-21.vi.1953, F. Schmid, CNC236545.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Paduniella magadha* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12351 *Paduniella magadha* HOLOTYPE.
- mahadenna* Schmid 1961, *Psychomyia***
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Cachim. et Jam. Gilgit 9-27.VII.1954 F.Schmid / CNC 236330.
Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu & Kashmir**: Gilgit, 35°55'15"N 74°18'30"E, 9-27.vii.1954, F. Schmid, CNC236330.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia mahadenna* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12347 *Psychomyia mahadenna* HOLOTYPE.
- maharaksa* Schmid 1961, *Psychomyia***
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Pakistan (Penjab) Hassan Abdal 27-XII-1954 F.Schmid / CNC 236371.
Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Punjab**: Hassan Abdal, 33°49'10"N 72°41'21"E, 27.xii.1954, F. Schmid, CNC236371.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia maharaksa* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12348 *Psychomyia maharaksa* HOLOTYPE.
- mahayinna* (Schmid 1961), *Metatype* [*Psychomyia*]**
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Pakistan (Penjab) Hassan Abdal 27-XII-1954 F.Schmid / CNC 236316.
Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Punjab**: Hassan Abdal, 33°49'10"N 72°41'21"E, 27.xii.1954, F. Schmid, CNC236316.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia mahayinna* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12346 *Psychomyia mahayinna* HOLOTYPE.

malickyi Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Teri Garhwal Gawana 22-24-V-1958
F.Schmid / CNC 236339.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Tehri
Garhwal District, Gawana, 22-24.v.1958, F.
Schmid, CNC236339.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia malickyi*
1996 F. Schmid / [CNC Type No. 22237].

matangana Schmid 1961, *Tinodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Fron-
tier Province] Mahandri 26-VI-1953 F.Schmid
/ CNC 236518.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakh-
tunkhwa**: Mahandri, 34°41'40"N 73°34'27"E,
26.vi.1953, F. Schmid, CNC236518.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes matangana*
1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12345 *Tinodes ma-
tangana* HOLOTYPE.

maurya Schmid 1961, *Paduniella*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Fron-
tier Province] Balakot 23-VI-1953 F.Schmid /
CNC 236547.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakh-
tunkhwa**: Balakot, 34°32'22"N 73°21'2.01"E,
23.vi.1953, F. Schmid, CNC236547.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Paduniella maurya*
1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12352 *Paduniella*
maurya HOLOTYPE.

meysi Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Balamore 3-4-I-1962
F.Schmid / CNC 236352.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Madras** [likely in either
present day Kerala or Tamil Nadu State],
Balamore, 3-4.i.1962, F. Schmid, CNC236352.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia meysi*
1996 F. Schmid / [CNC Type No. 22249].

Comments: Description listed date of collection as
the 4th.

monicae Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Foothills 25-II-1961
F.Schmid / CNC 236367.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:

Kameng Frontier Division [now divided into
the districts of Tawang, East Kameng and
West Kameng], Foothills, 25.ii.1961, F.
Schmid, CNC236367.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia monicae*
1996 F. Schmid.

Comments: CNC Type No. 22262, but listed as
"22263" in description.

moretti Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Sathuparai [sic] 22-I-
1962 F.Schmid / CNC 236342.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu**: Sothu-
parai, 10°7'50.49"N 77°27'49.80"E, 22.i.1962,
F. Schmid, CNC236342.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia moretti*
1996 F. Schmid / [CNC Type No. 22241].

morsei Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Kerala) Vellala Mudi 15-XII-
1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236344.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala**: Vellala Mudi,
15.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC236344.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia morsei*
1996 F. Schmid / [CNC Type No. 22243].

natichastra Schmid 1972, *Tinodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (W.B.) Bara Hata 22-III-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 236521.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. West Bengal**: Bara
Hata, 27°4'53.84"N 88°6'19.38"E, 22.iii.1959,
F. Schmid, CNC236521.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes natichastra*
1970 F. Schmid / *Tinodes natichastra* HOLO-
TYPE CNCNo. 11.905.

neboissi Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia*

holotype[?] (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (C.) [=Cachar District]
Bandarkhal 9-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC
236358.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Assam**: Cachar Dis-
trict, Bandarkhal, 25°3'30"N 92°48'4"E,
9.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236358.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia neboissi* 1996 F. Schmid.

Comments: The description listed holotype data as “Manipour, Bongba Khulen, 28.VII.1960”. One dissected male paratype in the CNC was collected at this event, as were 6 other non-type specimens. The identity of the type should be considered tentative and requires verification. CNC Type No. 22253, but listed as “22254” in description.

nimmoi* Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Nongjngi 1-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236364.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: West Jaintia Hills District, Nongjngi, 25°32'32"N 92°16'20"E, 1.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 236364.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia nimmoi* 1996 F. Schmid.

Comments: CNC Type No. 22259, but listed as “22260” in description.

nogradiae* Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Talaiyar Muduvakkudi 18-XII-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 236350.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala**: Talaiyar Muduvakkudi, 10°11'46"N 77°7'32.01"E, 18. xii.1958, F. Schmid, CNC236350.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia nogradiae* 1996 F. Schmid.

Comments: Description incorrectly listed year of collection as 1959.

ouudara* Schmid 1961, *Paduniella

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pakistan (Penjab) Hassan Abdal 27-XII-1954 F.Schmid / CNC 236548.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Punjab**: Hassan Abdal, 33°49'10"N 72°41'21"E, 27.xii.1954, F. Schmid, CNC236548.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Paduniella ouudara* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12350 *Paduniella ouudara* HOLOTYPE.

parsnai* Schmid 1959b, *Tinodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Iran (Ost.2) Zirab 23-V-1956 F.Schmid / CNC 236522.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. Mazandaran**: Zirab, 36°10'40"N 52°58'24"E, 23.v.1956, F. Schmid, CNC236522.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes parsnai* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12285 *Tinodes parsnai* HOLOTYPE.

prisatkayukta* Schmid 1972, *Tinodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Tangkhul Hungdung 18-VIII-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236523.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Tangkhul Hungdung, 25°4'29.28"N 94°13'51.96"E, 18. viii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236523.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes prisatkayukta* 1970 F. Schmid / *Tinodes prisatkayukta* HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11.919.

prithulavi* Schmid 1972, *Tinodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Kumaon) Loharket [sic] 19-IX-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 236524.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Bageshwar District, Loharket, 30°2'48"N 79°57'35"E, 19.ix.1958, F. Schmid, CNC236524.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes prithulavi* 1970 F. Schmid / *Tinodes prithulavi* HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11.908.

pseudorostocki* Botoșăneanu 1960, *Tinodes

Valid name: *Tinodes unidentatus* Klapalek 1894

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Interpretive data: **YUGOSLAVIA**. Perister [=Baba Mountain], 41°0'12"N 21°11'3"E, 12-16. viii.1955, F. Schmid, CNC481655.

Comments: Specimen lost – unique identifier added to unit tray for eventual addition to specimen.

reshi* Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Mysore) Malbidu 18-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236343.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka:** Malbidu, 18.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236343.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia reshi* 1996 F. Schmid / [CNC Type No. 22242].

schefterae* Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Mangu Chatti 20-V-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 236323.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Pauri Garhwal District, Mangu Chatti, 20.v.1958, F. Schmid, CNC236323.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia schefterae* 1996 F. Schmid / [CNC Type No. 22229].

scottae* Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Sikkim Yugang [sic] 14-V-1959 F. Schmid / CNC 236321.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Yuigang, 27°37'48"N 88°37'2"E, 14.v.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236321.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia scottae* 1996 F. Schmid / [CNC Type No. 22228].

spurisi* Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (C.) [=Cachar District] Bandarkhal 9-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236368.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Assam:** Cachar District, Bandarkhal, 25°3'30"N 92°48'4"E, 9.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236368.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia spurisi* 1996 F. Schmid.

Comments: CNC Type No. 22263, but listed as "22264" in description.

suni* Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Amatulla 9-III-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236334.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Amatulla, 26°55'47"N 92°7'18"E, 9.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC236334.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia suni* 1996 F. Schmid / [CNC Type No. 22234].

Comments: The type collection event is incor-

rectly listed in the description as "Kameng Frontier Division, Ankaling, 12.III.1961". While this does represent a collection event in Schmid's field notes, no specimens of *P. suni* from this event can be located.

sykorai* Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Kodaikanal 6-XII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236347.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu:** Kodaikanal, 10°14'21"N 77°29'23"E, 6.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC236347.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Ps. sykorai* 1996 F. Schmid / [CNC Type No. 22246].

tiani* Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Barato 24-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236341.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia Hills District, Barato, 25°36'21"N 92°27'5"E, 24.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236341.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia tiani* 1996 F. Schmid / [CNC Type No. 22240].

tichtrya* Schmid 1959b, *Tinodes

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Iran (Ost.3) Meyur 23-VIII-1956 F.Schmid / CNC 236528.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. Ardabil:** Moeil, 38°17'44.60"N 47°42'58.63"E, 23.viii.1956, F. Schmid, CNC236528.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes tichtrya* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12288 *Tinodes tichtrya* HOLOTYPE.

tobiasi* Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (W.B.) Lingsoka 10-IX-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236332.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. West Bengal:** Lingsoka, 27°8'59.92"N 88°40'22.25"E, 10.ix.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236332.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia tobiasi* 1996 F. Schmid / [CNC Type No. 22231].

Comments: Description listed collection date as

the 9th, during which time Schmid was also at that locality.

tomaszewskii Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Meppadi 9-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236351.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala:** Meppadi, 11°33'17"N 76°8'7"E, 9.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236351.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia tomaszewskii* 1996 F. Schmid / [CNC Type No. 22252].

unzickeri Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Khaorang 28-VIII-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236333.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Khaorang, 28.viii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236333.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia unzickeri* 1996 F. Schmid / [CNC Type No. 22233].

utchringita Schmid 1972, *Tinodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Borghat 19-XII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236530.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia Hills District, Borghat, 25°9'36"N 92°15'36"E, 19.xii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236530.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes utchringita* 1970 F. Schmid / *Tinodes utchringita* HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11.918.

utchunalinga Schmid 1972, *Tinodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Kumaon) Chhana 22-IX-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 236531.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Almora District, Chhana, 22.ix.1958, F. Schmid, CNC 236531.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes utchunalinga* 1970 F. Schmid / *Tinodes utchunalinga* HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11.917.

Comments: Description listed Pauri Garhwal District as the collection locality.

vadichayudha Schmid 1972, *Tinodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Perumalmalai 9-XII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236533.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu:** Perumal Malai, 10°15'57"N 77°32'42"E, 9.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC236533.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes vadichayudha* [sic] 1971 F. Schmid / *Tinodes vadichayudha* HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11.916.

vaillanti Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Lushai) [=Mizo Hills] Thingsat 10-IX-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236353.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Mizoram:** Aizawl District, Thingsat, 24°11'51"N 92°56'27"E, 10. ix.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236353.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia vaillanti* 1996 F. Schmid / [CNC Type No. 22250].

varsikiyja Schmid 1972, *Eoneureclipsis*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Amatulla 17-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236479.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Amatulla, 26°55'47"N 92°7'18"E, 17.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 236479.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Eoneureclipsis varsikiyja* 1971 F. Schmid / *Eoneureclipsis varsikiyja* HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11.901.

verethraghna Schmid 1959b, *Tinodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Iran (Ost.2) Zirab 23-V-1956 F.Schmid / CNC 236532.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. Mazandaran:** Zirab, 36°10'40"N 52°58'24"E, 23.v.1956, F. Schmid, CNC236532.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes verethraghna* 1957 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 12286 *Tinodes verethraghna* HOLOTYPE.

vristchika Schmid 1972, *Tinodes*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Amatulla 11-III-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236526.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Amatulla, 26°55'47"N 92°7'18"E, 11.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 236526.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Tinodes vristchika* 1971 F. Schmid / *Tinodes vritchika* HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11.921.

wangi Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (W.B.) Singtam 11-III-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236340.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Singtam, 27°8'13"N 88°23'34"E, 11.iii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236340.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia wangi* 1996 F. Schmid.

Comments: Description incorrectly listed collection date as the 1st.

wardi Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Luanglong Khunou 28-V-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236335.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Luanglong Khunou, 28.v.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236335.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia wardi* 1996 F. Schmid / [CNC Type No. 22232].

Comments: Description incorrectly listed date of collection as the 26th.

weaveri Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Borghat 19-XII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236361.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia Hills District, Borghat, 25°9'36"N 92°15'36"E, 19.xii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236361.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia weaveri* 1996 F. Schmid.

Comments: CNC Type No. 22256, but listed as "22257" in description.

wellsae Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Kerala) [sic] Panniyar 24-I-1962 F.Schmid / CNC 236325.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala:** Panniyar, 9°56'8.01"N 77°6'31"E, 24.i.1962, F. Schmid, CNC236325.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia wellsae* 1996 F. Schmid.

wigginsii Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Umsawmat 5-X-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236359.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** East Khasi Hills District, Umsawmat, 25°22'7"N 91°40'9"E, 5.x.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236359.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia wigginsii* 1996 F. Schmid.

Comments: CNC Type No. 22254, but listed as "22255" in description.

yangae Schmid 1997, *Psychomyia*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Mawkhap 18-III-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236320.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** East Khasi Hills District, Mawkhap, 25°23'17.01"N 91°54'0"E, 18.iii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236320.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Psychomyia yangae* 1996 F. Schmid / [CNC Type No. 22226].

PTILOCOLEPIDAE

atiloma Schmid 1991a, *Ptilocolepus*

holotype (1 male, pinned: point)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Mawpran 4-7-II-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 235949.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** East Khasi Hills District, Mawpran Nonglyndiang, 25°17'28"N 91°57'26"E, 4-7.ii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC235949.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Ptilocolepus atiloma* 1971 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Ptilocolepus atiloma* CNC No. 21234.

RHYACOPHILIDAE

amitabha Schmid 1966 [In: Schmid & Botoșăneanu (1966)], *Himalopsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Tangu 19-VI-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 235668.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Thangu, 27°53'33"N 88°32'13"E, 19.vi.1959, F. Schmid, CNC235668.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Himalopsyche amitabha* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11417 Him. amitabha.

angden Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Chachu 17-V-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 91910.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Chachu, 17.v. 1959, F. Schmid, CNC91910.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila angden* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11309 Rh. angden.

angnorbui Schmid 1963a, *Himalopsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned) (Figs 12, 13)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Binaik Chatti 16-VI-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 235669.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Pauri Garhwal District, Binaik Chatti, 16.vi.1958, F. Schmid, CNC235669.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Himalopsyche angnorbui* 1963 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11425 Him. angnorbui.

Comments: The collection date of 1-2.vii.1958 in the description applies only to the allotype.

assamensis Oláh & Kiss 2018, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Ankaling 12-III-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 758977.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Assam:** West Kameng District, Ankalin, 27°1'30"N 92°8'37"E, 12. iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC758977.

Determination: paratype ♂ *Rhyacophila chungse* 1965 F. Schmid / *Rhyacophila assamensis* sp. n. Holotype.

aureomaculata Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Shergaon 8-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC91905.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Shergaon, 27°6'18"N 92°16'20"E, 8.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC91905.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila aureomaculata* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11310 Rh. aureomaculata.

aureostigma Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (W.B.) Dilpa 21-III-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 91904.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. West Bengal:** Dilpa, 21.iii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC91904.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila aureostigma* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11311 Rh. aureostigma.

autumnalis Nimmo 1977, *Rhyacophila*

Valid name: *Rhyacophila potteri* Denning & Schmid 1971

holotype (1 male, ethyl alcohol)

Verbatim: Rowe Bk, 6350', Wat.Nat. Pk, Alberta.12/9/75. D.B.Donald / CNC 165668.

Interpretive data: **CANADA. Alberta:** Waterton Lakes National Park, Rowe Lake, 49°3'9"N 114°3'27"W, 1935m, 12.ix.1975, D.B. Donald, CNC165668.

Determination: RHYACOPHILA AUTUMNALIS Nimmo HOLOTYPE ♂ CNC No. 15162 TRICHOPTERA: RHYACOPHILIDAE / = *Rhyacophila potteri*, det. J. Giersch 2002.

Comments: Right-side wings on slide.

bhagirathi Schmid 1963a, *Himalopsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Moussa Pani 21-VI-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 235670.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Pauri Garhwal District, Moussa Pani, 21.vi.1958, F. Schmid, CNC235670.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Himalopsyche bhagirathi* 1963 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11418 Him. bhagirathi.

bhotia Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Tehri Garhwal Dobalgaon [sic] 14-IV-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 91713.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Tehri Garhwal District, Dobhal Gaon, 30°15'45"N 78°28'6"E, 14.iv.1958, F. Schmid, CNC91713.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila bhotia* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11210 Rh. bhotia.

bhuchanadhara* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Lifakpo 15-III-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 235636.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Liphakpu, 27°47'N 92°7'26"E, 15.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 235636.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila bhuchanadhara* [sic] 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11359 Rh. bhuchanadhara.

bonaparti* Schmid 1947, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Suisse-Valais Gd St Bernard 12-VII-1943 F. Schmid / CNC 235656.

Interpretive data: **SWITZERLAND. Valais:** Grand-Saint-Bernard, 45°53'38"N 7°11'13"E, 12.vii.1943, F. Schmid, CNC235656.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila bonaparti* 1950 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11376 Rh. bonaparti.

bosnica* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Apfelbeck Vučjalûka / [blank label] / hirticorn Klapálek / CNC 91832.

Interpretive data: **BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA.** Vučja Luka, 43°55'0"N 18°31'0"E, Apfelbeck, CNC91832.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila bosnica* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11258 Rh. bosnica.

philopotamoides centralis* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

Valid name: *Rhyacophila philopotamoides* McLachlan 1879

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Suisse-Vaud Mèbre 3-VI-1944 F.Schmid / CNC91776.

Interpretive data: **SWITZERLAND. Vaud:** Plateau Suisse, Mèbre, 46°34'24"N 6°37'19"E, 3.vi.1944, F. Schmid, CNC91776.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rh. philopotamoides centralis* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11249 Rh. ph. centralis.

chakungpa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Rapham 2-IV-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 91848.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Rapham, 2.iv.1959, F. Schmid, CNC91848.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila chakungpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11259 Rh. chakungpa.

chamolungpa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Lifakpo 15-III-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 91893.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Liphakpu, 27°47'N 92°7'26"E, 15.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC91893.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila chamolungpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11300 Rh. chamolungpa.

chandragoupta* Schmid 1959a, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pakistan (NWFP) [=North-West Frontier Province] Kaghan 27-29-VI-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 91838.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa:** Kaghan, 34°46'40"N 73°31'32.01"E, 27-29.vi.1953, F. Schmid, CNC 91838.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila chandragoupta* 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11257 Rh. chandragoupta.

chandzo* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Jhum La 1-2-VI-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 91769.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** Kameng Frontier Division [now divided into the districts of Tawang, East Kameng and

- West Kameng], Jhum La, 1-2.vi.1961, F. Schmid, CNC91769.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila chandzo* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11242 Rh. chandzo.
- changpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Sikkim Bakkim 12-IV-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 235640.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Bakkim, 12. iv.1959, F. Schmid, CNC235640.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila changpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11364 Rh. changpa.
- chayulpa chayulpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Sikkim Lingdok 7-V-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 91919.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Lingdok, 27° 23'12.24"N 88°34'21.26"E, 7.v.1959, F. Schmid, CNC91919.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyac. chayulpa chayulpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11326 Rh. ch. chayulpa.
- chematangpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Sikkim Chamiteng 24-VIII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 91872.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Chamiteng, 24.viii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC91872.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila chematangpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11283 Rh. chematangpa.
Comments: Type locality listed as "Chematang" in description.
- chembo Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Jhum La 24-25-III-1961 F. Schmid / CNC 91908.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: Kameng Frontier Division [now divided into the districts of Tawang, East Kameng and West Kameng], Jhum La, 24-25.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC91908.
- Determination*: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila chembo* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11312 Rh. ch. chembo.
- chenmo Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Sirohi Kashong 11-13-VII-1960 F. Schmid / CNC91761.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Sirohi Kashong, 25°6'23.19"N 94°27'28.51"E, 11-13. vii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC91761.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila chenmo* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11238 Rh. chenmo.
- chimdoro Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Bomdi La [sic] 26-30-IV-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 91873.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Bomdila, 27°15'51"N 92°24'58"E, 26-30.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 91873.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila chimdro* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11284 Rh. chimdro.
- chomoyuma Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Hkayam Boum 20-23-VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 91861.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Hkayam Boum, 20-23.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC91861.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila chomoyuma* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11260 Rh. chomoyuma.
- chugalungpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Sikkim Manu 10-V-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 91875.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Manu, 27° 31'2"N 88°34'58"E, 10.v.1959, F. Schmid, CNC91875.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila chugalungpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11285 Rh. chugalungpa.

chulukpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (W.B.) Dilpa 20-III-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 235586.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. West Bengal**: Dilpa,
20.iii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC235586.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyac. chulukpa* 1966
F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11327 Rh.
chulukpa.

chumikpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Nyukmadong [sic]
19-20-IV-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 91914.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
West Kameng District, Nyukmadung, 27°25'
1"N 92°7'57"E, 19-20.iv.1961, F. Schmid,
CNC91914.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila chum-*
ikpa 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11314 Rh. chumikpa.

chungse Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Chingsao 13-VI-1960
F.Schmid / CNC 91760.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Chingsao,
13.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC91760.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila chungse*
1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11239 Rh. chungse.

churongpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Saran [sic] 17-IX-1958
F. Schmid / CNC 91887.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Pauri
Garhwal District, Sarana, 29°33'17"N 79°34'
13"E, 17.ix.1958, F. Schmid, CNC91887.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila chu-*
rongpa 1966 F. Schmid HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11292 Rh. churongpa.

Comments: Type locality in description includes
"Almora".

colonus Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: U.S.A. Ore. Josephine Co. O'Brien 5-
VI-1965 F.Schmid / CNC 91809.

Interpretive data: **USA. Oregon**: Josephine Co.,
O'Brien, 42°4'8"N 123°43'15"W, 5.vi.1965, F.
Schmid, CNC91809.

Determination: *Rhyacophilus colonus* Schm.
HOLOTYPE ♂ CNCNo. 9345-1966.

crassa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Japon (Fuk.) Wakamatsu 27-VII-1952
K. Nagayama / CNC 91772.

Interpretive data: **JAPAN. Fukushima Prefecture**,
Aizuwakamatsu, 37°29'40"N 139°55'48"E, 27.
vii.1952, K. Nagayama, CNC91772.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila crassa*
1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11241 Rh. crassa.

curtior Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Japon (Honshu) Karuizawa 28-VIII-
1952 R. Ishikawa / CNC 235628.

Interpretive data: **JAPAN. Honshu**: Chūbu, Na-
gano Prefecture, Karuizawa, 36°20'54.50"N
138°35'49.30"E, 28.viii.1952, R. Ishikawa,
CNC235628.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila curtior*
1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11357 Rh. curtior.

dafla Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Dirang Dzung 18-
VII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 91921.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
West Kameng District, Derangzong, 27°20'
31"N 92°16'22"E, 18.vii.1961, F. Schmid,
CNC91921.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila dafla*
1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11321 Rh. dafla.

Comments: Description listed date of collection as
9.iv.1961, during which time Schmid was also
at that locality.

dakshi Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (W.B.) Shepi 23-III-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 91913.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. West Bengal:** Shepi, 27°7'38.59"N 88°5'6.30"E, 23.iii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC91913.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila dakshi* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11315 Rh. dakshi.

dgaldanpa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Domkho 11-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 235651.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Domkho, 27°9'55"N 92°13'50.01"E, 11.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 235651.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila dgaldanpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11366 Rh. dgaldanpa.

dikkaravasini* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Gudalur 6-7-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC235597.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu:** Gudalur, 11°30'13"N 76°29'29"E, 6-7.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC235597.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila dikkaravasini* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11335 Rh. dikkaravasini.

dirangpa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Rahung 16-VIII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 235601.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Rahung, 27°18'37"N 92°23'41"E, 16.viii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 235601.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila dirangpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11344 Rh. dirangpa.

dolingpa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Tarangblang 1-I-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 91898.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia

Hills District, Tarangblang, 25°11'17.01"N 92°12'33"E, 1.i.1960, F. Schmid, CNC91898.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila dolingpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11303 Rh. dolingpa.

dolmasampa* Schmid 1963a, *Himalopsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Tangshing 15-IV-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 235679.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Tangshing, 15.iv.1959, F. Schmid, CNC235679.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Himalopsyche dolmasampa* 1963 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11419 H. dolmasampa.

donaldi* Nimmo 1977, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, ethyl alcohol)

Verbatim: Rowe Bk, 6550', Wat.Nat. Pk, Alberta.10/8/75. D.B.Donald / CNC 165670.

Interpretive data: **CANADA. Alberta:** Waterton Lakes National Park, Rowe Lake, 49°3'9"N 114°3'27"W, 1996m, 10.viii.1975, D.B. Donald, CNC165670.

Determination: RHYACOPHILA DONALDI Nimmo HOLOTYPE ♂ CNC No. 15161 TRICHOPTERA: RHYACOPHILIDAE.

Comments: Right-side wings on slide.

dongkyapa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Brukpatarnchen 17-III-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 91725.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** Kameng Frontier Division [now divided into the districts of Tawang, East Kameng and West Kameng], Brukpatarnchen, 17.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC91725.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila dongkyapa* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11211 Rh. dongkyapa.

Comments: Locality possibly Brokpalangchen (27°4'35"N 92°5'59"E).

dongre* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Yugang [sic] 14-V-1959 F. Schmid / CNC 91917.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Yuigang, 27°37'48"N 88°37'2"E, 14.v.1959, F. Schmid, CNC91917.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila dongre* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11324 Rh. dongre.

dorje Schmid 1970b, Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Perumalmalai 3-6-XII-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 91746.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu:** Perumal Malai, 10°15'56.01"N 77°32'42"E, 3-6.xii.1958, F. Schmid, CNC91746.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila dorje* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11223 Rh. dorje.

drokpa drokpa Schmid 1970b, Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Kujjalong 28-30-VI-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 234654.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** Kameng Frontier Division [now divided into the districts of Tawang, East Kameng and West Kameng], Kujjalong, 28-30.vi.1961, F. Schmid, CNC235654.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila drokpa drokpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11367 Rh. drokpa drokpa.

drosampa Schmid 1970b, Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Rumkheng 20-23-III-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 91855.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** United Jaintia and Khasi Hills [now divided into East and West Khasi Hills Districts and East and West Jaintia Hills Districts], Rumkheng, 20-23.iii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC91855.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila drosampa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11263 Rh. drosampa.

drotangpa Schmid 1970b, Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Karponang 23-VIII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 91715.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Karponang, 23.viii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC91715.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila drotangpa* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11212 Rh. drotangpa.

gelukpa Schmid 1970b, Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Gey 18-V-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 235646.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Gey, 18.v.1959, F. Schmid, CNC235646.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila gelukpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11370 Rh. gelukpa.

guadarramica Schmid 1952, Rhyacophila

Valid name: *Rhyacophila meridionalis* Pictet 1865

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Espagne (Seg.) La Granja 23-IX-1950 F. Schmid / CNC 61674.

Interpretive data: **SPAIN. Segovia:** La Granja Parc Nat. 40°53'52"N 4°0'17"W, 23.ix.1950, F. Schmid, CNC91674.

Determination: HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11206 Rh. *guadarramica* / holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila guadarramica* 1950 F. Schmid.

drokpa gurla Schmid 1970b, Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Duldhar 2-VI-1958 F.Schmid.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Pauri Garhwal District, Duldhar, 2.vi.1958, F. Schmid, CNC235652.

Determination: holotype *Rhyacophila drokpa gurla* 1966 F. Schmid.

gyaldzen Schmid 1970b, Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Khasi and Jaintia Hills] Muktapur 11-12-XII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 91742.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia Hills District, Muktapur, 25°9'35"N 92°7'54"E, 11-12.xii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC91742.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila gyaldzen*

- 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11224 Rh. gyalzen.
- gyamo Schmid 1963a, *Himalopsyche***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Sikkim Tangshing 15-IV-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 235667.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Tangshing,
15.iv.1959, F. Schmid, CNC235667.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Himalopsyche gyamo*
1963 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11423 Him. gyamo.
- gyamo Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Sirohi Kashong 6-7-VI-
1960 F. Schmid / CNC 91895.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Siruhi Ka-
shong, 25°6'23.19"N 94°27'28.51"E, 6-7.vi.
1960, F. Schmid, CNC91895.
Determination: HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11301 Rh.
gyamo / holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila gyamo* 1966
F. Schmid.
- gyaspa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Inde (W.B.) Dilpa 21-III-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 235603.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. West Bengal:** Dilpa,
21.iii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC235603.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila gyaspa*
1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11345 Rh. gyaspa.
- gyelbu Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Sirohi Kashong 6-7-VI-
1960 F. Schmid / CNC 91911.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Siruhi Ka-
shong, 25°6'23.19"N 94°27'28.51"E, 6-7.vi.
1960, F. Schmid, CNC91911.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila gyelbu*
1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11316 Rh. gyelbu.
- hierophylax Schmid 1966** [In: Schmid & Boto-
șăneanu (1966)], *Himalopsyche*
holotype (1 male, pinned)
- Verbatim:* Pauri Garhwal Kedarnath 13-15-V-
1958 F.Schmid / CNC 235686.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Pauri
Garhwal District, Kedarnath, 30°44'4"N 79°4'
1"E, 13-15.v.1958, F. Schmid, CNC235686.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Himalopsyche hiero-*
phylax 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE
CNCNo. 11441 Him. hierophylax.
- hydaspica Schmid 1959a, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Cachem.et Jam. Muzaffarabad 16-21-
VI-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 91719.
Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu &**
Kashmir: Muzaffarabad, 34°21'35"N 73°28'
17"E, 16-21.vi.1953, F. Schmid, CNC91719.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila*
hydaspica 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE
CNCNo. 11213 Rh. hydaspica.
- ignorata Schmid 1974, *Rhyacophila***
Valid name: *Rhyacophila brunnea* Banks 1911
holotype (1 female, pinned)
Verbatim: Mt. Washington, N.H Tuckerman Bay
VIII-4-1958 Oliver S.Flint,Jr. / CNC 235618.
Interpretive data: **USA. New Hampshire:** Mt.
Washington, Tuckerman Bay, 44°15'45"N 71°
17'54"W, 4.viii.1958, Oliver S. Flint, Jr.
CNC235618.
Determination: HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 13309
Rhyacophila innorata [sic] Schm.
Comments: Description listed type locality as
"Tuckerman Rav."
- insularis Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: qualicum Falls S. Vancouver Id. 6-
VIII-1951 Richard Guppy / CNC 91789.
Interpretive data: **CANADA. British Columbia:**
Qualicum Falls, South Vancouver Island,
49°17'34"N 124°34'31"W, 6.viii.1951, Ri-
chard Guppy, CNC91789.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila insularis*
1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11251 Rh. insularis.
- jayadurga Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Makurti 1-I-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 235596.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu**: Mukurthi National Park, 11°25'43"N 76°33'37"E, 1.i. 1959, F. Schmid, CNC235596.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila jayadurga* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11336 Rh. jayadurga.

kadampa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Sirohi Kashong 6-7-VI-1960 F. Schmid / CNC 91714.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Siruhi Kashong, 25°6'23.19"N 94°27'28.51"E, 6-7.vi. 1960, F. Schmid, CNC91714.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila kadampa* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11214 Rh. kadampa.

kadaphes* Schmid 1959a, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Cachem. et Jam. Chhantir Gah 5-7-VIII-1954 F.Schmid / CNC 91868.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu & Kashmir**: Chhantir Gah, 5-7.viii.1954, F. Schmid, CNC91868.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila kadaphes* 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11277 Rh. kadaphes.

Comments: Locality a river near Imit, possibly located 36°33'58"N 73°47'45"E.

kadphises* Schmid 1959a, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Cachem. et Jam. Lilam 24-V-1954 F.Schmid / CNC 91867.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu & Kashmir**: Liam, 34°55'6"N 74°26'17"E, 24.v. 1954, F. Schmid, CNC91867.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila kadphises* 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11278 Rh. kadphises.

kagyupa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Rupa 11-VI-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 235589.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Rupa, 27°12'11.01"N 92°23'55"E, 11.vi.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 235589.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila kagyupa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11337 Rh. kagyupa.

kando* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Phutang 1-4-X-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 235632.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Phutang, 27°14'0"N 92°14'0"E, 1-4.x.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 235632.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila kando* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11355 Rh. kando kando.

kangjongpa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Kujjalong 28-30-VI-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 91863.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: Kameng Frontier Division [now divided into the districts of Tawang, East Kameng and West Kameng], Kujjalong, 28-30.vi.1961, F. Schmid, CNC91863.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila kangjongpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11264 Rh. kangjongpa.

kangsampa* Schmid 1966 [In: Schmid & Botoșăneanu (1966)], *Himalopsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Cachemire et Jammu Stenmarg 25-V-1954 F. Schmid / CNC 235674.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu & Kashmir**: Stenmarg, 25.v.1954, F. Schmid, CNC235674.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Himalopsyche kangsampa* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11415 Him. kangsampa.

Comments: Description incorrectly stated year of collection as 1959.

kanichka* Schmid 1959a, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Cachem. et Jam. Lilam 24-V-1954
F. Schmid / CNC 91864.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu & Kashmir**: Liam, 34°55'6"N 74°26'17"E, 24.v.1954, F. Schmid, CNC91864.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila kanichka* 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11279 Rh. kanichka.

karpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Tkentalong 29-31-XII-1959 F. Schmid / CNC 235609.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: United Jaintia and Khasi Hills [now divided into East and West Khasi Hills Districts and East and West Jaintia Hills Districts], Tkentalong, 29-31.xii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC235609.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila karpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11351 Rh. karpa.

kashongpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Sirohi Kashong 6-7-VI-1960 F. Schmid / CNC 91754.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Sirohi Kashong, 25°6'23.19"N 94°27'28.51"E, 6-7.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC91754.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila kashongpa* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11234 Rh. kashongpa.

kawachenpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Domkho 11-V-1961 F. Schmid / CNC 91849.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Domkho, 27°9'55"N 92°13'50.01"E, 11.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC91849.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila kawachenpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11265 Rh. kawachenpa.

kedara Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Kedarnath 13-15-V-1958 F. Schmid / CNC 91866.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Pauri Garhwal District, Kedarnath, 30°44'4"N 79°4'1"E, 13-15.v.1958, F. Schmid, CNC 91866.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila kedara* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11280 Rh. kedara.

khamakhya Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Kodaikanal 6-XII-1961 F. Schmid / CNC 235598.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu**: Kodaikanal, 10°14'21"N 77°29'23"E, 6.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC235598.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyac. khamakhya* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11338 Rh. khamakhya.

khasiorum Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Rumkheng 20-23-III-1960 F. Schmid / CNC 91907.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: United Jaintia and Khasi Hills [now divided into East and West Khasi Hills Districts and East and West Jaintia Hills Districts], Rumkheng, 20-23.iii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC91907.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila khasiorum* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11317 Rh. khasiorum.

Comments: Description incorrectly listed year of collection as 1959.

khimbarpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Jhum La 13-V-1961 F. Schmid / CNC 91902.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: Kameng Frontier Division [now divided into the districts of Tawang, East Kameng and West Kameng], Jhum La, 13.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC91902.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila khimbarpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11318 Rh. khimbarpa.

khiympa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Bakkim 12-IV-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 91865.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Bakkim, 12.iv.1959, F. Schmid, CNC91865.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila khiympa* 1966 F. Schmid HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11281 Rh. khiympa.

kincaidi Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Canada, B.C. Skagit Camp 3-VII-1965 F.Schmid / CNC 91775.

Interpretive data: **CANADA. British Columbia:** Skagit River Camp, 49°7'24.24"N 121°10'30.80"W, 3.vii.1965, F. Schmid, CNC91775.

Determination: *Rhyacophila kincaidi* Schm. HOLOTYPE ♂ CNCNo. 9346-1966.

kiyongpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Kuantun(2300m) 27, 40n. Br. 117,40ö. L. J.Klapperich 4. 3. 1938(Fukien) / CNC 91738.

Interpretive data: **CHINA. Fujian:** Kuantun, 27°40'0"N 117°40'0"E, 2300m, 4.iii.1938, J. Klapperich, CNC91738.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila kiyongpa* [sic] 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11225 Rh. kiyongpa.

kubra Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Chateng 12-VI-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 91889.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Chateng, 12.vi.1959, F. Schmid, CNC91889.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila kubra* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11296 Rh. kubra.

kunma Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Rahung 25-IV-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 91771.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Rahung, 27°18'37"N

92°23'41"E, 25.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 91771.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila kunma* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11243 Rh. kunma.

kusang Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Shnongpdeng 6-XII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 91741.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia Hills District, Shnongpdeng, 25°12'26"N 92°0'35"E, 6.xii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC91741.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila kusang* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11226 Rh. kusang.

kyadongpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Lachung 2-13-VII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 235648.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Lachung, 27°41'20"N 88°44'36"E, 2-13.vii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC235648.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila kyadongpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11371 Rh. kyadongpa.

kyimdongpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Serrarim 6-7-X-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 91885.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** United Jaintia and Khasi Hills [now divided into East and West Khasi Hills Districts and East and West Jaintia Hills Districts], Serrarim, 6-7.x.1960, F. Schmid, CNC91885.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila kyimdongpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11295 Rh. kyimdongpa.

kyungpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Warongpang 21-III-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 91874.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:**

- Kameng Frontier Division [now divided into the districts of Tawang, East Kameng and West Kameng], Warongpang, 21.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC91874.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila kyungpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11286 Rh. kyungpa.
Comments: Locality possibly Warrangpam (27° 6'19"N 92°5'2"E).
- lambakanta* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: JAPAN, Nagano, Utsukushigahara May 27, 1957 R. Ishikawa / CNC 235623.
Interpretive data: JAPAN. Nagano Prefecture, Utsukushigahara, 36°13'28"N 138°7'49"E, 27.v.1957, R. Ishikawa, CNC235623.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila lambakanta* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11363 Rh. lambakanta.
- langdarma* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Dirang Dzong 21-22-VII-1961 F. Schmid / CNC 91859.
Interpretive data: INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh: West Kameng District, Derangzong, 27°20' 31"N 92°16'22"E, 21-22.vii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC91859.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila langdarma* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11266 Rh. langdarma.
- laptopsa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Sikkim Palam 25-IV-1959 F. Schmid / CNC 235608.
Interpretive data: INDIA. Sikkim: Palam, 25.iv. 1959, F. Schmid, CNC235608.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila laptopsa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11346 Rh. laptopsa.
- chembo lartsepa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Barasu 5-V-1958 F. Schmid / CNC 91909.
Interpretive data: INDIA. Uttarakhand: Pauri Garhwal District, Barasu, 30°36'5"N 79°1'45"E, 5.v.1958, F. Schmid, CNC91909.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyac. chembo lartsepa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11313 Rh. ch. lartsepa.
Comments: Description incorrectly listed year of collection as 1959.
- lepcha* Schmid 1963a, *Himalopsyche***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Inde (W.B.) Bara Hata 22-III-1959 F. Schmid / CNC 235687.
Interpretive data: INDIA. West Bengal: Bara Hata, 27°4'53.84"N 88°6'19.38"E, 22.iii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC235687.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Himalopsyche lepcha* 1963 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11427 Him. lepcha.
- lepcha* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Sikkim Zomphuk 1-X-1959 F. Schmid / CNC 235584.
Interpretive data: INDIA. Sikkim: Zomphuk, 1.x.1959, F. Schmid, CNC235584.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila lepcha* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11328 Rh. lepcha.
- lhabu* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Loni 16-VI-1960 F. Schmid / CNC 91845.
Interpretive data: INDIA. Manipur: Loni, 16.vi. 1960, F. Schmid, CNC91845.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila lhabu* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11267 Rh. lhabu.
- lhadzongpa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Rupa 1-IV-1961 F. Schmid / CNC 91724.
Interpretive data: INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh: West Kameng District, Rupa, 27°12'11.01"N 92°23'55"E, 1.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC91724.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila lhadzongpa* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11215 Rh. lhadzongpa.

lhakpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Hanuman Chatti 17-VI-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 91880.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Chamoli District, Hanuman Chatti, 30°41'41"N 79°30'51"E, 17.vi.1958, F. Schmid, CNC 91880.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila lhakpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11289 Rh. lhakpa.

lhopa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Kodaikanal 5-12-XII-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 235595.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu**: Kodaikanal, 10°14'21"N 77°29'23"E, 5-12.xii.1958, F. Schmid, CNC235595.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila lhopa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11339 Rh. lhopa.

lobsang Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Meppadi 9-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 91745.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala**: Meppadi, 11° 33'17"N 76°8'7"E, 9.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC 91745.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila lobsang* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11227 Rh. lobsang.

lonpo Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Shergaon 30-III-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 235606.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Shergaon, 27°6'18"N 92°16'20"E, 30.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 235606.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila lonpo* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11347 Rh. lonpo.

loxias Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Griechenland 1956 Olymp - Prioni 1000m, 3. -13.6. / Fr. Borchmann leg. Eingang Nr.8,1956 / CNC 91710.

Interpretive data: **GREECE**. Olymp, Prionia, 39°52'56.68"N 21°21'57.91"E, 1000m, 3-13.vi.1956, Fr. Borchmann, CNC91710.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila loxias* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11205 Rh. loxias.

lungma Schmid 1963a, *Himalopsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Jagrao 26-VI-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 235666.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Pauri Garhwal District, Jagrao, 29°13'51.79"N 79° 45'49.14"E, 26.vi.1958, F. Schmid, CNC 235666.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Himalopsyche lungma* 1963 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11422 Him. lungma.

maitreya Schmid 1963a, *Himalopsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Akhrotkoti 17-18-V-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 235685.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Pauri Garhwal District, Akhrotkoti, 17-18.v.1958, F. Schmid, CNC235685.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Himalopsyche maitreya* [sic] 1963 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11426 Him. maitreya.

maitripa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Jhum La 15-22-IX-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 235635.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: Kameng Frontier Division [now divided into the districts of Tawang, East Kameng and West Kameng], Jhum La, 15-22.ix.1961, F. Schmid, CNC235635.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila maitripa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11360 Rh. maitripa.

malenanda Schmid 1963a, *Himalopsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Tangshing 15-IV-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 235671.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Tangshing,
15.iv.1959, F. Schmid, CNC235671.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Himalopsyche male-*
nanda 1963 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11424 Him. malenanda.

manipuri Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Marou 14-VIII-1960
F.Schmid / CNC 91722.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Marou,
24°54'28"N 94°15'0"E, 14.viii.1960, F.
Schmid, CNC91722.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila manipuri*
1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11216 Rh. manipuri.

manlungpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Talung Dzong 12-V-
1961 F.Schmid / CNC 91768.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
Kameng Frontier Division [now divided into
the districts of Tawang, East Kameng and
West Kameng], Talung Dzong, 12.v.1961, F.
Schmid, CNC91768.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila man-*
lungpa 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC
No. 11244 Rh. manlungpa.

marpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Chug 25-31-VII-
1961 F.Schmid / CNC 91886.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
West Kameng District, Chug, 27°25'4"N
92°14'3"E, 25-31.vii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC
91886.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila marpa*
1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11293 Rh. marpa.

milarepa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Bombdi La [sic] 13-
21-VI-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 235581.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
West Kameng District, Bomdila, 27°15'51"N
92°24'58"E, 13-21.vi.1961, F. Schmid, CNC
235581.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila milarepa*
1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11329 Rh. milarepa.

monyulpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Chug 17-IV-1961
F.Schmid / CNC 91856.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
West Kameng District, Chug, 27°25'4"N 92°
14'3"E, 17.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC91856.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila monyul-*
pa 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11268 Rh. monyulpa.

parva mukpo Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Loni 16-VI-1960
F.Schmid / CNC 91878.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Loni,
16.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC91878.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila parva*
mukpo 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC
No. 11288 Rh. parva mukpo.

muktepa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and
Khasi Hills] Laitlyngkot 14-III-1960 F.Schmid
/ CNC 91915.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: East
Khasi Hills District, Laitlyngkot, 25°26'
44.01"N 91°50'23"E, 14.iii.1960, F. Schmid,
CNC91915.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila muktepa*
1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11319 Rh. muktepa.

Comments: The description listed the holotype
collection data as "United Jaintia and Khasi
Hills, Rumkheng, 20-23-III-1960".

nabochepa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (W.B.) Dilpa 21-III-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 91891.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. West Bengal:** Dilpa, 21.iii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC91891.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila naboche-pa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11297 Rh. naboche-pa.

naga Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Hkayam Boum 20-23-VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 91765.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Hkayam Boum, 20-23.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC91765.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila naga* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11245 Rh. naga.

nagongpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Khasi and Jaintia Hills] Muktapur 11-12-XII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 91721.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia Hills District, Muktapur, 25°9'35"N 92°7' 4"E, 11-12.xii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC91721.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila nagongpa* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11217 Rh. nagongpa.

nakpo Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Sirohi Kashong 8-VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 91858.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Sirohi Kashong, 25°6'23.19"N 94°27'28.51"E, 8.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC91858.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila nakpo* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11269 Rh. nakpo.

namgyal Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Pynter 23-I-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 91739.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** East Khasi Hills District, Pynter, 25°15'49"N 91°57' 49"E, 23.i.1960, F. Schmid, CNC91739.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila namgyal*

1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11228 Rh. namgyal.

narayani Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Kerala) Kandalur 12-XII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 235599.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala:** Kandalur, 12.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC235599.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila narayani* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11341 Rh. narayani.

netongpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Jhum La 31-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 235582.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** Kameng Frontier Division [now divided into the districts of Tawang, East Kameng and West Kameng], Jhum La, 31.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC235582.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila netongpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11330 Rh. netongpa.

nevada Schmid 1952, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Espagne (Gr.) Ht val de Lanjaron 9-IX-1950 F. Schmid / CNC 91708.

Interpretive data: **SPAIN. Granada:** Haute vallée de Lanjarón, 36°55'8"N 3°28'46"W, 9.ix.1950, F. Schmid, CNC91708.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila nevada* 1950 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11208 Rh. nevada.

Comments: Description listed day of collection as the 8th.

ngawang Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Mawlang 12-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 91740.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** East Khasi Hills District, Mawlang, 25°39'44"N 91°50'30"E, 12.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 91740.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila ngawang*
1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11229 Rh. ngawang.

ngorpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (W.B.) Shepi 23-III-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 235645.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. West Bengal**: Shepi,
27°38.59'N 88°5'6.30"E, 23.iii.1959, F.
Schmid, CNC235645.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila ngorpa*
1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11372 Rh. ngorpa.

ngulpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 female, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Gangrea 12-15-VI-1958
F.Schmid / CNC 91869.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Pauri
Garhwal District, Gangrea, 12-15.vi.1958, F.
Schmid, CNC91869.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila ngulpa*
1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11282 Rh. ngulpa.

nigrorosea Schmid 1959a, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pakistan (Chitral) Khoghozi [sic] 3-5-
X-1954 F.Schmid / CNC 91881.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Khyber
Pakhtunkhwa**: Chitral District, Kaghazi,
35°56'36.97"N 71°56'3.83"E, 3-5.x.1954, F.
Schmid, CNC91881.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila nigro-
rosea* 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11290 Rh. nigrorosea.

scissa niyampa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Sirohi Kashong 6-7-VI-
1960 F. Schmid / CNC 91756.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Sirohi Kash-
ong, 25°6'23.19"N 94°27'28.51"E, 6-7.vi.
1960, F. Schmid, CNC91756.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila scissa
niyampa* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC
No. 11235 Rh. scissa niyampa.

norbu Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and
Khasi Hills] Demthring 16-IV-1960 F.Schmid
/ CNC 91744.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: East
Khasi Hills District, Demthring, 25°33'28"N
91°54'35"E, 16.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC
91744.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila norbu*
1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11230 Rh. norbu.

nyamangpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Karponang 22-VIII-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 235587.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Karponang,
22.viii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC235587.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila nya-
mangpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC
No. 11331 Rh. nyamangpa.

nyelungpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and
Khasi Hills] Syndai 14-XII-1959 F.Schmid /
CNC 91903.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: Jaintia
Hills District, Syndai, 25°11'8.01"N 92°8'
25"E, 14.xii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC91903.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila nye-
lungpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC
No. 11308 Rh. nyelunpa [sic].

drokpa nyenpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Singbeng 26-IV-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 235653.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Singbeng,
26.iv.1959, F. Schmid, CNC235653.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila drokpa
nyenpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC
No. 11369 Rh. drokpa nyenpa.

nyerongpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Nakhu 6-VII-1961
F.Schmid / CNC 235611.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Nakhu, 27°24'9"N 92°33'38.01"E, 6.vii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 235611.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila nyeronga* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11352 Rh. nyeronga [sic].

nyerpa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Jhum La 24-25-III-1961 F. Schmid / CNC 91767.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** Kameng Frontier Division [now divided into the districts of Tawang, East Kameng and West Kameng], Jhum La, 24-25.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC91767.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila nyerpa* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11247 Rh. sherpa.

Comments: The CNC type label was accidentally switched with that of *R. sherpa*.

nyukmadongpa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Nyukmadong 23-IV-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 91847.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Nyukmadung, 27°25' 1"N 92°7'57"E, 23.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 91847.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila nyukmadongpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11270 Rh. nyukmadongpa.

philopotamoides orientis* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

Valid name: *Rhyacophila philopotamoides* McLachlan 1879

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: N.Ilva Csiki / CNC 91777.

Interpretive data: **ROMANIA.** [Carpathes orientales], N. Ilva, Csiki, CNC91777.

Determination: holotype ♂ Rh. *philopotamoides orientis* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11250 Rh. ph. orientis.

paurava* Schmid 1959a, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Cachem. et Jam. Shardi 1-13-VIII-1953 F.Schmid / CNC 91906.

Interpretive data: **PAKISTAN. Azad Jammu & Kashmir:** Shardi, 34°47'35.17"N 74°11' 10.77"E, 1-13.viii.1953, F. Schmid, CNC 91906.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila paurava* 1957 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11320 Rh. paurava.

pemba* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Tarangblang 27-XII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 91743.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia Hills District, Tarangblang, 25°11'17.01"N 92° 12'33"E, 27.xii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC91743.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila pemba* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11231 Rh. pemba.

poba* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Tangshing 15-IV-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 235642.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Tangshing, 15.iv.1959, F. Schmid, CNC235642.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila poba* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11373 Rh. poba.

polha* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Domkho 11-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 91857.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Domkho, 27°9'55"N 92°13'50.01"E, 11.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 91857.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila polha* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11271 Rh. polha.

pulchra* Schmid 1952, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Espagne (Ma.) Puerto El Paular 24-IX-1950 F. Schmid / CNC 91675.

Interpretive data: **SPAIN. Madrid:** Puerto El Paular, 40°27'19"N 3°48'20.01"W, 24.ix.1950, F. Schmid, CNC91675.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila pulcher* 1950 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11209 Rh. pulcher.

Comments: Description listed date of collection as the 23rd.

kando rengma Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Hkayam Boum 20-23-VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 235633.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Hkayam Boum, 20-23.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 235633.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila kando rengma* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11356 Rh. kando rengma.

chayulpa ringmo Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Nyukmadong 21-IV-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 91920.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Nyukmadung, 27°25' 1"N 92°7'57"E, 21.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 91920.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyac. chayulpa ringmo* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11322 Rh. ch. ringmo.

robusta Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned) (Figs 10, 11)

Verbatim: Canada, B.C. Kitchener 19-V-1965 F.Schmid / CNC 235622.

Interpretive data: **CANADA. British Columbia:** Kootenay District, Kitchener, 49°9'46"N 116° 20'30"W, 19.v.1965, F. Schmid, CNC 235622.

Determination: *Rhyacophila robusta* Schm. HOLOTYPE ♂ CNCNo. 9343-1966.

rongpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Sirohi Kashong 6-7-VI-1960 F. Schmid / CNC 235655.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Siruhi Kash

ong, 25°6'23.19"N 94°27'28.51"E, 6-7.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC235655.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila rongpa* [sic] 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11374 Rh. rongpa.

sakyapa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Tarsali 6-7-V-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 91762.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Rudraprayag District, Tarsali, 30°35'40"N 79°2'1"E, 6-7.v.1958, F. Schmid, CNC91762.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila sakyapa* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11240 Rh. sakyapa.

sanglungpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Nanga 3-4-VIII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 235602.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Nanga, 3-4.viii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC235602.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila sanglungpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11348 Rh. sanglungpa [sic].

Comments: Locality possibly Naga-Namgor (27° 32'16"N 88°37'12"E).

senggepa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Laitlyngkot 17-III-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 91846.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** East Khasi Hills District, Laitlyngkot, 25°26' 44.01"N 91°50'23"E, 17.iii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC91846.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila senggepa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11272 Rh. senggepa.

shakangpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Kumaon) Chhana 22-IX-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 235593.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Almora District, Chhana, 22.ix.1958, F. Schmid, CNC235593.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila shakangpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11342 Rh. shakangpa.

sherchokpa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Phutang 28-IX-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 235630.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Phutang, 27°14'0"N 92°14'0"E, 28.ix.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 235630.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila sherchokpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11358 Rh. sherchokpa.

angnorbui sherpa* Schmid 1963a, *Himalopsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Shingba, 27° 48'5"N 88°46'10"E, 3169m, 30.vi.1959, F. Schmid, CNC481656.

Comments: Specimen possibly lost – unique identifier added to unit tray for eventual addition to specimen. Some paratype specimens of *Himalopsyche a. angnorburi* share the collection data of the missing *H. a. sherpa* type, but all bear type labels of the nominal subspecies. One of these male paratypes is dissected and may be mislabeled, but it is impossible to determine with certainty as Schmid did not always provide a complete list of collection localities for type materials.

sherpa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Tikipchu 19-IV-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 91766.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Tikipchu, 19. iv.1959, F. Schmid, CNC91766.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila sherpa* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11246 Rh. nyerpa.

Comments: CNC type label accidentally switched with that of *R. nyerpa*.

shingripa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Chateng 28-VII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 91890.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Chateng, 28.vii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC91890.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila shingripa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11298 Rh. shingripa.

sikungpa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Akhrotkoti 17-18-V-1958 F.Schmid . CNC 91851.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Pauri Garhwal District, Akhrotkoti, 17-18.v.1958, F. Schmid, CNC91851.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila sikungpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11274 Rh. sikungpa.

simplex* Nimmo 1977, *Rhyacophila

Valid name: *Rhyacophila ophrys* Ross 1948

holotype (1 male, ethyl alcohol)

Verbatim: Ruby Ck, nr Ruby Lk, 6750', Wat.Nat.Pk, Alberta.29/6/75. D.B.Donald / CNC 165672.

Interpretive data: **CANADA. Alberta**: Waterton Lakes National Park, Bertha Lake, Ruby Ck. nr Ruby Lake, 49°6'13"N 113°58'37"W, 2057m, 29.vi.1975, D.B. Donald, CNC 165672.

Determination: *Rhyacophila simplex* Nimmo HOLOTYPE ♂ CNC No. 15160 TRICHOPTERA: RHYACOPHILIDAE.

Comments: Right-side wings on slide.

sudar Olah & Kiss 2018, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Akhrotkoti 17-18-V-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 758978.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Pauri Garhwal District, Akhrotkoti, 17-18.v.1958, F. Schmid, CNC758978.

Determination: Rh. bidens Kim. ♂ F. Schmid 1965 / *Rhyacophila sudar* sp. n. Holotype.

sumdopa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Lifakpo 29-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 91862.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:

West Kameng District, Liphakpu, 27°47'N
92°7'26"E, 29.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC91862.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila sumdopa*
1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11275 Rh. sumdopa.

tarkiya Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Sikkim Karponang 23-VIII-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 235585.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Karponang,
23.viii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC235585.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila tarkiya*
1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11332 Rh. tarkiya.

tashepa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Sikkim Chachu 21-V-1959 F.Schmid /
CNC 91737.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Chachu, 21.v.
1959, F. Schmid, CNC91737.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila tashepa*
1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11222 Rh. tashepa.

tashidingpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Lungdur 11-12-X-
1961 F.Schmid / CNC 235588.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
West Kameng District, Lungdur, 27°3'28"N
92°8'41"E, 11-12.x.1961, F. Schmid, CNC
235588.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila tashi-*
dingpa 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC
No. 11334 Rh. tashidingpa.

putata temba Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Poi 5-VII-1960 F.
Schmid / CNC 91852.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Poi, 25°16'
35"N 94°33'26"E, 5.vii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC
91852.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila putata*
temba 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11273 Rh. put. temba.

tengyelingpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Sikkim Zema 24-V-1959 F.Schmid /
CNC 91876.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Zema, 27°45'
35"N 88°32'30"E, 24.v.1959, F. Schmid,
CNC91876.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila tengye-*
ingpa 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11287 Rh. tengyelingpa.

scissoides thailandica Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Siam (Irang) Chong 29-IV-1960 E.I.
Coher / CNC 91758.
Interpretive data: **THAILAND**. Irang, Chong,
29.iv.1960, E.I. Coher, CNC91758.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila scisso-*
ides thailandica 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE
CNCNo. 11236 Rh. scissoides thailandica.

todma Schmid 1963a, *Himalopsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Phurkia 13-IX-1958 /
CNC 235672.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Pauri
Garhwal District, Phurkia, 13.ix.1958, F.
Schmid, CNC235672.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Himalopsyche todma*
1963 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11420 Him. todma.
Comments: Description incorrectly stated October
as month of collection.

tolungpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Lifakpo 15-III-1961
F.Schmid / CNC 91897.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
West Kameng District, Liphakpu, 27°47'N.
92°7'26"E, 15.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC91897.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila tolungpa*
1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11304 Rh. tolungpa.

tralala Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: U.S.A. Wash. Mason Co. Stimson Creek 3-IV-1949 D.Frechin / CNC 91729.

Interpretive data: **USA. Washington**: Mason Co. Stimson Creek, 47°25'40"N 122°54'47.01"W, 3.iv.1949, D. Frechin, CNC91729.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila tralala* 1965 F. Schmid.

trashipa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Sirohi Kashong 6-7-VI-1960 F. Schmid / CNC 235634.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Siruhi Kashong, 25°6'23.19"N 94°27'28.51"E, 6-7.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC235634.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila trashipa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11361 Rh. trashipa.

mocsaryi tredosensis* Schmid 1952, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Espagne (Lér) Val de Tredos 27-VI-1950 F. Schmid / CNC 91687.

Interpretive data: **SPAIN. Lleida**: Val de Tredos, 42°42'7"N 0°54'56.01"E, 27.vi.1950, F. Schmid, CNC91687.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila mocsari* [sic] *tredosensis* 1950 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11207 Rh. *tredosensis*.

trescaviscensis* Botoșăneanu 1960, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Bosnie Trescavica 18-20-VII-1955 F. Schmid / CNC 91831.

Interpretive data: **BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA**. Trescavica, 43°36'7.20"N 18°19'22.80"E, 18-20.vii.1955, F. Schmid, CNC 91831.

Determination: Holotype ♂ / *Rhyacophila trescaviscense* [sic] Bots. ♂ / holotype F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11433 Rh. *trescaviscensis*.

triangularis* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Hoengshan Prov. Hunan 30.10.1933. Höne / CNC 91716.

Interpretive data: **CHINA. Hunan**: Hoengshan, 30.x.1933, Höne, CNC91716.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila triangularis* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11218 Rh. *triangularis*.

trulungpa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Hilang 7-VI-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 235604.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Pauri Garhwal District, Hilang, 7.vi.1958, F. Schmid, CNC235604.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyac. trulungpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11349 Rh. *trulungpa*.

tsering* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (kerala) Kandalur 12-XII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 91747.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala**: Kandalur, 12.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC91747.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila tsering* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11233 Rh. *tsering*.

chayulpa tsetangpa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Tarsali 6-7-V-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 91918.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Rudraprayag District, Tarsali, 30°35'40"N 79°2'1"E, 6-7.v.1958, F. Schmid, CNC91918.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyac. chayulpa tsetangpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11323 Rh. *ch. tsetangpa*.

tshiringpa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned) (Figs 7-9)

Verbatim: Sikkim Talam 16-VI-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 91770.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Talam, 27°49'33"N 88°33'12"E, 16.vi.1959, F. Schmid, CNC91770.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila tshiringpa* 1965 F. Schmid.

tshogpa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Rapham 2-IV-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 235637.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Rapham, 2.iv.1959, F. Schmid, CNC235637.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila tshogpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11362 Rh. tshogpa.

tsiudmarpo* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Talung Dzong 4-5-VI-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 91860.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: Kameng Frontier Division [now divided into the districts of Tawang, East Kameng and West Kameng], Talung Dzong, 4-5.vi.1961, F. Schmid, CNC91860.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila tsiudmarpo* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 11276 Rh. tsiudmarpo.

Comments: Collection data on the specimen label differs from that in the description: "Kameng Frontier Division, Jhum La 1-2-VI-1961".

tsona* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Sirohi Kashong 6-7-VI-1960 F. Schmid / CNC 91916.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Sirohi Kashong, 25°6'23.19"N 94°27'28.51"E, 6-7.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC91916.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila tsona* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11325 Rh. tsona.

tsongkhapa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Tangshing 15-IV-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 235641.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Tangshing, 15.iv.1959, F. Schmid, CNC235641.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila tsongkhapa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11375 Rh. tsongkhapa.

tungkorpa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Tikjak 7-IV-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 91882.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Tikjak, 7.iv.1959, F. Schmid, CNC91882.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila tungkorpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11291 Rh. tungkorpa.

tungpa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Gahrwal Jungal Chatti 11-V-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 91892.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Pauri Garhwal District, Jungal Chatti, 11.v.1958, F. Schmid, CNC91892.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila tungpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11299 Rh. tungpa.

ugyenpa* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Serrarim 4-X-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 235610.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: United Jaintia and Khasi Hills [now divided into East and West Khasi Hills Districts and East and West Jaintia Hills Districts], Serrarim, 4.x.1960, F. Schmid, CNC235610.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila ugyenpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11353 Rh. ugyenpa.

unipunctata* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: U.S.A. Ore. Lane Co. Hemlock Butte Pass 10-VI-1965 F.Schmid / CNC 91821.

Interpretive data: **USA. Oregon**: Lane Co., Hemlock Butte Pass, 43°34'24"N 122°12'1"W, 10.vi.1965, F. Schmid, CNC91821.

Determination: *Rhyacophila unipunctata* Schm. HOLOTYPE ♂ CNCNo. 9344-1966.

wangpo* Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (W.B.) Khani 16-IX-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 91736.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. West Bengal**: Khani, 16.ix.1959, F. Schmid, CNC91736.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila wangpo*

- 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11221 Rh. wangpo.
Comments: The description incorrectly listed the date of collection as the 10th. Body missing, only slide-mounted abdomen present on pin.
- yarlungpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Lifakpo 15-III-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 91899.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Liphakpu, 27°4'7"N 92°7'26"E, 15.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC91899.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila yarlungpa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11307 Rh. yarlungpa.
- yatrwalla Schmid 1966** [In: Schmid & Botoşăneanu (1966)], *Himalopsyche*
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Hilang 7-VI-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 235676.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Pauri Garhwal District, Hilang, 7.vi.1958, F. Schmid, CNC235676.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Himalopsyche yatrwalla* 1963 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11416 Him. yatrwalla.
- yigrongpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Sikkim Bongteng 6-IV-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 91718.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Bongteng, 6.iv.1959, F. Schmid, CNC91718.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila yigrongpa* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11219 Rh. yigrongpa.
- yipung Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Mattiyang 17-VI-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 91720.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Mattiyang, 17.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC91720.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila yipung* 1965 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11220 Rh. yipung.
- yishepa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Sikkim Yoksam [sic] 30-IX-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 91888.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Yuksom, 27°22'21"N 88°13'22"E, 30.ix.1959, F. Schmid, CNC91888.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila yishepa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11294 Rh. yishepa.
- yonggyapa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Singkap [sic] 16-17-VIII-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 235600.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Shingkap, 24°50'54"N 94°12'11.01"E, 16-17.viii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC235600.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila yonggyapa* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11350 Rh. yonggyapa.
- yongma Schmid 1963a, *Himalopsyche***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Sikkim Tangshing 15-IV-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 235665.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Tangshing, 15.iv.1959, F. Schmid, CNC235665.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Himalopsyche yongma* 1963 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11421 Him. yongma.
- yullha Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Sikkim Gey 20-V-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 235583.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Gey, 20.v.1959, F. Schmid, CNC235583.
Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila yullha* 1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11333 Rh. yullha.
Comments: The description listed the day of collection as the 18th. Schmid was in Gey from the 18th to the 20th.
- zungpa Schmid 1970b, *Rhyacophila***
holotype (1 male, pinned)
Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Amatulla 11-III-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 235594.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:**
West Kameng District, Amatulla, 26°55'47"N
92°7'18"E, 11.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC
235594.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Rhyacophila chungpa*
1966 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11343 Rh. chungpa.

SERICOSTOMATIDAE

amudita Schmid 1991a, *Gumaga*

Valid name: *Gumaga orientalis* (Martynov 1935)
holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Khumyara 3-4-V-1958
F.Schmid / CNC 311432.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand:** Pauri
Garhwal District, Khumyara, 3-4.v.1958, F.
Schmid, CNC311432.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Gumaga amudita* 1990
F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Gumaga amudita*
CNC No. 21237.

Comments: Locality possibly Khumara (30°33'
15"N 79°3'44"W).

asambaddha Schmid 1991a, *Asahaya*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Kerala) Periyakanal 17-XII-1958
F.Schmid / CNC 311431.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala:** Periyakanal,
10°2'4"N 77°10'9"E, 17.xii.1958, F. Schmid,
CNC311431.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Asahaya asambaddha*
1990 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE *Asahaya*
asambaddha CNC No. 21237.

Comments: Description incorrectly listed date of
collection as the 18th. Two wings slide-mount-
ed on pin.

persica Schmid 1964c, *Schizopelex*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Iran (Ost.1) Ijdalam 6-X-1956
F.Schmid / CNC 311439.

Interpretive data: **IRAN. Mazandaran:**
Azhdalam, 36°56'39.24"N 50°32'57.92"E, 6.x.
1956, F. Schmid, CNC311439.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Schizopelex persica*
1963 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
12506 *Schizopelex persicus*.

STENOPSYCHIDAE

alamkrita Schmid 1969, *Stenopsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Talung Dzong 26-III-
1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236299.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:**
Kameng Frontier Division [now divided into
the districts of Tawang, East Kameng and
West Kameng], Talung Dzong, 26.iii.1961, F.
Schmid, CNC236299.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stenopsyche alamkrita*
1967 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11146 St. alamkrita.

apiguna Schmid 1969, *Stenopsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Salari 9-VII-1961
F.Schmid / CNC 236285.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:**
West Kameng District, Salari, 27°19'14.01"N
92°27'15"E, 9.vii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC
236285.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stenopsyche apiguna*
1967 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11135 St. apiguna.

dirghajihvi Schmid 1969, *Stenopsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Domkho 8-VI-1961
F.Schmid / CNC 236289.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:**
West Kameng District, Domkho, 27°9'55"N
92°13'50.01"E, 8.vi.1961, F. Schmid,
CNC236289.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stenopsyche dirgh-
ajihvi* 1968 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
11136 St. dirghajihvi.

Comments: Description incorrectly listed year of
collection as 1967.

dvyankopayukta Schmid 1969, *Stenopsyche*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Khasi and
Jaintia Hills] Thangrain 22-IV-1960 F.Schmid
/ CNC 236310.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia
Hills District, Thangrain, 25°34'48"N 92°
26'22"E, 22.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236310.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stenopsyche* dvyankopayukta 1967 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11145 St. dvyankopayukta .

haimavatika* Schmid 1969, *Stenopsyche

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Rampur 29-IV-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 236292.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Pauri Garhwal District, Rampur, 30°13'24"N 78°51'55"E, 29.iv.1958, F. Schmid, CNC236292.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Stenopsyche* haimavatika 1967 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 11137 St. haimavatika.

UENOIDAE

arcuata* Wiggins, Weaver & Unzicker 1985, *Uenoa

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Nyukmadong 22-IV-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 280243.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**: West Kameng District, Nyukmadung, 27°25'1"N 92°7'57"E, 22.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 280243.

Determination: Holotype ♂ *Uenoa* arcuata Wiggins, Weaver & Unzicker / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 19805 *Uenoa* arcuata Wiggins.

fernandoschmidi* Botoșăneanu 1979, *Uenoa

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Pauri Garhwal Kedarnath 13-15-V-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 280242.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Pauri Garhwal District, Kedarnath, 30°44'4"N 79°4'1"E, 13-15.v.1958, F. Schmid, CNC280242.

Determination: *Uenoa* fernandoschmidi ♂ Bots. / HOLOTYPE / *Uenoa* fernando-schmidi Holotype ♂ CNC 21624.

laloukesi* Schmid 1968e, *Neothremma

Valid name: *Neothremma alicia* Dodds & Hisaw 1925

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Canada, Alta. Banff N.P. Lake Louise 7-VII-1965 F.Schmid / CNC 280229.

Interpretive data: **CANADA. Alberta**: Banff National Park, Lake Louise, 51°25'30.46"N 116°10'41.46"W, 7.vii.1965, F. Schmid, CNC 280229.

Determination: HOLOTYPE ♂ CNCNo. 9648 *Neothremma laloukesi* Schm. 1967.

mostbento* Schmid 1968e, *Oligophlebodes

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: U.S.A., Ore. Linn Co. Tombstone Prairie 20-VI-1965 F.Schmid / CNC 1175648.

Interpretive data: **USA. Oregon**: Linn Co., Tombstone Prairie, 44°23'43"N 122°8'18"W, 20.vi.1965, F. Schmid, CNC1175648.

Determination: HOLOTYPE ♂ CNC No. 9647 *Oligophlebodes mostbento* Schm. 1967.

reapiri* Schmid 1968e, *Farula

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: U.S.A., Ore. Linn Co. Tombstone Prairie 20-VI-1965 F.Schmid / CNC 280228.

Interpretive data: **USA. Oregon**: Linn Co., Tombstone Prairie, 44°23'43"N 122°8'18"W, 20.vi.1965, F. Schmid, CNC280228.

Determination: HOLOTYPE ♂ CNCNo. 9648 *Farula reapiri* Schm. 1967.

zelti* Nimmo 1971, *Oligophlebodes

holotype+allotype (2 male/female, ethyl alcohol)

Verbatim: SOUTH CK., FOR.TR.Rd., S of N. Sask R. AT NORDEGG, ALTA., hab. SMALL MTN., STREAM, 9.15.p.m. 8/8/65, A.NIMMO / CNC 659735.

Interpretive data: **CANADA. Alberta**: South Creek, Forestry Trunk Road, 20 miles south of Nordegg, 52°18'57"N 116°2'18"W, 8.viii.1965, A. Nimmo, CNC659735.

Determination: HOLOTYPE ♂ CNC No. 10,589 OLIGOPHLEBODES ZELTI NIMMO / ALLOTYPIC ♀ CNC No. 10,589 OLIGOPHLEBODES ZELTI NIMMO.

Comment: Holotype and allotype each with 2 wings on slide.

XIPHOCENTRONIDAE

abhimanyu* Schmid 1982, *Drepanocentron

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Sikkim Pemayangtse 27-IV-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 236415.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Pemayangtse,
27°18'19"N 88°15'6"E, 27.iv.1959, F. Schmid,
CNC236415.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Drepanocentron*
abhimanyu 1980 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE
CNCNo. 16374 *Drepanocentron abhimanyu*
1980.

Comments: Description incorrectly listed year of
collection as 1950.

achwatirtha* Schmid 1982, *Abaria

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Kattalaimala 16-17-I-
1962 F.Schmid / CNC 236428.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Madras** [likely in either
present day Kerala or Tamil Nadu State],
Kattalaimala, 16-17.i.1962, F. Schmid, CNC2
36428.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Abaria achwatirtha*
1980 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
16381 *Abaria achwatirtha* 1980.

birghu* Schmid 1982, *Drepanocentron

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Bhairabkunda 8-III-
1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236404.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
Udalguri District, Bhairabkunda, 26°53'2"N
92°6'51"E, 8.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC236404.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Drepanocentron*
birghu 1980 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC
No. 16363 *Drepanocentron birghu* 1980.

brihadratha* Schmid 1982, *Drepanocentron

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Bhairabkunda 20-21-
X-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236409.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
Udalguri District, Bhairabkunda, 26°53'2"N
92°6'51"E, 20-21.x.1961, F. Schmid, CNC
236409.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Drepanocentron briha-*
dratha 1980 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC
No. 16368 *Drepanocentron brihadratha* 1980.

Comments: Description listed collection dates
from the 20th to the 22nd. Four wings slide-
mounted on pin.

brihaspati* Schmid 1982, *Drepanocentron

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Lushai) [=Mizo Hills] Sonai 15-
IX-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236410.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Mizoram**: Sonai,
15.ix.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236410.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Drepanocentron bri-*
haspati 1980 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC
No. 16369 *Drepanocentron brihaspati* 1980.

Comments: Four wings slide-mounted on pin.

chichupala* Schmid 1982, *Melanotrichia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Kerala) Kandalur 31-I-1962
F.Schmid / CNC 236374.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala**: Kandalur,
31.i.1962, F. Schmid, CNC236374.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Mel. pachupati* 1979
F. Schmid [misabeled] / Holotype *Melano-*
trichia chichupala Sch. Det. O. Lonsdale /
CNCNo. 16338 *Mel. chichupala* 1980 HOLO-
TYPE.

Comments: Three wings slide-mounted on pin.

citrangada* Schmid 1982, *Drepanocentron

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Shergaon 8-V-1961
F.Schmid / CNC 236414.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
West Kameng District, Shergaon, 27°6'18"N
92°16'20"E, 8.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC
236414.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Drepanocentron cit-*
rangada 1980 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC
No. 16373 *Drepanocentron citrangada* 1980.

dacharatha* Schmid 1982, *Drepanocentron

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Sikkim Lathong 15-V-1959 F.Schmid /
CNC 236416.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Lathong,
27°39'40"N 88°36'5"E, 15.v.1959, F. Schmid,
CNC236416.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Drepanocentron dach-*
aratha 1980 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo.
16375 *Drepanocentron dacharatha* 1980.

devavrata* Schmid 1982, *Abaria

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: U.J.K.H. [=United Khasi and Jaintia Hills] Syndai 25-XII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236429.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: Jaintia Hills District, Syndai, 25°11'8.01"N 92°8'25"E, 25.xii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236429.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Abaria devavrata* 1980 F.Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 1683 *Abaria devavrata* 1980.

Comments: Description listed date of collection as 14.xii.1959; in December 1959, Schmid visited this locality from the 14th to the 16th, and the 25th and the 26th. Four wings on one slide on pin, some remaining body parts on second slide on same pin, remainder of body including head missing.

devayani* Schmid 1982, *Cnodocentron

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Laitlyngkot 16-III-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236391.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: East Khasi Hills District, Laitlyngkot, 25°26'44.01"N 91°50'23"E, 16.iii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 236391.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Cnodocentron devayani* 1980 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 16351 *Cnodocentron devayani* 1980 HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

dhananjaya* Schmid 1982, *Melanotrichia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Sohkhā 7-XII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236382.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: Jaintia Hills District, Sohkhā, 25°12'30"N 92°2'26.01"E, 7.xii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236382.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Mel. dhananjaya* 1979 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 16342 *Mel. dhananjaya* 1980 HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

druhyu* Schmid 1982, *Drepanocentron

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Marou 14-VIII-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236411.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Marou, 24°54'28"N 94°15'0"E, 14.viii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236411.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Drepanocentron druhyu* 1980 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 16370 *Drepanocentron druhyu* 1980.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

drupada* Schmid 1982, *Melanotrichia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Aishi 25-VII-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236381.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Aishi, 24°47'23"N 94°34'31"E, 25.vii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236381.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Mel. drupada* 1979 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 16345 *Mel. drupada* 1980 HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

dusyanta* Schmid 1982, *Abaria

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Kunjankhuzi 2-I-1962 F.Schmid / CNC 236423.

Interpretive data: **INDIA**. Madras [likely in either present day Kerala or Tamil Nadu State], Kunjankhuzi, 2.i.1962, F. Schmid, CNC 236423.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Abaria dusyanta* 1980 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 16382 *Abaria dusyanta* 1980.

Comments: Four wings slide-mounted on pin, remainder of body mounted on second slide on same pin.

dvaravati* Schmid 1982, *Drepanocentron

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Sirohi 26-VI-1960 F. Schmid / CNC 236407.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Sirohi, 25°6'23.19"N 94°27'28.51"E, 26.vi.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236407.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Drepanocentron dvaravati* 1980 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 16366 *Drepanocentron dvaravati* 1980.

Comments: Four wings slide-mounted on pin.

girika* Schmid 1982, *Cnodocentron

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Rahung 25-IV-1961
F.Schmid / CNC 236390.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
West Kameng District, Rahung, 27°18'37"N
92°23'41"E, 25.iv.1961, F. Schmid, CNC
236390.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Cnodocentron girika*
1980 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 16349 *Cnodocentron girika* 1980 HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

haryachwa* Schmid 1982, *Drepanocentron

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (W.B.) Git Dabling [sic] 13-IX-
1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236418.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. West Bengal**: Git
Dubling, 27°3'13"N 88°35'51"E, 13.ix.1959,
F. Schmid, CNC236418.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Drepanocentron haryachwa*
1980 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC
No. 16377 *Drepanocentron haryachwa* 1980.

ikchvaku* Schmid 1982, *Melanotrichia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and
Khasi Hills] Thangrain 22-IV-1960 F.Schmid /
CNC 236386.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: Jaintia
Hills District, Thangrain, 25°34'48"N 92°26'
22"E, 22.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236386.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Mel. ikchvaku* 1979 F.
Schmid / CNCNo. 16347 *Mel. ikchvaku* 1980
HOLOTYPE.

jamadagni* Schmid 1982, *Melanotrichia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Songpekmun 1-IX-
1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236384.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Suang-
pekmun, 24°20'7"N 93°17'18"E, 1.ix.1960, F.
Schmid, CNC236384.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Mel. jamadagni* 1979
F. Schmid / CNCNo. 16346 *Mel. jamadagni*
1980 HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

janamejaya* Schmid 1982, *Melanotrichia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Khasi and
Jaintia Hills] Syndai 14-XII-1959 F.Schmid /
CNC 236380.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: Jaintia
Hills District, Syndai, 25°11'8.01"N 92°8'
25"E, 14.xii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236380.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Mel. janamejaya* [sic]
1979 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 16344 *Mel.*
janamejaya 1980 HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

kachika* Schmid 1982, *Melanotrichia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Pamjai 31-VIII-1960
F.Schmid / CNC 236378.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Pamjai,
31.viii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236378.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Mel. kachika* 1979 F.
Schmid / CNCNo. 16340 *Mel. kachika* 1980
HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

madhavi* Schmid 1982, *Abaria

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Bhairabkunda 3-4, 7-
III-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236425.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
Udalguri District, Bhairabkunda, 26°53'2"N
92°6'51"E, 3-4, 7.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC
236425.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Abaria madhavi* 1980
F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 16387
Abaria madhavi 1980.

Comments: Three wings slide-mounted on pin.

nahucha* Schmid 1982, *Drepanocentron

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Lagairong 26-V-1960
F.Schmid / CNC 236406.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Lagairong,
24°42'0"N 93°32'0"E, 26.v.1960, F. Schmid,
CNC236406.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Drepanocentron*
nahucha 1980 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC
No. 16364 *Drepanocentron nahucha* 1980.

Comments: Four wings slide-mounted on two
slides on pin.

pachupati* Schmid 1982, *Melanotrichia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Devala 8-I-1959
F.Schmid / CNC 236376.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu**: Devala,
11°28'21"N 76°22'55"E, 8.i.1959, F. Schmid,
CNC236376.

Determination: holotype ♂ Mel. *pachupati* 1979
F. Schmid / CNCNo. 16335 Mel. *pachupati*
1980 HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

prajapati* Schmid 1982, *Melanotrichia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Bhairabkunda 5-6-
III-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236379.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh**:
Udalguri District, Bhairabkunda, 26°53'2"N
92°6'51"E, 5-6.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC
236379.

Determination: holotype ♂ Mel. *prajapati* 1979 F.
Schmid / CNCNo. 16341 Mel. *prajapati* 1980
HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

prathamajam* Schmid 1982, *Proxiphocentron

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Sirwani 1-V-1959 F.Schmid /
CNC 236373.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Sirwani,
1.v.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236373.

Determination: holotype ♂ Proxiph. *prathamajam*
1980 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 16379 Proxi-
phocentron *prathamajam* HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin, re-
mainder of body mounted on second slide on
same pin.

puru* Schmid 1982, *Abaria

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Kumaon) Sarju 20-IX-1958
F.Schmid / CNC 236427.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Uttarakhand**: Almora
District, Sarju, 20.ix.1958, F. Schmid, CNC
236427.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Abaria puru* 1980 F.
Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 16386 *Abaria*
puru 16386.

Comments: Four wings slide-mounted on pin,
remainder of body mounted on second slide on
same pin.

radhasuta* Schmid 1982, *Melanotrichia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and
Khasi Hills] Serrarim 4-X-1960 F.Schmid /
CNC 236388.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya**: United
Jaintia and Khasi Hills [now divided into East
and West Khasi Hills Districts and East and
West Jaintia Hills Districts], Serrarim,
4.x.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236388.

Determination: holotype ♂ Mel. *radhasuta* 1979
F. Schmid / CNCNo. 16348 Mel. *radhasuta*
1980 HOLOTYPE.

Comments: The description listed the collection
date as 6-7.x.1960, a second period during
which Schmid was at Serrarim. Two wings
slide-mounted on pin.

richika* Schmid 1982, *Abaria

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Sikkim Mabong 23-IX-1959 F.Schmid
/ CNC 236421.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim**: Mabong, 27°
10'33"N 88°18'10"E, 23.ix.1959, F. Schmid,
CNC236421.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Abaria richika* 1980 F.
Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 16385 *Abaria*
richika 1980.

Comments: Four wings slide-mounted on pin,
genitalia and part of thorax on second slide on
same pin.

sarmichta* Schmid 1982, *Drepanocentron

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Poi 5-VII-1960 F.
Schmid / CNC 236413.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur**: Poi, 25°
16'35"N 94°33'26"E, 5.vii.1960, F. Schmid,
CNC236413.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Drepanocentron sar-*
michta 1980 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC
No. 16372 *Drepanocentron sarmichta* 1980.

Comments: Four wings slide-mounted on two
slides on pin.

satrajita Schmid 1982, Drepanocentron

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Mawlang 12-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236403.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** East Khasi Hills District, Mawlang, 25°39'44"N 91°50'30"E, 12.iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC 236403.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Drepanocentron satrajita* 1980 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 16362 *Drepanocentron satrajita* 1980.

Comments: Four wings slide-mounted on pin.

satyavati Schmid 1982, Drepanocentron

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Sohkharam 10-XII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236419.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** United Jaintia and Khasi Hills [now divided into East and West Khasi Hills Districts and East and West Jaintia Hills Districts], Sohkharam, 10.xii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236419.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Drepanocentron satyavati* 1980 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 16378 *Drepanocentron satyawati* [sic] 1980.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

tchaturbhujia Schmid 1982, Cnodocentron

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Sikkim Ligship [sic] 25-IX-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236393.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Legship, 27° 16'46"N 88°16'29"E, 25.ix.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236393.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Cnodocentron 4-bhujia* 1980 F. Schmid / CNC No. 16352 *Cnodocentron 4-bhujia* 1980 HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Four wings slide-mounted on pin.

turvasu Schmid 1982, Drepanocentron

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Chattrik 23-VII-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236412.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Chattrik, 24°57'29.01"N 94°37'12"E, 23.vii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236412.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Drepanocentron turvasu* 1980 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 16371 *Drepanocentron turvasu* 1980.

Comments: Four wings slide-mounted on pin.

uchinara Schmid 1982, Abaria

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Sikkim Manu 10-V-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236426.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Sikkim:** Manu, 27° 31'2"N 88°34'58"E, 10.v.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236426.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Abaria uchinara* 1980 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 16384 *Abaria uchinara* 1980.

Comments: Four wings slide-mounted on pin, remainder of body mounted on second slide on same pin.

ugrasena Schmid 1982, Drepanocentron

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Manipur) Huiahu [sic] 3-VII-1960 / CNC 236408.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Manipur:** Huishu, 25°12'47.01"N 94°33'10"E, 3.vii.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236408.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Drepanocentron ugrasena* 1980 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNC No. 16367 *Drepanocentron ugrasena* 1980.

Comments: Four wings slide-mounted on pin, genitalic slide missing.

uparichara Schmid 1982, Melanotrichia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Khasi and Jaintia Hills] Muktapur 11-12-XII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236377.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia Hills District, Muktapur, 25°9'35"N 92°7' 54"E, 11-12.xii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236377.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Mel. uparichara* 1979 F. Schmid / CNC No. 16337 *Mel. uparichara* 1980 HOLOTYPE.

Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.

vasudeva Schmid 1982, Melanotrichia

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (U.D.M.N.C.H.) [=United district

- of Mikir Hills and North Cachar] Langtrang 30-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236387.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Assam:** [United District now treated as separate Mikir Hills and Karbi Anglong Districts], Langtrang, 30. iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236387.
Determination: holotype ♂ Mel. vasudeva 1979 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 16336 Mel. vasudeva 1980 HOLOTYPE.
Comments: Four wings slide-mounted on pin.
- vichvamitra Schmid 1982, Melanotrichia**
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Musianglamare 9-I-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236383.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia Hills District, Musianglamare, 9.i.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236383.
Determination: holotype ♂ Mel. vichvamitra 1979 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 16343 Mel. vichvamitra 1980 HOLOTYPE.
Comments: Description listed type locality as "Musanglamare". Two wings slide-mounted on pin.
- vicitravirya Schmid 1982, Drepanocentron**
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Bohar [sic] 13-III-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236417.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Boha, 27°12'N 92°9'54"E, 13.iii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC236417.
Determination: holotype ♂ Drepanocentron vicitravirya 1980 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 16376 Drepanocentron vicitravirya 1980.
Comments: Four wings slide-mounted on two slides on pin.
- vrissaparvan Schmid 1982, Cnodocentron**
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Rupa 3-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236392.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Rupa, 27°12'11.01"N 92°23'55"E, 3.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 236392.
Determination: holotype ♂ Cnodocentron vrissaparvan 1980 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 16350 Cnodocentron vrissaparvan 1980 HOLOTYPE.
Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.
- yadu Schmid 1982, Melanotrichia**
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Assam (Kameng) Rupa 3-V-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 236385.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Arunachal Pradesh:** West Kameng District, Rupa, 27°12'11.01"N 92°23'55"E, 3.v.1961, F. Schmid, CNC 236385.
Determination: holotype ♂ Mel. yadu 1979 F. Schmid / CNCNo. 16339 Mel. yadu 1980 HOLOTYPE.
Comments: Two wings slide-mounted on pin.
- yakcha Schmid 1982, Abaria**
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (U.D.M.N.C.H.) [=United district of Mikir Hills and North Cachar] Umbaso 26-IV-1960 F.Schmid / CNC 236424.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Assam:** Karbi Anglong District, Umbaso, 25°43'48"N 92°31'34"E, 26. iv.1960, F. Schmid, CNC236424.
Determination: holotype ♂ Abaria yakcha 1980 F. Schmid / HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 16381 Abaria yakcha 1980.
Comments: Four wings slide-mounted on pin.
- yayati Schmid 1982, Drepanocentron**
holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)
Verbatim: Inde (U.J.K.H.) [=United Jaintia and Khasi Hills] Laremshiap 17-XII-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 236405.
Interpretive data: **INDIA. Meghalaya:** Jaintia Hills District, Larem Shyiap, 25°10'46"N 92°11'55"E, 17.xii.1959, F. Schmid, CNC236405.
Determination: holotype ♂ Drepanocentron yayati 1980 F. Schmid HOLOTYPE CNCNo. 16365 Drepanocentron yayati 1980.
Comments: Description incorrectly listed date of collection as the 16th.

FOSSIL SPECIES

cretacica Botoșăneanu & Wichard 1983, *Electralberta*

holotype (1 male, fossil:amber)

Verbatim: CAS 420 / TRICHOPTERA Polycentropodidae MEDICINE HAT ALTA JULY 8-11 1971 J.F.McALPINE.

Interpretive data: **CANADA. Alberta**: Grassy Lake, near Medicine Hat, 49°46'39"N 111°41'39"W, amber collected from tailings at open pit coal measure, 8-11.vii.1971, J.F. McAlpine, CAS420.

Determination: HOLOTYPE / Trichoptera: *Electralberta cretacica* Botosaneanu ♂ holotype.

Comments: Upper Cretaceous, Belly River Series, Foremost Formation. Details of type locality derived from Lonsdale & Locke (2018).

EXTANT SPECIES NOT CLASSIFIED TO FAMILY

didinki Schmid 1993c, *Karomana*

holotype (1 male, pinned)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Senbaganur 3-8-XII-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 311461.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu**: Senbaganur, 10°13'59.01"N 77°30'49"E, 3-8.xii.1958, F. Schmid, CNC311461.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Karomana didinki* 1992 F.Schmid / *Karomana didinki* Schm CNC1566.

Comments: Four wings slide-mounted on pin, remainder of body mounted on second slide on same pin.

elwe Schmid 1993c, *Ngoya*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Kerala) Velela Mudi 15-XII-1961 F.Schmid / CNC 311463.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala**: Vellala Mudi, 15.xii.1961, F. Schmid, CNC311463.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Ngoya elwe* 1992 F. Schmid / *Ngoya elwe* Schm. CNC 21569.

lafcadiello Schmid 1993c, *Mpuga*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Devala 8-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311448.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Tamil Nadu**: Devala, 11°28'21"N 76°22'55"E, 8.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311448.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Mpuga lafcadiello* 1992 F. Schmid / *Mpuga lafcadiello* Schm. CNC 21568.

lafcadio Schmid 1993c, *Mpuga*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Attikati 22-XII-1958 F.Schmid / CNC 311449.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Karnataka**: Attikati, 22.xii.1958, F. Schmid, CNC311449.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Mpuga lafcadio* 1992 F. Schmid / *Mpuga lafcadio* Schm CNC 21567.

olwe Schmid 1993c, *Ngoya*

holotype (1 male, pinned: minuten)

Verbatim: Inde (Madras) Meppadi 9-I-1959 F.Schmid / CNC 311426.

Interpretive data: **INDIA. Kerala**: Meppadi, 11°33'17"N 76°8'7"E, 9.i.1959, F. Schmid, CNC311462.

Determination: holotype ♂ *Ngoya olwe* 1992 F. Schmid / *Ngoya olwe* Schm. CNC 21570.

Acknowledgements – Oliver Flint Jr. provided information on the deposition of Schmid material in the ROM and the USNM. Many of the details regarding Fernand Schmid's life were derived from conversations with family members Noelle Harris and Sean Cahill, who are thanked for their time and encouragement. Figures 15 and 16 belong to the CNC archives; the remaining images of Schmid, his field photos and the scanned image of his field notes belong to the personal archives of Noelle Harris and are reprinted with permission. Specimen photographs of all pinned types of Trichoptera in the CNC were taken by Mariah Fleck and are copyright of Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada. Sonia Gagnon translated some of the passages in Schmid's field notes. Some localities in Asia were geocoded by Vazrick Nazari, Pritha Dey and Mohandas Giriyaappa. Comments provided by reviewers J. Oláh and J. Morse were much appreciated.

This paper is dedicated to Oliver Flint Jr. and his wonderful wife Carol, who went out of their way to make this Canadian author feel at home during his postdoctoral fellowship in Washington, D.C. Ollie was a giant of Trichoptera research and a specialist of many other interesting and mostly aquatic groups. He passed away in May 2019 and is deeply missed.

Figures 1–2. *Leptocerus sukhabddha* Schmid, holotype male; 1 = lateral; 2 = labels.
Figures 3–4. *Psilotreta schmidi* Parker & Wiggins, holotype male; 3 = dorsal; 4 = labels.
Figures 5–6. *Paraphlegopteryx schmidi* Weaver, holotype male; 5 = lateral; 6 = labels.

Figures 7–9. *Rhyacophila tshiringpa* Schmid, holotype male; 7 = dorsal; 8 = lateral; 9: labels. **Figures 10–11.** *Rhyacophila robusta* Schmid; 10 = lateral; 11 = labels. **Figures 12–13.** *Himalopsyche angnorbui* Schmid; 12 = dorsal; 13 = labels.

Figures 14–18. Fernand Schmid; 14 = Fernand, characteristically relaxing with his pipe at his cottage in Wakefield, Quebec; 15 = an early departmental photo in Ottawa; 16 = a later photograph from 1990; 17 = Fernand on his motorcycle on his Spanish expedition in 1950; 18 = Fernand (left) collecting in Spain with an associate.

Figures 19–27. Field photos taken by Fernand Schmid; 19 = Pakistan, Jaffarabad (1953 or 1954); 20 = India, Uttarakhand, Laxman Jhula, near Rishikesh, along the Ganges (March 1958); 21 = Uttarakhand, Rishikesh, marker along road (March 1958); 22–24 = Uttarakhand: Rudraprayag (May 1958); 25 = Karnataka: Kakankote (January 1959); 26 = Kerala, Meppadi (January 1959); 27 = Karnataka: Yodpai (January 1959).

Figures 28-34: Field photos taken by Fernand Schmid; 28 = Madhya Pradesh, Satonwada (1959 or 1961); 29-33 = Assam, unknown localities; 34 = Kerala, Vellala Mudi (December 1961). Figure 34 = A page from one of Schmid's field books, this one detailing collection localities in Manipur in July 1960.

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